

D5.2

Technical evaluation and demonstration of the UCs

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
4G	4 th Generation of mobile technology standards
5G	5 th Generation of mobile technology standards
5G SA	5G Standalone
AD	Automated Driving
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BTP	Basic Transport Protocol
C-ACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CMR	Cooperative Manoeuvre Recommender
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CRE	Collision Risk Estimator
CV	Connected Vehicle
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DR	Dead Reckoning
DT	Digital Twin
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Emergency Vehicle
gNB	(next) generation NodeB (5 th generation base station)
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GW	Gateway

HD	High Definition
HMI	Human Machine Interface
I2V	Infrastructure-to-Vehicle
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IMA	Integrity Measurement Architecture
IP	Internet Protocol
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITS-G5	European standard for vehicular communications based on the IEEE-1609. X and IEEE-802.11p standards
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LL	Living Lab
LTE-PC5	LTE interface PC5
MAPEM	MAP (topology) Extended Message
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MCS	Modulation and Coding Schemes
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MEC-ES1	MEC in area Spain 1 (UC3 testbed)
MEC-ES2	MEC in area Spain 2 (UC3 testbed)
MEC-FR	MEC in area France (UC3 testbed)
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NAT	Network Address Translator
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OBU	On-Board Unit
ODD	Operational Design Domain
O-D	Origin-Destination
PC	Personal Computer
PC5	5G reference point for direct communications between UEs
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure

PDR	Packet Delivery Ratio
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
RMT	Risk Management in Tunnel
RSU	Roadside Unit
RTCM	Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
SA	Standalone
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SEN	Service Edge Node
SIA	Software Integrity Architecture
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SPATEM	Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message
SPU	Sensor Processing Unit
TCG	Trusted Computing Group
TCP	Transport Control Protocol
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TMS	Traffic Management System
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
Uu	LTE/5G radio interface
V2I2V	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure-to-Vehicle
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VA	Video Analytics
VAM	VRU Awareness Message
VIMA	VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistance
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

PoDIUM aims to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure to address the challenges in road automation and telecommunications, especially those linked with connectivity, cooperation, data management, interoperability and reliability, trust and data truthfulness, in order to foster the development of advanced Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions.

This deliverable presents the technical evaluation and demonstration of the Use Cases, providing evidence of their implementation and performance in the context of the PoDIUM platform. Furthermore, it presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) together with their analysis and conclusions, offering a comprehensive view of the outcomes achieved.

The main conclusions for each Living Lab and Use Case can be summarised as follows:

German Living Lab, Use Case 1 (UC1):

UC1 demonstrates the value of a cooperative local environment model for handling complex urban traffic situations, contributing directly to European safety and efficiency objectives. The use case assesses heterogeneous communication technologies, including 5G cm/mmWave and 60 GHz WiFi, to ensure high availability and redundancy. Two scenarios were evaluated: cooperative manoeuvres between Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) when facing an obstacle, using either vehicle-only data or enhanced infrastructure support, and a second scenario focusing on Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection with infrastructure-assisted sensing. All needs identified in D2.1 were addressed, from accurate local environment modelling to reliable connectivity and the integration of connected vehicles and VRUs. Key challenges, such as occlusion, data quality, heterogeneous communication channels, and cooperative planning, were successfully mitigated. Significant technical effort centred on implementing a hardware-based multi-connectivity scheduler capable of robust packet duplication and deduplication across diverse communication links. The work also highlighted the importance of using standardized messages for coordination between server-side and vehicle-side planners. Overall, UC1 achieved its strategic goals, demonstrating effective cooperative corridor management, improved traffic efficiency, enhanced service availability in occluded areas, and strengthened VRU protection. The results further indicate that lightweight deployments based solely on road-user data can be viable, while hardware-supported redundancy mechanisms remain essential for reliable high-throughput communication.

Spanish Living Lab, Use Case 2 (UC2):

UC2 successfully validated the PoDIUM architecture in Barcelona's dense urban environment, while automated driving tests were also successfully conducted at the UTAC circuit. Key challenges addressed include optimising traffic management decisions using cloud-based Digital Twins, ensuring reliable emergency vehicle priority with minimal impact on overall traffic flow, and maintaining high VRU protection levels under dense, dynamic, and safety-critical urban conditions. The platform demonstrated robust performance, achieving the highest levels of availability and communication reliability. In the emergency vehicle prioritisation scenario, the dynamic system increased the probability of receiving a green light while reducing traffic disruption to crossing traffic, compared to existing static methods. The system also proved its ability to perform successful cooperative manoeuvres with Connected Vehicles (CVs) and CAVs. In the second scenario, the traffic optimisation capabilities were confirmed, by correctly processing most vehicle trips for real-time monitoring and enabling rerouting in the event of an incident along the vehicles' routes. Furthermore, VRU protection mechanisms were highly effective in increasing the safety margin and enabling vehicles to react more smoothly and safely and reducing deceleration intensity. These results confirm the ability of the hybrid Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) to enhance safety and efficiency in complex urban areas.

Spanish Living Lab, Use Case 3 (UC3):

UC3 successfully validated the PoDIUM architecture in a real highway environment along the C32 near Barcelona, demonstrating the platform's capacity to support cooperative services for CVs operating under real-world day-time traffic conditions. Key challenges included the real-time generation and dissemination of safety and traffic optimisation strategies under dynamic conditions, and the enablement of scalable, collaborative CCAM services across borders to support informed traffic management and congestion reduction. The use case focused on the delivery and execution of traffic strategies, such as speed reduction, lane avoidance, and hazard alerts, based on real-time inputs from roadside perception systems and vehicle-reported data processed by the PoDIUM Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) platform. Strategy computation and the transmission of IVIM and DENM messages remained consistently within operational targets, confirming a robust and stable communication chain between roadside units, the MEC, and in-vehicle systems. Even though automated vehicle tests could not be performed due to national regulatory constraints, UC3 validated the full cooperative workflow using CVs, proving that human drivers effectively receive and implement strategies prompted by the system's multi-modal HMI. These empirical results confirm that the PoDIUM hybrid physical and digital infrastructure is technically ready for cross-border CCAM operations, providing a solid foundation for future large-scale deployment across Spanish and European highway networks.

Italian Living Lab, Use Case 4 (UC4):

Use Case 4 demonstrates an infrastructure-based application that assists CAVs at urban intersections while protecting VRUs. Key challenges include ensuring trustworthy and reliable data through advanced trust and integrity mechanisms and heterogeneous-source fusion, while guaranteeing compliance with hybrid communication paradigms and seamless interoperability between short-range and cellular technologies under current standards. Deployed in Turin, the system fuses trusted data from multiple sources, including roadside sensors, vehicle sensors, VRU smartphone app, Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) infrastructure, and traffic lights through a digital twin. It then provides guidance to the CAVs and connected VRUs to safely go across a busy urban intersection. The Use Case demonstrates that the digital infrastructure can provide the necessary information to road users to improve safety at intersections. This necessary information is not only trustworthy, thanks to the protection of nodes against integrity attacks, but also true, given the redundancy of data sources as many sensors are available, such as vehicle sensors, RSU sensors, VRU app published data, etc, the resulting data is more reliable than single-source data.

Italian Living Lab, Use Case 5 (UC5):

UC5 successfully enhanced safety and cooperative awareness within the Brenner Motorway tunnel, a challenging environment where the absence of satellite positioning required innovative technical solutions and highlighted key challenges related to multi-source data integration, accurate risk assessment and reliable communication. By integrating roadside sensors with a digital twin, the system monitored traffic and roadworks in real time, enabling dynamic risk evaluation based on validated data and generating actionable warnings that allowed both CAVs and CVs to adapt speed and lane selection effectively. To maintain continuous positioning inside the tunnel, the project relied on a sophisticated fusion of trilateration, dead reckoning and onboard sensor data, while ensuring stable communication between infrastructure, vehicles and RSUs despite signal degradation. Trials confirmed that data synchronization and communication strategies supported safe manoeuvring in mixed traffic scenarios, even when non-connected vehicles disrupted shared perception, and demonstrated the successful deployment of RSUs and sensors under legal and technical constraints, with regulatory compliance no longer constituting a challenge due to the characteristics of the selected test site.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UCs) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of three well-equipped Living Labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy, and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for the availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) platform. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability, and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards Digital Twins (DTs).
- New Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust, and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange, and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The aim of PoDIUM is to enhance CCAM services in Europe. To reach this goal the project focuses on the development and integration of the PDI needed to ensure the vehicle's connectivity via certain network technologies. A total of five PoDIUM UCs will be tested and validated under real-life conditions in the three LLs, located in Germany, Spain, and Italy. These UCs require advancing several technologies and elements that will be integrated under the common PoDIUM architecture. Previous deliverables explained the development of the technologies (WP3) and the Living Labs integration and data collection (WP4).

The main objective of Deliverable D5.2 is to report the results of the technical evaluation of the PoDIUM UCs. The report documents also the demonstration activities carried out in the three Living Labs.

1.3. Intended audience

This deliverable is classified as "Public", therefore, it will be uploaded on the PoDIUM website, where it will be available for all project partners and any interested readers, such as stakeholders and experts involved in the development of CCAM systems. Nevertheless, the consortium members are the main intended audience of this document.

1.4. Structure of the document and its relationship to other work packages/deliverables

The document is structured per Use Case (UC) basis, each one having the following sections:

- A description of the use case, split into several individual scenarios.
- Where applicable, a summary of integration actions completed between the submission of D4.2 [5] and the present deliverable, along with an overview of updates to the original plan.
- A description of the demonstration activities conducted, together with the associated data collection efforts.
- The results of the trials, including the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) values and the corresponding conclusions.

This deliverable D5.2 builds on the integration activities completed in WP4 and presents the results and analysis of the final demonstrations and data acquisition from a fully technical perspective. In parallel, Deliverable D5.3, produced within the same work package, complements this view by addressing the user perspective on the technological developments and reporting on the public acceptance and impact assessment of the PoDIUM solutions.

2. Use Case 1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm

2.1. Introduction to the UC

Use Case 1 explores the benefits of a cooperative local environment model and a cooperative planner for managing complex urban traffic situations with the goal to support the ambitious EU safety and environmental targets by improving road safety and efficiency. The focus is on corridor management in situations where not all lanes of a road are available, e.g., when one is blocked by a stopped vehicle. Various situations are considered in which an obstacle on one lane needs to be passed by traffic arriving simultaneously from both directions sharing the only remaining lane. For example, the situation with two vehicles that only have their onboard sensors available or one vehicle and one cyclist for which infrastructure sensors are available. To improve communication availability and reliability, UC1 also includes different communication technologies (5G mobile network with cm- and mm-wave and 60 GHz WiFi) that are realized and assessed.

The global architecture of the UC1 and its main functional components, which have already been described in D3.3 [3], are illustrated in Figure 1 for ease of reference in this document.

Figure 1: UC1 functional diagram.

2.2. Demonstration activities and data collection

UC validation has undergone multiple phases, including pre-tests (documented in deliverable D4.2 [5]), definitive tests to obtain the KPIs, and the final demonstration. The layout and the configuration of the different elements of the testbed are detailed in D4.2 [5]. During the pre-tests, UC1 components were evaluated individually or through trials conducted with stationary vehicles. The definitive tests, with all components integrated, were conducted with the UC validations scenarios documented in deliverable D5.1 [6].

The definitive test to obtain the KPIs were performed in the following dates: 08.04.2025, 20.05.2025, 14.07.2025, 18.08.2025. The final demonstration of UC1 was conducted on the 09.04.2025. The vehicles used for the tests are shown in Figure 2, while the driven routes can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 2: UULM and Bosch CAV at the final demonstration of UC1.

Figure 3: Route of vehicles during the tests. Map data from OpenStreetMap <https://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=18/48.433027/9.968669>.

During the execution of the UC1 tests, multiple datasets were collected and stored in a repository. Table 69 of the Annex outlines the whole set of logged parameters and the links to access them. These data have been collected in the logging points indicated in Figure 4 and following the guiding lines of D4.1 [4].

Figure 4: Logging points in the UC1's functional diagram according to D4.1 [4].

In addition to all logs, a README guide to the structure of the data logs as well as the computation methods to obtain the trial results are stored in the Zenodo repository given in Table 2 of the Annex.

In the following we provide an overview of the zipped folders in the repository:

- The logs for KPI_UC1_1 are located in the folder *UC1_KPI_1_CAV* with CAV and MEC logs named correspondingly.
- The logs for KPI_UC1_2 are located in the folder *UC1_KPI_2_VRU* with CAV and MEC logs named correspondingly.
- The logs for KPI_UC1_3 are located in the folder *UC1_KPI_3*, with *cav-log.pcap* and *mec-log.pcap* being the logs for all packets captured at the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) and the MEC, respectively.
- The logs for KPI_P_1 and KPI_P_4 are given together with evaluation scripts in the folder *UC1_KPI_P1_P4*.
- KPI_P_2 is given in *UC1_KPI_P2* and KPI_P_3 and KPI_P_5 are located together in the folder *UC1_KPI_P3_P5*.

2.3. Trial Results

In this section, we present the results of the Test Cases proposed for UC1 in D5.1 [4]. The results have been obtained through analysis of the previous data sets.

2.3.1. Test Case for KPI_P_1 Service Availability in UC1

In UC1, the service availability is defined as the percentage of time the platform service is working during definitive tests. The availability of the platform services is recorded during experiments when at least one connected road user is within the use case pilot area.

Method of calculation

Recording of platform service message is triggered when an experiment is started. Each module of the platform outputs data and log messages with at least 1Hz when working. The recordings contain the published data and log messages over time. The total time is the sum of all recording durations. The downtime has been computed as the sum of time intervals where at least one module missed publishing its availability for more than 5 seconds.

Table 1: TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC1.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC1			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_P_1 service Availability in UC1			
Descriptive Statistics	Total time	Downtime	Availability	
	1697s	0s	100.0%	

Conclusions

The service availability during the definitive test was 100%, as no outage occurred on the platform itself or any of the three service modules. The verification criterion required service availability of at least 95%, which was fulfilled. The robustness of both the platform and the deployed services enabled the successful evaluation and demonstration of the use case.

2.3.2. Test Case for KPI_P_2 Update Latency in UC1

In UC1, the Update Latency is defined as the time between the detection of a road user and its availability in the Digital Twin. This Update Latency is composed of: latency of the road user detection by the Sensor Processing Unit (SPU) (camera delay, image transmission delay, and deep learning inference delay) and the detection transmission delay from the SPU to the MEC server.

Method of calculation

The different SPUs send their detections to the MEC server. The detections include the timestamp of the camera image. The Input Delay is then the difference between the time of the MEC server and the timestamp of the detection. This is possible as all components use a synchronized clock.

Table 2: TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC1.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC1			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_P_2update Latency in UC1			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	22183	84.80 ms	91.41 ms	21.75 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	
	416.22 ms	51.50 ms	[55.94, 111.13] ms	

Plots

Figure 5: UC1 Update Latency histogram.

Figure 6: UC1 Update Latency CDF.

Conclusions

The results in Table 2 show that the update latency for UC1 allows to realize our UC1. The mean latency is about 84 ms and the standard deviation is about 21 ms, so, in general, the Digital Twin receives fast updates. The large maximal update time is practically not relevant, as larger latencies happened only rarely, as can be seen in Figure 5 and Figure 6. The verification criterion required an update latency between 50 ms and 2500 ms which means that this KPI is fulfilled.

2.3.3. Test Case for KPI_P_3 Notification Latency in UC1

In UC1, the KPI of the notification latency is based on obtaining measurements to calculate the latency from the time the MEC starts to notify a road user in form of a CAV or VRU regarding a road event until this notification is received by the road user.

Method of calculation

For this KPI, messages generated on the MEC and sent to a CAV are logged at the nearest point of computation and the nearest point of consumption, respectively, including their timestamps. The latency is calculated as the difference in timestamps between the two logs of the same message. This logging mechanism ensures accurate latency tracking by leveraging synchronized clocks and uniform

time-stamping standards across the involved system components. Data integrity and logging granularity were also verified to ensure the robustness of measurements.

Table 3: TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC1.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC1			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_P_3 notification Latency in UC1			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	71123	17.29 ms	14.88 ms	12.76 ms
	Max	Min	Mean CI 95%	Percentile 95
	391.67 ms	4.02 ms	[17.16, 17.41] ms	27.08 ms

Plots

Figure 7: UC1 Notification Latency violin plot.

Figure 8: UC1 Notification Latency CDF.

Conclusions

As seen in Table 3 of 71123 logged packets, the mean notification latency was 17.29 ms, and the 95th percentile latency was 27.08 ms. The verification criterion requires a 95th percentile notification latency between 50 ms and 2.5 seconds, depending on the service. The 95th percentile notification latency of 27.08 ms fulfils the KPI.

This result demonstrates that the Podium UC1 system is able to provide a real-time responsiveness, making it well-suited for dynamic traffic scenarios such as incident resolution or event-driven control. The latency values not only meet the verification criteria but indicate that the MEC platform can scale to denser environments. The results across the logged samples indicate overall strong system performance, with the vast majority of notifications delivered at low latency. A small number of higher-latency samples were observed, contributing to a wider spread in the distribution; however, these can be attributed to the variability introduced by real-world testing conditions, such as environmental interference. Despite these factors, the system maintained a low mean latency and a 95th percentile holding the KPI performance threshold. The consistent behaviour across most samples under realistic deployment scenarios demonstrates the system’s maturity at this stage of evaluation.

2.3.4. Test Case for KPI_P_4 Processing Delay in UC1

In UC1, the processing delay is defined as the computation time between the availability of detections to the digital twin and the availability of a corresponding Manoeuvre Coordination Message (MCM) for the road user.

Method of calculation

To compute the processing delay, the cooperative manoeuvre planning service logs the computation times induced between availability of new detections and the publishing of corresponding MCMs for all involved road users.

Table 4: TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC1.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC1			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_P_4-processing delay in UC1			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	6098	26.03ms	20.77ms	19.55ms
	Max	Min	Mean CI 95%	Percentile 95
	156.12ms	5.02ms	[25.54, 26.52]ms	68.03ms

Plots

Figure 9: UC1 Processing Delay histogram.

Figure 10: UC1 Processing Delay CDF.

Conclusions

The results in Table 4 show that the median and average processing time is fast with 21ms and 26ms, respectively. The 95th percentile of processing delays is significantly higher at 68 ms, but it remains well within the bounds for the KPI target value of 2.5 seconds.

The primary focus of UC1 is corridor management, which is not extremely latency sensitive but benefits from low latencies to achieve best possible results.

As traffic scenes vary in their complexity, the processing delays introduced by the cooperative manoeuvre planning service vary as well. For scaling the platform service to larger and more complex environments, software performance optimization will be beneficial to maintain fast processing times.

2.3.5. Test Case for KPI_P_5 Communication Reliability in UC1

In UC1 the KPI of the communication reliability is based on obtaining measurements of the platform relaying messages between CAV and MEC to calculate the fraction of delivered messages and hence estimate the reliability.

Method of calculation

Messages are sent from the CAV to the MEC in the uplink and vice versa in the downlink. The messages are logged at both the CAV and the MEC. To calculate the reliability of the communication, we match packets in both logs that belong to the test case measurement run. A packet present in both logs is considered a matched sample, while a logged sent message that is not logged on the receiving side is considered an unmatched sample (message lost). The end-to-end packet matching approach enables a precise and quantitative assessment of message delivery integrity, including loss.

Table 5: TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC1.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC1			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_P_5-communication Reliability in UC1			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	# uplink samples	# uplink matched samples	# downlink samples
	96377	25254	22135	71123
	# downlink matched samples	% successful uplink matched	% successful downlink matched	% successful overall matched
	70888	87.64	99.66	96.51

Conclusions

We log a total of 96377 samples in the tests for this KPI. As seen from Table 5, in total, 93023 of 96377 samples were successfully matched, which is a successful matching rate of 96.51%. The validation criterion requires a success rate between 99.99% and 90%, depending on the criticality of the situation. With a matching rate of 96.51%, we observe that the KPI is met. It provides a quantification to gauge the system to the application criticality.

These results illustrate a reliable communication architecture that is capable of maintaining message delivery even under variable network conditions. This performance is critical for ensuring seamless operations of CCAM, where timely and accurate data exchange is vital. This high reliability supports the platform's scalability potential, suggesting that it can accommodate higher data volumes and more complex communication demands without compromising communication performance.

2.3.6. Test Case for KPI_UC1_1 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV

Test if a CAV successfully passes a blockage with a cooperative manoeuvre while another CAV approaches the blockage and yields on the non-blocked lane.

Method of calculation

The success of individual test runs is evaluated qualitatively by at least one expert. The experts observe the traffic flow during test runs to evaluate if the conditions for a cooperative manoeuvre are given. When the conditions are fulfilled, the experts verify that the CAVs successfully passed the blockage.

Table 6: TC_KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV			
Descriptive Statistics	# tests	# successful manoeuvres	# failed manoeuvres	Success rate
	9	8	1	89%

Conclusions

As seen in Table 6, during the test runs, eight out of nine manoeuvres were marked as successful, resulting in a success rate of 89%. The verification criterion requires a success rate of more than 75%, thus, the KPI_UC1_1 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV for the use case is met.

In the test run of the failed manoeuvre, the obstacle on the road was detected by the digital twin but was not considered as blockage by the cooperative manoeuvre planning service because an internal standstill duration threshold was not satisfied. Additionally, initiated test runs were aborted and not considered due to abnormal traffic flow, as stated in the pre-test conditions.

2.3.7. Test Case for KPI_UC1_2 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU

Test if a VRU successfully passes a blockage with a cooperative manoeuvre while a CAV approaches the blockage and yields on the non-blocked lane.

Method of calculation

The success of individual test runs is evaluated qualitatively by at least one expert. The experts observe the traffic flow during test runs to evaluate if the conditions for a cooperative manoeuvre are given. When the conditions are fulfilled, the experts verify that the VRU successfully passed the blockage.

Table 7: TC_UC1_2-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU.

TC Identifier	TC_UC1_2-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU			
Materials used	VRU and CAVs including computing and communication devices on the VRU and the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU			
Descriptive Statistics	# tests	# successful manoeuvres	# failed manoeuvres	Success rate
	8	8	0	100%

Conclusions

As seen in Table 7: During the test runs, eight out of 8 manoeuvres were marked as successful, resulting in a success rate of 100%. The verification criterion requires a success rate of more than 75%, thus, the KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU for the use case is met.

2.3.8. Test Case for KPI_UC1_3 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-MultiC utilization

Test if Multi-Connectivity is able to utilize all available communication technologies successfully at the same time.

Method of calculation

Test runs were conducted in which the CAV initiates a transmission to the MEC. Specifically, 62 test runs were conducted from CAV to MEC, with 10 packets per test, split into 5 packets in uplink and downlink. The sender-side scheduler passes the data to the different communication technologies, and the receiving scheduler processes the incoming streams. The results are calculated as the percentage of packets transmitted from the sender that reached the receiver and were duplicated over all available communication channels. The available communication channels are 5G cm- and mm-wave and 60 GHz WiFi in the uplink, and 5G cm-wave and 60 GHz WiFi in the downlink. Each packet's duplication across all technologies was independently verified, and network traces confirmed concurrent channel utilization. The underlying scheduler's load balancing and channel selection logic was assessed to ensure reliability.

Table 8: TC_UC1_3-Cooperative-Maneuver-MultiC.

TC Identifier	KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Maneuver-MultiC			
Materials used	CAVs including computers and communication devices on the vehicles. Sensing and communication infrastructure at Ulm-Lehr living lab. 5G network using cm and mmWave. MEC infrastructure.			
KPI	KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-MultiC utilization			
Descriptive Statistics	# tests	# sample packets	# successful uplink transmission	
	62	620	310	310
	# uplink duplications on 5G-cmWave	# uplink duplications on 5G-mmWave	# uplink duplications on 60 GHz adhoc	# downlink duplications on 5G-cmWave
	310	310	310	310
	# downlink duplications on 60 GHz adhoc	% successful uplink transmission	% successful downlink transmission	% successful uplink duplication
	310	100	100	100
	% successful downlink duplication			
100				

Conclusions

In this test case, each packet reached its destination, and each packet was duplicated on all available communication channels. The verification criterion requires more than 95% of test runs to be successful. As seen in Table 8 the 62 test runs, 62 were successful, which results in 100% of test runs being successful. Thus, the KPI KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Maneuver-MultiC for Multi connectivity in UC1 is met.

In terms of scalability, we observe for the scheduler, which is a P4 software switch, that additional communication channels can simply be integrated without compromising the reliability of the switch. The test case outcome confirms that the system multi-connectivity architecture performs as intended,

ensuring high reliability and parallel data streaming. The ability to utilize all communication paths simultaneously enhances reliability and paves the way for high-resilient data transmission strategies.

The underlying P4-based scheduler, functioning at the network edge, plays a pivotal role in orchestrating the packet distribution across multiple technologies. Its programmability offers future-proofing and adaptability for emerging new messages and interfaces. The system's current success rate suggests high potential for real-world deployment in more congested or interference-prone environments, where multi-connectivity fallback mechanisms are critical.

2.4. Conclusions

In D2.1 [1], we identified the following **potential needs**, which have been successfully addressed during the project's development:

- Developing accurate local environment models of the intersection area in the Ulm-Lehr LL.
- Relying on reliable connectivity and communication to allow real-time data exchange and cooperative decision-making.
- Availability of vehicles and VRUs with advanced connectivity and automation capabilities for efficient operation.
- Investigating potential disruptions of vehicle driving functions relying on MEC/cloud services.

To fulfil these needs, we anticipated several **potential challenges**, as outlined in D2.1 [1] (page 17), which have been effectively managed:

- Occlusion: The occluded areas at the Ulm-Lehr LL may pose challenges in obtaining accurate data for building local environment models, as line-of-sight between sensors and road users can be obstructed. The successful manoeuvre results show that this challenge did not jeopardize the construction of environment models.
- Data quality: The quality of transmitted data can vary, such that a respective trust building for data reliability has to be developed and established. The results show that the data quality allowed successful manoeuvres.
- Environment model: Build an accurate model from road users' data only (without using infrastructure sensors) for a lightweight solution. This was successfully managed.
- Cooperative planner: Develop a cooperative planner capable of solving sophisticated traffic situations with blockages and occlusions. This was successfully managed.
- Heterogeneity of connected road users: The involvement of CAVs and VRUs. This was successfully managed.
- Heterogeneity of communication channels: Achieve reliable end-to-end data transfer using heterogeneous communication technologies with dynamic and spatially local properties. The results show successful manoeuvres despite and using heterogeneous communication technologies.

The most significant technological challenges of UC1 can be summarized as follows:

- The integration of a hardware-based communication scheduler for packet duplication and deduplication. The stringent requirements for the PoDIUM multi-connectivity scheduler dictate that this scheduler receives a hardware support. Hence, alternative solutions using transport-layer multi-connectivity scheduling such as Multipath TCP (MPTCP) or Multipath QUIC (MPQUIC) were ruled out as these would lead to packet drops under duplication and deduplication at high throughput. The technological integration of hardware-based P4-scheduling and packet duplication/deduplication including encapsulation over heterogeneous communication technologies (5G cm- and mmWave, and adhoc 60 GHz WiFi) proved hard, however, it was managed throughout the project. The **recommendation** based on this effort

is that while traffic steering and load balancing over heterogeneous communication technologies can be efficient in transport-layer schedulers the intensive packet processing for collision-free duplication/deduplication requires hardware support and should be decoupled from transport-layer scheduling.

- Interaction between the server planner and the local vehicle planners proved difficult. This was mainly due to the MCM message we used for information exchange, which was not yet standardized (see, e.g., D3.3 [3]). Based on our experience, we recommend using only standardized messages as the interface between different components.

Overall, we have successfully achieved the **strategic goals** defined in D2.1 [1]. In the following we provide the conclusions regarding their attainment, based on the results obtained so far:

- UC1 showed successful management of CAVs and other connected road users, especially VRUs in an urban corridor management scenario.
- UC1 successfully extended service availability in occluded areas of the Ulm-Lehr LL and showed efficient and fast decision-making based on cooperative local environment models that are transmitted using a multi-connectivity approach.
- UC1 showed the ability of VRUs protection through the involvement of CAVs in addition to connected VRUs.
- UC1 successfully demonstrated traffic efficiency improvement through a cooperative corridor management.

Building upon the lessons learned during the development and validation of the PoDIUM technologies in UC1, the following recommendations are proposed to ensure effective deployment and optimization of the platform in real-world environments. These recommendations address the identified challenges and provide actionable steps for operation:

- UC1 showed that it is able to build an accurate local environment model from road users' data only without using infrastructure sensors for a lightweight solution. While deployment scenarios integrating infrastructure-based sensors work well, a solution based on road users' data alone provides maneuver results at no infrastructure costs.
- The integration of a hardware-based Multi-Connectivity scheduler has proven essential for efficient packet duplication and deduplication under high throughput. While traffic steering is well handled at the transport layer, specifically decoupling redundancy scheduling from transport-layer functionality ensures efficiency of packet handling while improving reliability.

3. Use Case 2: PDI for Use-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

3.1. Introduction to the UC

The UC2 evaluation activities of the Spanish LL are described in this chapter. UC2 explores and demonstrates how real-time data exchange between connected vehicles (CVs) and traffic infrastructure can enhance urban mobility. This is achieved through dynamic traffic signal control, cooperative manoeuvres, predictive traffic management and AI-based video processing. These features enable key CCAM functionalities in complex city environments.

As a brief reminder, UC2 explores three scenarios: Scenario 1 prioritises emergency vehicles (EVs) along emergency corridor using Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)-based positioning, while enabling cooperative manoeuvres of CAVs to clear the lane for the EV. Scenario 2 aims to optimise traffic flow using live CCAM data and an urban digital twin to implement dynamic control strategies and alert CAVs to incidents along their routes. Scenario 3 aims to protect VRUs by detecting collision risks and triggering timely warnings for vehicles and VRUs.

UC2 is implemented in the heart of the city centre of Barcelona, around the Gran Via corridor and its surrounding areas, which are highly dynamic and complex environments. The selected area (see section 3.1.1.1 of D3.3 [3]) includes a large emergency corridor to test priority for emergency vehicles, a grid of certain dimensions to test traffic optimisation in case of incidents, and a complex intersection with pedestrian and bike lanes to test services to protect VRUs (mainly pedestrians and cyclists).

The global architecture and its main functional components, which have already been described in D3.3 [3], are illustrated in Figure 11 for ease of reference in this document.

Figure 11: UC2 functional diagram.

3.2. Completion of integration actions since the last deliverable

The following WP4 actions were completed between the submission of D4.2 [5] and the final testing and demonstration activities which led to the start of the evaluation activities reported in the current deliverable:

PDI innovation's integration and validation

- While the functional integration of CVs and EV with the infrastructure was largely completed as planned, the On-Board Unit (OBU) integration for the MILLA shuttle was not completed in Spain, because the necessary AD (Automated Driving) permits were not obtained there. Consequently, the integration was completed and tested in France during the AD demonstration at the UTAC circuit in November 2025.
- As regards VRU-related integrations, full connectivity to the Google Firebase service could not initially be achieved due to pending security adjustments from the network provider (Vodafone). The full validation of the VRU app was carried out once this issue had been resolved in September 2025.

Pre-demo testing activities

Concerning the pre-test conditions that could not be fulfilled when D4.2 [5] was submitted:

- All permits relating to the IDIADA CV and the firefighter's vehicle (EV) had been obtained by the time D4.2 [5] was submitted. These were primarily permits for the CV to circulate in the bus lane along the Gran Via corridor, as well as a permit for the EV to circulate for testing purposes. This enabled the involved partners to carry out the planned tests in Barcelona involving the CV and the EV and calculate the full set of KPIs proposed in D5.1 [6].

However, as previously mentioned, the AD permit for testing the MILLA CAV in Spain could not ultimately be obtained. Nevertheless, the MILLA CAV is fully operational and can circulate at the planned urban speed of 50 km/h in Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) Level 4 automation. It has only been tested on a closed circuit in France.

- In scenario 1 regarding EV priority, the evaluation activities for guard times were pending because of the phased testing process, so this was a work in progress at that time. Guard times, are specific programmed time intervals used in the traffic signal controller to ensure that the intersection transitions safely and efficiently, granting the emergency vehicle right of way. Once the testing phase had been completed, the KPI_UC2_4 EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction, which deals with guard times, was calculated.

The pre-demo methodology and data logging for UC2 have been met as defined in D4.2 [5], despite the aforementioned impossibility of carrying out the tests with the CAV in Barcelona. This did not affect the planned tests with the remaining vehicles or the evaluation activities, however.

Regarding the pre-demo testing activities that could not be completed by the time D4.2 [5] was submitted:

Functional tests:

- The MEC was tested and fully validated, confirming the correct functioning and interoperability of its functionalities and ensuring that connected vehicles and infrastructure can communicate with each other.
- The Cloud was also tested and fully validated, demonstrating reliable communication between the deployed cloud-based services, the infrastructure and the MEC components. This allowed coordinated responses to dynamic road events and improved traffic flow during emergency scenarios.

- Integration and testing were performed to fulfil the functional requirements relating to the CV (transmission of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) messages, installation of the Human Machine Interface (HMI) and display of warnings, and the transmission rate of Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs)) except for the requirement relating to positioning acquisition from a GNSS device. This was successfully tested and validated in September 2025, during open road testing. The requirements for sending and receiving messages in the CAV were tested and validated for the three scenarios in the tests previously carried out in France.
- VRU functional testing was successfully carried out, validating the key infrastructure components for road user safety in Scenario 3. The requirements for VRU detection and tracking, Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM) dissemination and the core functionalities of the VRU-App were validated in laboratory.

However, the functional requirements relating to the full on-road connectivity of the VRU-App were not yet complete when D4.2 [5] was submitted. The tests for scenario 3, which were performed in Barcelona in September 2025, could validate the requirements for the on-road use of the VRU-App functionalities.

Figure 12 shows the time taken from VRU detection to warning appearance in the VRU-app, based on tests carried out in Barcelona as reported in section 3.3.

Nº samples	Average	Median (P50)	P90	Minimum	Maximum
8	1.92 s	1.89 s	2.1 s	1.6 s	2.12 s

Figure 12: Box plot and data showing times related to the VRU-App.

These results may seem to have high latency, but it's important to take into account all the hops and the journey the message goes through before it reaches the mobile device and the warning is displayed. First, the message leaves the vehicle and is received by the edge via Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT); it processes it and uploads it to a Firestore database, from which the mobile device retrieves the data with a refresh rate of 1 second.

- The Roadside Unit (RSU) requirements relating to the dissemination and reception of V2X messages (CAM and DENM) were successfully tested in July 2025 as part of the Scenario 3 trials in Barcelona.

Non-functional tests

As reported in D4.2 [5], most non-functional tests were fully validated on 20 July 2025 at the test site in Barcelona, as well as at the IDIDA laboratory.

- P_UC2-CAV_001: The CV acquired positioning from the GNSS device installed on top of the vehicle, as shown in Figure 14. The white device shown is the OBU antenna, which incorporates the GPS and Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) settings. This data was used to send CAM messages to the MEC in all three of the scenarios that were tested in Barcelona.

MILLA CAV's functional behaviour requires that AD mode can't be activated if the positioning information is unavailable. During the demonstration tests at the UTAC circuit, the vehicle operated in AD mode without any functional interruption (i.e., no unexpected disengagement or emergency stops). This successfully verifies the continuous availability and reliability of the positioning data throughout the operation, confirming that the MILLA CAV is compliant with this requirement.

- P_UC2-CAV_002: The functional design of MILLA CAV ensures that AD mode can't be activated if the Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) service is not configured correctly. The successful completion of all demonstration tests in AD mode at the UTAC circuit, without any interruption to the service, indicates that the RTK service was correctly configured and remained stable throughout testing.

The CV did not use the RTK service, instead using a setting that seemed to be commonly used by conventional road users. This service was not necessary for the tests to be carried out with sufficient accuracy, as demonstrated by the KPIs achieved (section 3.4).

- P_UC2-CAV_003: The Network Transport of Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services (RTCM) via Internet Protocol (NTRIP) requirement was not applicable to the MILLA CAV, since the vehicle does not use NTRIP for RTK corrections.
- P_UC2-CAV_004: This was met as there were no network interruptions during testing, as shown in Figure 13, which depicts 5G connectivity during one hour of UC2 testing in Barcelona.

Figure 13: 5G network connection continuity from tests in Barcelona.

On the other hand, the MILLA CAV has also successfully met this requirement for AD mode. The MILLA CAV's functional design requires that AD mode cannot be activated without an active internet connection. Furthermore, if the connection is lost for more than 5 seconds, the autonomous system is designed to trigger a forced emergency stop in order to adhere to French legal requirements for continuous connectivity to the tele-supervision centre. During demonstration tests at the UTAC circuit, the MILLA CAV operated in AD mode without any interruptions to its functionality (i.e. there were no unexpected disengagements from AD mode or forced emergency stops by the autonomous system), thus confirming the CAV's full compliance with this safety and legal requirement.

All the data required to comply with these four requirements has been uploaded to the Zenodo repository.

- PNF_UC2-NET_001, PNF_UC2-NET_002 and PNF_UC2-NET_003: The end-to-end latency requirement has been verified through the KPI_P_3 measurement campaign (notification latency in UC2, section 3.4.3), in which all observed values remained well below the 2-second

threshold. Regarding bandwidth and QoS, these aspects are inherently satisfied by using a 5G Standalone (5G SA) network, such as that used at the test site in UC2. Even under conservative conditions, 5G SA provides stable link speeds exceeding 100 Mbps and supports guaranteed Quality of Service (QoS) profiles, offering throughput margins that are several orders of magnitude above the minimum requirement of 200 kbps. Therefore, the combination of validated low latency and the performance characteristics inherent to 5G SA confirm that the requirements for both bandwidth and reliability are fulfilled by design.

Testing scenarios

The completion of the pending testing activities for the UC2 scenarios, as set out in Deliverable D4.2 [5], is as follows:

- For Scenario 1, testing had progressed through three preparatory phases in the field, during which essential systems were validated. The key remaining activity was Phase 4: a real-world cooperative driving manoeuvre involving an EV and a CV. This crucial coordination trial took place in September–October 2025, as detailed in Section 3.3.
- Scenario 2 had not yet been tested when D4.2 [5] was finalised. Although all the necessary technical developments for the Traffic Management System (TMS) and its integration with existing city systems were complete, the system could not be activated until data had been collected from the CVs. This was completed in October 2025, as reported in Section 3.3.
- For Scenario 3, core validation was successfully performed during field trials in July 2025. Only the functional requirements relating to the VRU-App's full on-road operation were pending, involving the final configuration of access to the cloud database (Google Firebase service). This was validated in September 2025, as previously justified.

Adjustments and mitigation actions

The principal constraint affecting the timely execution of testing in the Spanish Living Lab (UC2) was the unavailability of the MILLA CAV due to pending permits. The necessary AD permissions, including special red plates and DGT permits to circulate on Spanish roads, could not be obtained in time for the tests planned for May–June 2025. Consequently, the major cooperative manoeuvre trials for the three scenarios were consequently postponed and planned to take place from September onwards. Although preliminary integration using CVs and the EV was possible, subsequent critical phases of UC2 validation were delayed until the permit decision was finalised. The aim was to integrate the CAV into the tests upon its arrival to Barcelona. Ultimately, however, the necessary AD permits were not secured.

Therefore, the tests conducted in Barcelona in September–October 2025 proceeded without the CAV. It was ultimately impossible to obtain the AD permits due to regulatory constraints (fully reported in deliverable D6.4 [7]) and CAV-specific functional tests, including scenarios originally intended for Barcelona, were relocated to the UTAC circuit in France. This mitigation plan ensured that the essential CV and EV functionality trials conducted in Barcelona during September–October were successfully carried out, with no impact on the evaluation activities planned in D5.1 [6] and reported in Section 3.4.

3.3. Demonstration activities and data collection

This section describes the preparation and demonstration activities in UC2 which mainly took place in September–October 2025:

Preparation of the test site and vehicles

The preparatory phase leading up to the planned testing focused on finalising the deployment of the physical infrastructure and ensuring the readiness of the key vehicles (CVs and EVs). The fixed infrastructure, including the MEC servers, AI cameras and RSU, had been successfully installed in the core test area (the intersection of Gran Vía and Girona Street), as reported in D4.2 [5]. The key vehicles

for the tests in Barcelona (the CV provided by IDIADA and the EVs from the Barcelona Fire Department) were fully equipped with the necessary hardware and software to communicate with the infrastructure via CAMs and DENMs. Next Figure 14 shows the preparation phase of the test site in Barcelona during July and September 2025.

Figure 14: Pictures of the test site preparation phase in Barcelona. From top to down: Deployment of a computer in a street cabinet; rear part of the test vehicle with computers and OBU; test vehicle with PoDIUM partners testing the equipment; driver's dashboard; OBU antennas on top of the second test vehicle; and rear part of the second test vehicle with one OBU.

Scenario 1: Prioritisation of emergency vehicles

When D4.2 [5] was submitted, the functional testing of Scenario 1 had reached Phase 3. This involved successfully validating the real-time positioning of EVs via GNSS data and activating traffic light prioritisation through the EMEBO system (see D3.3 [3] and D4.2 [5] for more details). The critical step scheduled for September–October 2025 was Phase 4: real-world cooperative driving manoeuvres. This final phase aimed to test the complete coordination layer involving an EV and a CV. The objective was to confirm that the CV could successfully receive DENM messages from the Cooperative Manoeuvre Recommender (CMR) and that the driver could react to HMI warnings by performing the recommended manoeuvre to clear the lane for the approaching EV. This testing was designed to define

and execute Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) coordination, building upon established corridor activation and traffic signal priority elements.

Tests took place at the Barcelona test site on 8.10.2025 and 30.10.2025, and finally on 18-19.11.2025. The latter coincided with the UC2 demonstration event, which took place on the same day as the PoDIUM Final Event. Figure 15 shows the route followed by the EV along the Gran Via corridor during scenario 1 tests, including the analysis for a specific intersection and particular points relating to the EV position during green activation and deactivation. More detailed information can be found in section 3.4.6. Figure 16 and Figure 17 show views from inside the EV and CV, respectively.

Figure 15: Route followed by the EV along the Gran Via corridor during the final tests of scenario 1.

Scenario 2: Traffic optimisation

By the end of July 2025, Scenario 2 had not been tested at all. While all the technical developments for the Traffic Management System (TMS) and its integration with the MISTRAL Smart Mobility Platform operating in Barcelona were complete, functional execution required significant real-world traffic input. The main activity planned for September 2025 was the collection and analysis of mobility data from CVs, including traffic metrics such as speed and Origin-Destination (O-D) patterns. This extensive data collection was necessary to provide the TMS with reliable, statistically meaningful insights, thereby enabling subsequent functional testing of dynamic traffic management strategies and incident response loops (e.g. sending notification messages (DENMs) for rerouting).

Tests took place at the Barcelona test site on 7.10.25 and 29.10.25. Figure 18 shows the routes performed by the CVs around the test site in Barcelona to collect traffic data that feed the TMS so that it can process all traffic metrics and therefore detect any congestion along the CVs routes. More detailed information about these trips can be found in sections 3.4.7 and 3.4.8. Figure 19 shows the view from inside the CV, including the planned route, and the HMI which displays alerts for traffic incidents (congestion) along the route.

Figure 16: Sight from inside the EV during the final tests of scenario 1.

Figure 17: Sight from inside the CV during the final tests of scenario 1.

Figure 18: Routes of CVs to gather traffic data (mainly OD patterns) for scenario 2.

Figure 19: Sight from inside the CV during the final tests of scenario 2.

Scenario 3: Protection of VRUs

Scenario 3 was highly successful in terms of functionality during the field trials in early July 2025. This confirmed that the infrastructure was able to detect and track VRUs (using AICs) and enable the Collision Risk Estimator (CRE) (see D3.3 [3] and D4.2 [5] for more details) to generate DENM alerts for the CV HMI. The core item pending for the September–October phase was not related to the detection system itself, but to the VRU-App mobile application. As reported in section 3.2, this integration and validation were successfully carried out in September 2025, enabling the Scenario 3 tests to begin. Tests took place at the Barcelona test site on 7.10.25 and 29.10.25.

Figure 20 shows the intersection between the Gran Via corridor and Girona Street, where the tests were conducted, and depicts the location of the installed infrastructure (cameras, RSU and cabinet containing the router and Jetson NVIDIA module for Artificial Intelligence (AI) video processing over the traffic controller), as well as the existing pedestrian crossings (blue) and bike lanes (green). The tests involved a VRU (in this case, a bike rider) who was attempting to cross the central carriageway of the Gran Via using the bike lane; therefore, there was a potential collision point with CVs travelling along this route. The cameras detected the VRU's position and trajectory, estimating the risk of collision with a CV and sending warnings to the CVs (through DENM messages) and the VRU (through the VRU-App).

Figure 22 and Figure 30 show, respectively, the driver's view from the CV (including the HMI) and the VRU's view (including the VRU-App), as both approach the selected intersection to test the scenario.

Figure 20: Intersection Gran Via/Girona where tests took place for scenario 3.

Figure 21: Sight from inside the CV during the final tests of scenario 3.

Figure 22: VRU with the smartphone serving as HMI of alerts generated in scenario 3.

Testing scenarios with the MILLA CAV

In addition to the testing phases conducted in Barcelona in September–October 2025, which proceeded without the MILLA CAV (Figure 23), a complementary demonstration of the CAV shuttle took place at the UTAC-Linas Montlhéry closed circuit in Paris, as previously mentioned.

The same three UC2 scenarios were executed as cooperative manoeuvres in full AD mode SAE L4 at the UTAC circuit. These scenarios aimed to demonstrate safety improvements through cooperation between the CAV and the infrastructure through autonomously reacting to the same DENM messages which were used in the tests carried out in Barcelona.

Figure 23: The CAV, MILLA shuttle on the days of the demonstration.

This demonstration was carried out in two phases:

- The pre-demonstration phase, conducted from 27 to 31 October 2025.
- The demonstration phase for UC2 took place on 4-5.11.25 for UC2. During this phase, scenario 2 'Traffic optimisation' was carried out on 4.11.25, while scenarios 1 'EV prioritisation' and 3 'VRU protection' took place on 5.11.25. Most of the data was collected during the demonstration phase for the validation of requirements and calculation of KPIs. Figure 24 shows the different UTAC circuit areas in which each scenario was tested.

<p>UTAC-Linas Montlhéry closed circuit. Area 2 (city circuit) used for testing at speeds of up to 50 km/h. Area 1 (highway circuit) used for testing at speeds of up to 130 km/h.</p>	
<p>City circuit mapping with Scenario 2 and "Pedestrian Crossing" (additional to UC2) scenarios</p>	
<p>Highway circuit mapping with scenarios 1 and 3</p>	

Figure 24: Circuits followed by the MILLA Shuttle at UTAC- Linas Montlhéry closed circuit

The test procedure for the sequence of the three scenarios was performed as follows:

- 1) Normal situation in AD mode, before receiving any C-ITS messages, in the three scenarios:
 - The MILLA shuttle receives missions from the Tele Supervision Centre, the Safety Driver and the Traffic Management Centre (TMC), ensuring operations are carried out in safe conditions and in compliance with the (ODD) and legislation.
 - The shuttle initiates at the origin points of the route in full AD mode.
 - The shuttle accelerates until it reaches a speed of 50 km/h \pm 10% in full AD mode.

- 2) Reception of the C-V2X message, due to the absence of physical infrastructure, such as that deployed in Barcelona. These were DENM messages in JSON format. The cause codes linked to each DENM message for each scenario were as follows:
 - In scenario 1, cause code *emergencyVehicleApproaching (95)*.
 - In scenario 2, cause code *trafficCondition --> trafficJam*.
 - In scenario 3, cause code *collisionRisk(97)*.
- 3) Reaction to the traffic strategy accordingly to each scenario:
 - Scenario 1: The shuttle changes lanes from the occupied lane to the lane immediately to its left.
 - Scenario 2: The shuttle planner automatically updates to use the alternative route, and the shuttle takes this route autonomously to continue driving in AD mode without driver handover.
 - Scenario 3: The shuttle slows down to a speed of 30km/h (+/-10%).
- 4) Return to the normal situation:
 - Scenario 1: The shuttle continues to circulate in full AD mode until the next station.
 - Scenario 2: The shuttle continues to run on the alternative route in AD mode until the next stop station.
 - Scenario 3: The shuttle continues at a speed of 30km/h (+/-10%) in full AD mode until the next stop station.

Figure 25 shows several views of the demonstration carried out for scenario 2 "Traffic optimisation".

<p>MILLA shuttle in operation during demonstration: View from the driver's space. The safety driver is physically present, but does not control the steering wheel. The blue LED indicates that the shuttle is in full AD mode.</p>	
<p>Passenger HMIs showing the initial and alternative routes on the shuttle planner.</p>	
<p>MILLA shuttle in operation during demonstration: View from the passenger space. Passenger HMI shows the shuttle perception with the initial route on the shuttle planner. Some partners attended the demonstration.</p>	

Figure 25: Test Day schedule for scenario 2 "Traffic optimisation" during the demonstration.

Demonstration event

The UC2 live demonstration was part of the PoDIUM final event, which took place in the heart of Barcelona’s Eixample district on 19 November, very close to the test site located at the intersection of Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes and Girona Street (see Figure 26). This location was chosen as it provides an ideal, challenging urban environment in which to test cooperative driving features. It features multi-lane traffic, public transport, traffic lights, pedestrian crossings, cyclists and mixed traffic conditions. The aim was to show how the PoDIUM architecture can enable CCAM in a real urban environment rather than just a laboratory setting. Challenges faced in this dense setting included ensuring latency was below the required threshold for real-time reactions, and integrating communication between infrastructure, EVs and CVs. The on-site demonstration was scheduled to run for approximately one and a half hours (15:00–17:00) to avoid peak afternoon traffic.

The core of the live demonstration focused on showcasing two main scenarios from UC2:

- EV prioritisation (scenario 1): In this scenario, priority was given to a Firefighters’ vehicle along the Gran Via corridor. At the same time, the CV received a DENM message from the infrastructure recommending it to perform a safe and cooperative manoeuvre. The system then actively coordinated the movements of the CV and the EV, clearing the lane for the EV to pass safely and efficiently through the corridor (see Figure 27).

Figure 26: People attending the live demonstration event.

Figure 27: EV passing through the intersection where the cooperative manoeuvre was performed.

Figure 28: VRU attempting to cross the intersection.

- VRU protection (scenario 3): This scenario focused on the protection of VRUs, which involved detecting and protecting pedestrians and cyclists using real-time V2X communication. This scenario detailed the dynamics of VRUs at the intersection, including their trajectories, detection zones, potential collision areas, and the subsequent warnings issued to vehicles and VRUs (see Figure 28).

Figure 29: View of the streaming showing the HMI, rear and front cameras.

In order to show attendees what was happening on the street effectively, the event relied heavily on live streaming and real-time guidance. The entire live demonstration was streamed via the YouTube PoDIUM channel. Attendees could access the stream (Figure 29) on their mobile phones by scanning the QR code on their badge or yellow vest. The stream featured multiple visual perspectives, including three live scenes: the HMI inside the vehicle and live rear and front cameras. Participants were also asked to wear headphones so that they could hear the real-time commentary and direction provided by a guide throughout the test. This ensured that the commentary aligned with visible actions taking place on the street and in the streamed video feeds.

Data collection

During the execution of the UC2 trials, multiple datasets were collected and stored in a repository. Table 70 of the Annex outlines the whole set of logged parameters and the links to access them. This

data has been collected in the logging points indicated in Figure 30 and following the guiding lines of D4.2 [4].

Figure 30: Logging points in the UC2's functional diagram according to D4.1 [4].

The log collection strategy for UC2 was designed to ensure the complete traceability of all the events required for calculating KPIs, in line with the PoDIUM architecture's component-based logging approach and partner responsibilities (Figure 30). All logs are stored in the Zenodo repository. The links to these logs can be found in Table 70 of Annex 1. In addition to the logs, the Zenodo repository contains a README guide to the structure of the data logs and the computation methods used to obtain the trial results.

The log structure is segmented into four primary folders, each corresponding to a key logging point in the functional view:

- **UC2_TMS_Strategy:** this component focuses on data generated by the Traffic Management functions and the Digital Twin processing. It contains logs of all dynamic traffic light states triggered by the EV prioritisation (scenario 1), and computed O-D metrics and trip delays derived from data from CVs (scenario 2).

It can validate the following KPIs in UC2: KPI_UC2_1 (traffic light flow), KPI_UC2_4 (traffic impact), KPI_UC_2 (O-D accuracy) and KPI_UC2_3 (trip delay).

- **UC2_VRU_Risk management:** this component specifically focuses on the logs generated by the AI Camera and MEC risk assessment services. It contains data of VRU detection events and the precise timing of DENM generation for warning values in scenario 3.

It can validate the KPI_P_4 (processing delay) in UC2.

- **UC2_CITS_Gateway:** this component contains logs related to C-ITS communication reliability and the raw data streams from CVs. It contains logs of all incoming and outgoing C-ITS messages (CAMs, DENMs) via the gateway and the generated HMI messages to assess communication reliability and latency. Also includes the raw kinematic data (position, speed) transmitted by the CVs used as source data.

It can validate the following KPIs in UC2: KPI_P_1 (service availability), KPI_P_2 (update latency), KPI_P_3 (notification latency) and KPI_P_3 (communication reliability), KPI_UC2_5 (successful cooperative manoeuvres), KPI_UC2_6 (collision risk_reaction time) and KPI_UC2_7 (collision risk_softer deceleration).

- UC2_CAV: this component logs the internal processes of the MILLA CAV during the UTAC trials, recording the timing of the C-ITS messages reception, the automation system’s decision-making latency and the resulting vehicle actuator response.

It can validate the following KPIs in UC2: KPI_UC2_5 (successful cooperative manoeuvres), KPI_UC2_6 (collision risk_reaction time).

3.4. Trial Results

In this section, we present the results of the Test Cases proposed for UC3 in D5.1 [4]. The results have been obtained through analysis of the previous data sets.

3.4.1. Test Case for KPI_P_1 Service Availability in UC2

Service availability refers to the percentage of time our system remains fully operational and accessible during the defined observation period. It is evaluated during field trials conducted at the Barcelona test site, using real operational conditions to determine the robustness and reliability of the system.

Method of calculation

The infrastructure is instrumented to capture and record system status at 10-second intervals, generating a continuous log of operational data. By analysing this log, we are able to identify periods of service degradation or downtime with high temporal accuracy. Since system monitoring is enabled only on designated testing days, our analysis focuses exclusively on the log data generated during the most recent testing event, ensuring that all findings and conclusions are based on the latest available operational snapshot.

Table 9: TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC2			
Materials used	Gateway/MQTT logs			
KPI	KPI_P_1 serviceAvailability in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	Total time	Downtime	Availability	
	86400 s	0 s	100%	

Plot

Figure 31: Service availability of the system.

Conclusions

No service interruptions or performance downtimes were detected throughout the entire test day. This outcome indicates that the system operated consistently within expected performance thresholds and demonstrated a high level of robustness under the observed conditions. The absence of failures during the monitoring window reinforces confidence in the system’s stability and its ability to maintain reliable service during critical operational periods.

3.4.2. Test Case for KPI_P_2 Update Latency in UC2

This KPI is defined as the time interval between the moment a vehicle transmits a CAM message and the moment that same message becomes available within the MEC environment. The latency is measured starting from the instant the message is created by the vehicle and ending when it is received and recorded in the infrastructure deployed at the MEC. The appearance of the message in the MEC means that it has successfully traversed the communication (via 5G or via C-V2X) and processing pipeline and is now accessible to all applications hosted on the MEC platform.

Method of calculation

To compute this KPI, the infrastructure log data was analysed to determine the lifetime of each message. Specifically, the lifetime is calculated as the difference between the timestamp at which the message is received at the MEC and the *generationDeltaTime* field contained within the CAM. This method provides an accurate measurement of the end-to-end delay experienced by each message as it travels from the vehicle to the MEC platform. It is important to note that these measurements include messages received at the MEC not only through 5G connectivity but also via C-V2X. As a result, the computed KPI reflects the combined performance of both communication paths, offering a comprehensive view of message propagation behaviour under real operational conditions.

Table 10: TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC2			
Materials used	CV published CAM messages over 5G using a 5G router and over C-V2X using a Cohda MK6 OBU. Vehicle and MEC infrastructure were time-synchronized via Network Time Protocol (NTP) to ensure consistent timestamp alignment.			
KPI	KPI_P_2 updateLatency in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	199522	155.30 ms	151.0 ms	45.39 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	301 ms	57 ms	[155.1, 155.5] ms	233 ms

Plot

Figure 32: Boxplot of the update latency through the transmission of CAM messages, in milliseconds.

Conclusions

As shown in the graph, most samples exhibit an end-to-end latency below 200 ms from vehicle to infrastructure. Although this remains within the acceptable KPI thresholds [50 ms, 2.5 s], the overall latency level is relatively high. This can be attributed primarily to the characteristics of the private 5G SA network used during the project, which presented elevated latency, most likely due to network QoS configurations or available bandwidth.

Additionally, the standard deviation observed in the results is notably high. This variation is mainly caused by the combination of C-V2X and 5G-based message transmissions, which inherently have different latency profiles. The coexistence of these two communication technologies introduces variability in message delivery times, reflected in the dispersion of the measured samples.

To achieve a stricter target, such as the widely adopted 100 ms for real-time C-ITS awareness applications, it will be necessary to optimise the transport of C-ITS messages, particularly over the private 5G network. This will ensure the robustness and responsiveness required for time-critical decisions, especially in scenarios 1 (EV prioritisation) and 3 (VRU protection), where lower CAM latencies are necessary.

3.4.3. Test Case for KPI_P_3 Notification Latency in UC2

Notification Latency is defined as the time interval between the transmission of a DENM message by the MEC and its availability within the vehicle. This latency is measured from the instant the message is first published on the MEC until it is received and validated by the vehicle. The presence of the message in the vehicle’s broker signifies that it is accessible to all applications hosted on the vehicle platform. This metric provides a clear measure of the system’s responsiveness to deliver real-time notifications from the edge infrastructure to connected vehicles, end-to-end communication chain.

Method of calculation

To measure this latency, vehicle log data was analysed to calculate the time difference between the reception timestamp of a DENM message, received via either C-V2X or 5G, and the *referenceTime* field contained within the DENM. This approach enables an accurate measurement of the total elapsed time from the creation of the DENM at the MEC to its reception and validation by the vehicle, providing a clear indication of the system’s end-to-end notification performance.

Table 11: TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC2			
Materials used	The infrastructure gateway generates DENMs, which are received by the vehicle via a 5G router or a Cohda MK6 OBU (C-V2X). Vehicle and infrastructure are time-synchronized via NTP.			
KPI	KPI_P_3 notificationLatency in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	2230	217.79 ms	213 ms	28.73 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	314 ms	133 ms	[216.6, 218.9] ms	275.55 ms

Plot

Figure 33: Boxplot of the notification latency through the transmission of DENM messages, in milliseconds.

Conclusions

Similar to the previous KPI (KPI_P_2: Update Latency for UC2), the observed Notification Latency exhibits a higher-than-expected mean and standard deviation. This is primarily due to the characteristics of the private 5G network and the use of hybrid communications (C-V2X and 5G). Despite this variability, the KPI remains within the defined target limits [50 ms, 2.5 s], confirming that system performance meets the required general specifications.

In conclusion, the data validly represents the current system performance. However, to enable the required responsiveness for emergency vehicle prioritisation and VRU protection scenarios, optimisation is necessary to reduce latency closer to the operational target of 100 ms.

3.4.4. Test Case for KPI_P_4 Processing Delay in UC2

Processing delay is the elapsed processing time from hazard detection to the point at which the CCAM DENM becomes available for delivery, excluding any transport latency. It is measured within the MEC and covers application layer ingestion, validation/fusion, prioritisation, encoding and security signing, including internal queuing. It excludes radio access, IP transport and core/backhaul functions. Start time: hazard detection timestamp at MEC ingress; end time: DENM handed over or queued to the outbound stack.

Method of calculation

Processing delay is computed as the difference between the hazard detection generation timestamp and the message processing completion timestamp, both recorded within the MEC. This yields the elapsed time from event creation to the DENM being ready for delivery, using synchronised timestamps.

Table 12: TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC2			
Materials used	Two cameras connected to the MEC over Ethernet. Video analytics service running on the MEC ingests the camera streams and produces detections for subsequent processing. VRU and CVs.			
KPI	KPI_P_4 - processingDelay in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	276	57.74 ms	57.14 ms	31.13 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	115.03 ms	8.38 ms	[52.51, 62.97] ms	106.43 ms

Plot

Figure 34: Processing Delay Distribution of Detections.

Figure 35: Frequency Distribution for Detections.

Conclusions

The verification criterion required processing delays within 50 ms to 2.5 s. This target was met, with mean values close to the lower bound of the range. These results indicate strong scalability: increasing detection volumes is expected to have only a marginal impact on processing delay and overall service performance.

3.4.5. Test Case for KPI_P_5 Communication Reliability in UC2

In UC2, the Communication Reliability KPI is derived from measurements of the platform’s capability to successfully transmit messages between vehicles and the MEC, considering both uplink and downlink directions. The metric is calculated as the ratio of successfully delivered messages to the total number of transmitted messages, providing a quantitative assessment of the overall reliability of the communication process. This KPI offers insight into the consistency and dependability of message delivery across the different communication technologies employed in the system.

Method of calculation

To compute this KPI, the messages transmitted by the vehicles were compared against those successfully received by the MEC platform, and conversely, the messages sent by the MEC were compared against those received by the vehicles. This bidirectional comparison allows for an accurate determination of the fraction of successfully delivered messages, providing a clear measure of the communication reliability in both transmission directions.

Since not all DENM messages generated by the MEC are relevant to a given vehicle due to their spatial proximity with the referenced event, the communication reliability analysis was restricted to DENMs associated with events occurring within a 100 m radius of the vehicle. This spatial filtering ensures that the computed reliability KPI accounts only for messages that the vehicle could realistically receive, thereby providing a more accurate and representative assessment of communication performance within the operational area.

Table 13: TC_KPI_P_5-communicationReliability in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_5-communicationReliability in UC2			
Materials used	Vehicle with 5G router and MK6 Cohda OBU. MEC.			
KPI	KPI_P_5 communicationReliability in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Sent messages	Received messages	Reliability
	63321 CAMS + 1037 DENM	64358	63757	99.06%

Conclusions

A message loss rate below 1% is considered within the defined target range, demonstrating that the communication system achieves the expected level of reliability. This evaluation encompasses messages transmitted through both 5G and C-V2X technologies, ensuring that the metric reflects the performance of all communication channels employed in the system. Furthermore, the reported reliability percentage represents the overall system performance, accounting for both downlink and uplink transmissions. As such, it provides a comprehensive view of the platform’s ability to consistently deliver messages between the MEC and vehicles under real operational conditions.

3.4.6. Test Case for KPI_UC2_1 Traffic_light_flow_improvement in UC2

The purpose of this KPI is to measure the improvement in the percentage of times that EVs find green light when they arrive at a controlled intersection that is caused by the enhancement of EV priority management applied within UC2.

The preexisting priority management in Barcelona made use of a prognosis method to estimate the arrival time of EVs at each of the intersections of the corridor followed by those EVs. Thanks to PoDIUM integration, the system received the position of each EV in real time and calculated the estimated arrival time of each EV to each intersection taking the most recent position into account, which is expected to provide a greater accuracy, and a higher probability of EV finding green lights.

Method of calculation

Due to the limited availability of EV for the execution of the pilot tests, it was not possible to execute baseline test as originally planned in the description of the KPI in D5.1. Instead of that, an alternative calculation design was made. This calculation consisted of comparing actual pass time of the EV through each of the intersections in the corridor with both the actual priority activation and deactivation times in the real experiment and the hypothetical activation and deactivation times in case only the preexisting priority management had been used.

For this calculation, the following logs have been used:

- Logs of the CAM messages sent by the firefighters control system to the PoDIUM platform with the position of each EV every two seconds.
- Logs of the specific messages sent by the firefighters control system to the PoDIUM platform with the activation and cancellation of the emergency corridor.
- Logs of the TMC system processing the position of the vehicle and calculating the prognosis.
- Logs of the TMC activation of and deactivation of priority at each intersection.

In the following figures the X axis corresponds to the time since the beginning and the corridor and the Y axis the distance of the position of the emergency vehicle or the intersection along the corridor. The movement of the EV is represented by a blue or purple line, while activation and deactivation of the

priority is represented by green and red lines (activation/deactivation time vs distance of the intersection along the corridor).

Figure 36 and Figure 37 display the result of two of the experiments, showing how the activation and deactivation adapted dynamically to the real movement of the vehicle and the instant at which the vehicle arrived at each intersection was, with enough margin, included between the activation and deactivation time. Figure 38 displays the hypothetical results for a baseline case. We assumed that the movement of the vehicle along the corridor would had been the same as in the experiments, while the activation and deactivation would had occurred according to the preexisting system prognosis.

Figure 36: UC2 Priority management example from PDI experiment 11.11.25 15:16h.

Figure 37: UC2 Priority management example from PDI experiment 30.10.25 10:54h.

Figure 38: UC2 Baseline priority management examples.

The graphs show that, in real experiments, the circumstances of the traffic made the EV run at lower speed than the predicted by the prognosis, and that for the final half of the corridor the vehicle would have arrived at the intersections when the priority would have been already deactivated.

In a real baseline experiment, the movement of the vehicle in the first half of the corridor would have been (approximately) like the one of the PDI experiment, because the EV would have found green in the intersections, while in the second half it would have advanced even more slowly because of red traffic lights. Therefore, the assumption made for the calculation of the evaluation PDI is less optimistic than the calculation with a real baseline experiment would have been.

The results of the comparisons described above have been translated into a percentage of times that the EV crossed an intersection between the activation and deactivation instants of the priority for that experiment and intersection. These percentages have been calculated for the PDI and the baseline cases and compared, obtaining the value of the KPI as the difference between the two percentages.

Table 14: TC_KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement in UC2			
Materials used	One connected EV vehicle was used for the tests, equipped with GNSS and a router. This EV send its position to the firefighters control system, which in turn sent CAM messages to the UC2 system cloud, that fed the TMC system implementing the priority.			
KPI	KPI_UC2_1 Traffic_light_flow_improvement in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	#baseline samples	#baseline success	%baseline success
	175	89	40	44.9%
	#PDI samples	#PDI success	%PID success	Improvement
	86	83	96.5%	51.6%

Plot

Figure 39: Plot displaying KPI_UC2_1 results.

Conclusions

The effect of the application of the PDI was a very significant increase in the probability for an EV to arrive at intersections with the traffic lights priority activated. The increase (51.6%) is above the 10% that was defined in D5.1 as “**Very good**” result for this PDI.

3.4.7. Test Case for KPI_UC2_2 Percentage_trips_ok_OD in UC2

This KPI represents the percentage of trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS when generating O-D matrix data.

The CV position (CAM message) information was collected by the Vehicle Manager and processed by the service in the TMC in charge of generating O-D matrices. This was done by identifying the position of vehicle(s) when they started to send CAM messages and started to move and the position where they made a long stop or stopped sending CAM messages for a long time.

The positions were matched with the geometry of origin and destination zones in the TMC data.

Method of calculation

The following logs were used to calculate the KPI:

- Logs of CAM messages received from the CV.
- Logs of trip events (start and end of trips) detected by the TMC, with their instants, duration, distance run and coordinates.
- Content of the TMC database were the O-D matrix results collected, once the trip events were aggregated per sample period.

The coordinates of the positions of in CAM message for each of the 19 trips of the experiment were represented geographically (Figure 40) to check that the information in the trip detection events were consistent with these positions.

The shape of TMC O-D zones were also represented (Figure 41), to check that the origin and destination zones of trip events were consistent with the aggregated data stored in the O-D matrix results table in the database of the TMC.

Figure 40: Representation of some of the test trips (the letter is the start point and the flag the end point of each trip) together with the O-D zones in the Barcelona TMC, one of the steps of calculation of KPI UC2_2. Green and red bands correspond to another KPI.

The value of the KPI was obtained by calculating the percentage of the test trips in which O-D were correctly identified and processed in the calculation of O-D matrices.

Figure 41: Representation of O-D matrix data generated by the TMC during the tests, also used for the calculation of KP UC2_2.

Table 15: TC_KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD in UC2			
Materials used	One connected vehicle was used for the tests, equipped with a mobile phone that ran an application that sent CAM messages to the UC2 system cloud			
KPI	KPI_UC2_2 Percentage_trips_ok_OD in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Successful	Failed	Success rate
	19	18	1	95%

Plot

Figure 42: Percentage of trips correctly processed of O-D (KPI UC2_2).

Conclusions

A very high proportion of the trips done during the tests were correctly processed and the 95% value defined as success value for KPI UC2_2 in D5.1 [6] has been reached.

In fact, the only one trip that was not correctly processed was due to an incorrect design of that particular test, as the locations chosen as origin and destination were too near to each and caused the trip to be rejected by the TMC as not relevant of the purpose of the generation of an O-D matrix.

3.4.8. Test Case for KPI_UC2_3 Percentage_trips_ok_delay in UC2

This KPI represents the percentage of travel times across road links correctly processed by the TMS.

The CV position (CAM message) information was collected by the Vehicle Manager and processed by the service in the TMC in charge of generating average travel times per road segment (also called "links"). This was done by identifying the position and instant of vehicle(s) when they arrived at the beginning of a road segment and the left the road segment or crossed the destination intersection.

The "delay" was also calculated from the travel time, by comparing the travel time with the time to run the same distance at a standard speed and considering the difference as a delay if the measured travel time was higher.

Method of calculation

The following logs were used to calculate the KPI:

- Logs of CAM messages received from the CV.
- Logs of trip events along road segments detected by the TMC, with their instants, duration, distance run and coordinates.

Content of the TMC database were the travel time results collected and aggregated per sample period.

For traffic control strategic reason, the TMC is interested only in a part of the road segments in the traffic network, and only those were included in the TMC data model and, consequently, in the results of the PoDIUM experiment.

The coordinates of the positions of in CAM messages for each of the 19 trips of the experiment were represented geographically to check that the information in the trip detection events were consistent with these positions. The representation included the trajectory along each of the road segments, coloured depending on whether they were correctly processed or if they were considered invalid (Figure 43). The shape of the road segments in the TMC data model was also represented to identify the cause of any possible incorrect detection and to see or if any road segment was ignored.

Figure 43: Representation of the trajectory of the CV within one of the tests, with the road segments in TMC data model in cyan and trips along trips with green (correctly processed) or red (anomalous).

As it can be seen in Figure 44, some of the detections as invalid (red) in logs were actually correct, because they corresponded to places where the vehicle trajectory crossed transversally or touched tangentially the corresponding road segment.

In other cases, the trajectory of the vehicle along a road segment was not correctly processed due to, for example, the imprecision of the GNSS position received and/or the imprecision of the shape of the road segment present in the TMC data model.

Figure 44: Example of test trip along a road segment that was incorrectly processed.

A table was produced with the accounting of correct or wrong road segment (also called *links*) identification to calculate the proportion that defines the KPI.

The statistics classified the trips in 4 categories:

- Processed OK and computed: trips along road segments that had to be computed by the TMC and were
- Discarded OK: trips tangential or transversal to road segments that had to be discarded by the TMC and were.
- Discarded Error: trips along road segments that had to be computed by the TMC and were not.
- Ignored road segments: trips along road segments that were not computed in any way. This did not happen in any case.

Table 16 presents the results. The first row contains the values for the calculation of the KPI (Success rate), for which the "Discarded OK" trips were not considered because, strictly speaking, they were not trips that had to participate in traffic metrics calculations. The second row displays the values taking also those trips into consideration.

Table 16: TC_KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay in UC2			
Materials used	One connected vehicle was used for the tests, equipped with a mobile phone that run an application that sent CAM messages to the UC2 system cloud			
KPI	KPI_UC2_3 Percentage_trips_ok_delay in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Trips correctly processed and computed for traffic metrics	Trips incorrectly processed	Success rate
	80	72	8	90%
	Trips correctly discarded	Trips correctly computed or discarded	Total trips	Correct computation rate
	58	130	138	94%

Plots

Figure 45 shows the KPI results strictly considering the trips along road segments that should have been computed by the TMC for the calculation of traffic metrics.

Figure 45: Plot displaying KPI UC2_3 results.

Figure 46 illustrates in detail the results of the tests, considering all the situations, including the trips correctly discarded. Figure 47 provides a less strict metric of the test success, considering all trips.

Figure 46: Plot detailing the different cases considered in KPI UC2_3 calculations.

Figure 47: Computation results plot (considering all trips).

Figure 48 displays the proportion of the causes for the wrong processing of trips: imprecision of the TMC road segments model, imprecision of the GNSS signal or both.

Figure 48: Proportions of causes of wrong trip processing (details for KPI UC2_3).

Conclusions

As shown in Table 16 a high proportion of the trips were correctly processed. However, the ambitious success rate (95%) defined in deliverable D5.1 [6] was not reached, due to two aspects of the pilot that, as a lesson learned, should have been improved:

- The precision of the Global Positioning System (GPS) instrument of the CV used for this kind of tests.
- The precision of the shape of the road segments in the TMC data model, enough for other functionalities of this system but not for the functionality involved in these tests.

3.4.9. Test Case for KPI_UC2_4 EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction in UC2

One of the expected effects of the improvement in the management of traffic lights priority for EVs is that, being able to predict the arrival time of EVs at the intersection with high accuracy, there is no need for long guard times, this is, to need to activate the priority some seconds long before nor to deactivate it long after the estimated arrival time of the EV to each intersection. Long guard times were required by the preexisting priority management to avoid estimation inaccuracy cause EVs finding the priority deactivated at their arrival at intersections. Those long guard times increase the impact of EV priority on the traffic, because they make red traffic light times for streets transversal to the EV corridor much longer than usual.

The purpose of this KPI is measuring in which proportion PoDIUM UC2 can allow decreasing those guard times and reduce the impact of EV priority in the traffic.

Method of calculation

The same as for KPI_UC2_1, the short availability of emergency vehicles for the tests did not allow running the iterative tests initially designed to calculate this KPI in D5.1 [6]. Instead of that, an alternative calculation design was made.

This design makes use of the data collected during pilot experiments to make the best possible estimation of how much guard time might be reduced without compromising the accomplishment of the main purpose of the priority.

The chosen approach consisted in calculating, for each test execution and each intersection crossed, an "optimal activation time" and an "optimal deactivation time" based on:

- The actual time spent by the EV to run along the road segment approaching the intersection. This time is relevant, because if the traffic light is already green when the EV arrives at the beginning of that road segment it has much smaller probability to find stopped or slow vehicles in front of the EV.

- A guard time of 20s for activating the priority in advance and 15s for deactivating it after the crossing of the vehicle, to provide the priority management with some margin in case of some unexpected situation.

The difference between this optimal duration and the actual duration during each experiment has been calculated for each case, in percentage, and the average of this percentage has been taken for the value of the KPI, thus considered a good measurement of the reduction of the impact of EV priority in the rest of the traffic that can be provided by the improved management of priority implemented within PoDIUM UC2.

Figure 49 shows this approach graphically, with time in X axis and position of the intersection in the Y axis. Green and red lines represent the activation and deactivation time respectively of the priority for each intersection. Dark blue line represents the pass time of the vehicle crossing the intersection. Light blue line represents the optimal activation instant and pink line the optimal deactivation instant.

Figure 49: Calculation procedure for KPI_UC2_4.

The calculation of the KPI was made by calculating the proportion of the time between the green and cyan line plus the time between the pink and red line with regards to the total time between the green and red lines. The average of this proportion for all the experiments and all the intersection was calculated to obtain the value of the KPI, considered as the percentage of possible reduction of traffic impact that can be provided by the UC2 EV priority service.

For this calculation, the following logs have been used:

- Logs of the CAM messages sent by the firefighters control system to the PoDIUM platform with the position of each EV every two seconds.
- Logs of the specific messages sent by the firefighters control system to the PoDIUM platform with the activation and cancellation of the emergency corridor.
- Logs of the TMC system processing the position of the vehicle and calculating the prognosis.
- Logs of the TMC activation of and deactivation of priority at each intersection.
- Logs from the traffic controllers with the colour of the traffic lights at each instant.

Table 17: TC_KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction in UC2			
Materials used	One connected EV vehicle was used for the tests, equipped with GNSS that run and a router. This EV send its position to the firefighters control system, which in turn sent CAM messages to the UC2 system cloud, that fed the TMC system implementing the priority.			
KPI	KPI_UC2_4 EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	41	53.8%	51.8%	7.9%
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	78.1%	42.1%	[51.4, 56.2] %	65.3%

Plots

Figure 50: Whiskers box plot for KPI_UC2_4.

Figure 51: Histogram for KPI_UC2_4.

Conclusions

The results obtained for KPI_UC2_4 show clearly that the PoDIUM EV priority management service is capable, not only to facilitate the movement of emergency vehicles (as indicated by KPI_UC2_1) but also reduce the impact of such priority in the rest of the traffic. Considering the criterion defined in D5.1, the 25% target value for success has been clearly surpassed, reaching above 50%.

3.4.10. Test Case for KPI_UC2_5 EV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2

This KPI has been obtained twice, first based on the tests carried out in Barcelona in real traffic conditions, and secondly based on the tests carried out in the UTAC circuit with the MILLA CAV.

1- KPI calculation from the tests in real traffic conditions in Barcelona

This KPI represents the percentage of coincidences for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV.

Method of calculation

This KPI is designed to validate the effectiveness of the system in notifying CVs about the presence of an EV. It is measured by comparing the total number of test runs involving the EV against the subset of runs in which the corresponding notification was successfully displayed on the vehicle's HMI. This metric provides a clear indication of the system's ability to deliver timely and actionable alerts to drivers, ensuring that critical safety information reaches its intended recipients during operational scenarios.

Table 18: TC_KPI_UC2_5-EV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_5-EV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2		
Materials used	CV with 5G router and smartphone/tablet as HMI		
KPI	KPI_UC2_5 EV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2		
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Successful Runs	% Successful runs
	5	5	100 %

Conclusions

All test runs involving the EV were successfully detected and notifications were displayed in the CV. The total number of runs was relatively low because the tests required the availability of a real EV from Bombers de Barcelona (Barcelona Fire Department truck), which was limited. Despite the small sample size, the results confirm the effectiveness of the notification system under real operational conditions.

2- KPI calculation from the tests in the UTAC closed circuit

In this case the tests involved the successful execution of cooperative manoeuvres of the MILLA CAV for the three scenarios: EV prioritisation, traffic optimisation and VRU protection. The detailed description of each scenario is available in section 3.3.

Method of calculation

The success of individual test runs is evaluated qualitatively by at least one expert and partners and displayed in the CAV. The cooperatives manoeuvres are applied at a defined location on closed circuit. When the conditions are fulfilled and according to the test procedure sequence described in section 3.3, the experts and partners verify that the CAVs successfully perform the cooperative manoeuvre.

Table 19: TC_KPI_UC2_7-CAV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_7-CAV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2			
Materials used	Milla CAV including Milla native autonomous system with 5G network communication and Cohda OBU integrated with Flexstack. Communication infrastructure via orange public 5G network and virtual RSUs (JSON files in absence of physical MEC infrastructure).			
KPI	KPI_UC2_7 CAV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics	# tests	# successful manoeuvres	# failed manoeuvres	Success rate
	10	10	0	100%

Conclusions

As can be seen in Table 19, ten manoeuvres were marked as successful during the test runs, resulting in a success rate of 100%. According to the verification criterion, the KPI has been met.

3.4.11. Test Case for KPI_UC2_6 Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2

This KPI has been obtained twice, first based on the tests carried out in Barcelona in real traffic conditions, and secondly based on the tests carried out in the UTAC circuit with the MILLA CAV.

1-KPI calculation from the tests in real traffic conditions in Barcelona

The purpose of the test is to calculate the average improvement in safety margin achieved by CVs equipped with C-V2X when a collision with a VRU is predicted, compared to a baseline vehicle. This KPI quantifies the earlier intervention capability provided by the C-V2X system, thereby measuring its effectiveness. An effective C-V2X system allows the vehicle/driver to initiate evasive action or deceleration sooner, reducing the time or distance needed for a safe reaction and increasing the safety margin.

Method of calculation

The KPI is calculated as the average percentage improvement in the relevant safety metric (distance to collision) achieved by the C-V2X system compared to the baseline scenario. The original KPI definition focused on reducing the required reaction time (based on time to collision). Following a revision of the evaluation plan, the final calculation uses a distance metric (distance to collision) to measure the percentage reduction in the required reaction distance. This shifts the measurement from the temporal safety margin to the spatial safety margin. The objective remains to demonstrate a positive percentage improvement, indicating a successful reduction in necessary reaction effort.

Table 20: TC_KPI_UC2_6-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_6-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2			
Materials used	PDI needed to measure the relative position of the objects: C-V2X Test Vehicle (CV) equipped with the safety application (HMI), VRU (bike rider in this case), and GPS positioning system on both (OBU in the CV, VRU-App in the biker). This hardware captures the precise distance to collision at the moment of intervention versus the baseline.			
KPI	KPI_UC2_6 Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics for the baseline scenario	# rounds	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	27.49 m	27.28 m	2.03 m
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	30.13 m	25.28 m	[24.27, 30.71] m	29.77 m
Descriptive Statistics for the C-V2X scenario	# rounds	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	39.69 m	38.76 m	3.67 m
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	44.91 m	36.33 m	[33.85, 45.52] m	44,01 m

Plot

Figure 52: Box plot of distance to potential impact (collision point) comparing baseline and C-V2X scenarios.

Conclusions

The evaluation of four test runs shows that the C-V2X system achieved an average gain in the reaction distance metric, which is interpreted as a successful reduction in the required reaction distance compared to the baseline.

In all tested scenarios, the C-V2X functionality provided a substantial safety margin advantage, demonstrating the system's effectiveness in initiating an alert or response significantly earlier than the baseline. This reduces the reaction time required by the vehicle or driver by an average of 45.62%. As the established target for time reduction was 20%, it can be concluded that the test was successful, since the improvement in reaction distance exceeds the time reduction target. This means that the warning is issued earlier and, considering the vehicle is moving at a constant speed before reacting,

the vehicle is also further away from the collision point at the moment of the warning. In short, by having an earlier warning, the safety system reduces the urgency of the situation.

2- KPI calculation from the tests in the UTAC closed circuit

Test if a CAV can anticipate the risk of collision by receiving DENM message from the MEC in the "VRU protection" scenario. The detailed description and test procedure sequence of "Collision risk alert" scenario are available in section 3.3.

Method of calculation

For this test, the baseline test involved replacing the RSU with a VRU (a pedestrian) so that the shuttle could react autonomously to a collision risk and stop safely.

The test procedure sequence of the "VRU protection" scenario is available in section 3.3.

Table 21: TC_KPI_UC2_6-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_6-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2			
Materials used	MILLA CAV including MILLA native autonomous system with 5G network communication and Cohda OBU integrated with FlexStack. Communication infrastructure via orange public 5G network and virtual RSUs (JSON files in absence of physical MEC infrastructure).			
KPI	KPI_UC2_6 Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics for the baseline scenario	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	420.75 ms	409 ms	45.83 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	483	382	[398.29, 443.21] ms	474.6 ms
Descriptive Statistics for the C-V2X scenario	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	329 ms	321,5 ms	30.69 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	371 ms	302 ms	[313.96, 344.04] ms	365.2 ms

Plot

Figure 53: Boxplot of the CAV braking reaction time (in ms) for baseline and for the cooperative manoeuvre "VRU protection" scenario.

Figure 54: Histogram of the reduction (in percentage) of the CAV breaking reaction time to collision between baseline and the cooperative manoeuvre "collision risk alert" scenario.

Conclusions

As seen in Table 21 during the test runs, the CAV anticipates better the collision with a cooperative manoeuvre (by receiving DENM message/alert). Figure 53 and Figure 54 show that the CAV reaction (braking) time reduction is greater than or equal to 20%. According to the verification criterion require, the KPI_UC2_6_Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction for the use case is met.

3.4.12. Test Case for KPI_UC2_7 Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_s after_deceleration in UC2

The purpose of the test is to calculate the reduction in deceleration severity required by the equipped CV to avoid a high-risk collision with a VRU. The aim is to minimise the number of instances of hard braking in the C-V2X scenario compared to the baseline.

If a positive reduction is achieved, it means that the C-V2X system is effectively leveraging its earlier warning capability to enable smoother, safer and more comfortable braking manoeuvres.

Method of calculation

The KPI is calculated as the average percentage reduction in the deceleration value required by the vehicle in the C-V2X scenario compared to the baseline scenario. The final KPI value is the average of the individual percentage reductions.

Table 22: TC_KPI_UC2_7-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration in UC2.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC2_7-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration in UC2			
Materials used	The materials used for calculating the KPI rely on specialized equipment to measure vehicle dynamics. The physical infrastructure necessary for generating this data also involves an equipped CV with C-V2X and the safety application (HMI).			
KPI	KPI_UC2_7 Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration in UC2			
Descriptive Statistics for the baseline scenario	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	3.27 m/s ²	3.27 m/s ²	0.59 m/s ²
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	2.61 m/s ²	3.94 m/s ²	[2.34, 4.21] m/s ²	3.88 m/s ²
Descriptive Statistics for the C-V2X scenario	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	2.23 m/s ²	2.22 m/s ²	0.73 m/s ²
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	2.90 m/s ²	1.59 m/s ²	[1.08, 3.39] m/s ²	2.896 m/s ²

Plot

Figure 55: Box plot of braking deceleration comparing baseline and C-V2X scenarios.

Conclusions

The achieved average reduction of 32.83% (from 3.27 to 2.23 m/s²) significantly exceeds the minimum established threshold of 20%. This demonstrates that the C-V2X system successfully facilitates a substantial shift away from hard braking events towards much softer, safer, and more comfortable deceleration profiles.

3.5. Conclusions

Based on the evaluation analysis provided in the previous sections, the following conclusions can be drawn for UC2. These conclusions are derived from definitive tests conducted in Barcelona under real traffic conditions and complemented by tests of CAV functionalities at the UTAC closed circuit in France.

Before we proceed with the technical evaluation, here are some conclusions regarding the potential needs, challenges, and strategic goals identified in deliverable D2.1 [1].

Achievement of potential needs, challenges and strategic goals

In D2.1 [1], we identified the following **potential needs**, which have been successfully addressed during the project's development:

- To set up a complex and realistic traffic environment for testing with CVs, CAVs and VRUs: This was achieved by deploying the UC in the Gran Via corridor in the heart of Barcelona, integrating CVs and EVs into live traffic.
- To Set up the Digital Twin integrating the road network and users (CVs and VRUs): The MISTRAL Smart Mobility Platform successfully acted as the Digital Twin, integrating real-time data from the TMS and CVs.
- To integrate and process data from multiple sources: High Definition (HD) cameras, vehicles, road users, and third-party services: This was successfully tested and demonstrated in the third scenario, which included integration with third-party services such as the Google Firebase service.

- To adapt local recommendations for different types of vehicles and road users: the system provide context-aware and personalized safety/efficiency messages based on the road user type (CV/CAV, EV or VRU).
- Modify traffic plans according to needs (priority): The system has successfully demonstrated its ability to dynamically adjust traffic light phases for EVs, thereby enhancing green light performance (reported in sections 3.3, 3.4.6 and 3.4.9).
- Exchange real-time information with the TMS: Vehicles successfully shared speed, location and O-D data, enabling the TMS to process trip data with high accuracy (reported in sections 3.3, 3.4.7 and 3.4.8).
- All messages used in infrastructure to vehicle (I2V) or vehicle to vehicle (V2V) communications are based on European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) standards, as CAM and DENM.

To fulfil these needs, we anticipated several **potential challenges**, as outlined in D2.1 [1], which have been effectively managed:

- Data accuracy and reliability: Despite the challenges posed by the urban corridor environment, the system achieved a high communication reliability rate and sufficient accuracy in trip processing.
- Integration of diverse data sources: The platform successfully fused data from various sources, including high-definition AI cameras, CV OBUs, and the Barcelona's Traffic Management System.
- Coordination among stakeholders: The pilot successfully coordinated real-time operations between emergency services (Barcelona Fire Service), traffic management authorities (Barcelona Department of Mobility), and PoDIUM research partners.
- Privacy and security concerns: The Barcelona City Council and ETRA signed agreements to comply with local, regional, and national General Data Protection Regulation [11] and security [12] legislation.

Overall, we have successfully achieved the **strategic goals** defined in D2.1 [1]. Below are the conclusions regarding their attainment, based on the results obtained so far

- Traffic Management optimization and efficient decision-making based on a Digital Twin on the Cloud: Validated in scenario 2 tests and demonstration through the successful generation of O-D matrices and delay computations based on CV data (reported sections 3.3, 3.4.7 and 3.4.8).
- Advanced VRU detection and protection based on AI cameras and CCAM: Achieved in scenario 3 tests and demonstration through the AI-camera based detection system, the Collision Risk Estimator functionality and C-V2X communication with CVs and VRUs, which increased the safety margin (distance to collision and decreased braking) (reported in sections 3.3, 3.4.11 and 3.4.12).
- Priority at intersections for connected emergency vehicles: Successfully demonstrated by reducing the impact on crossing traffic (guard times) while ensuring EV priority (reported in sections 3.3, 3.4.6 and 3.4.9).
- Accidents minimization in complex urban conditions such as emergency situation: It is assumed that scenario 3 (VRU protection) will contribute to this goal, given that the system has been tested and validated for its ability to trigger softer, earlier deceleration in collision risk scenarios. This was tested in a complex intersection with dense traffic and VRU movement patterns (reported in sections 3.3, 3.4.11 and 3.4.12).
- Congestion reduction in complex urban conditions such as emergency situations: Scenario 2 (traffic optimisation) is expected to contribute to this goal, given that the system has been tested and validated in a complex urban dense area for identifying congestion events from CV data,

and for issuing warnings to these vehicles so they can be rerouted (reported in sections 3.3, 3.4.7 and 3.4.8).

Technical evaluation

Overall conclusion: The evaluation of UC2 was highly successful, validating the ability of the PoDIUM architecture to enhance urban mobility through three key scenarios: Emergency vehicle prioritisation, traffic optimisation and VRU protection.

The Barcelona trials successfully obtained the required data and met all target KPIs using CVs and real infrastructure in a complex urban environment (the Gran Via corridor). The UTAC trials amplified and complemented these results by validating the specific automated responses of the MILLA CAV (SAE L4), which could not operate in Barcelona due to permit restrictions.

The project has achieved the following **key technological advancements** through the development and successful evaluation of this UC2:

Communications:

- Hybrid PDI gateway: A C-V2X and 5G (SA) hybrid gateway was developed that successfully managed C-ITS message transmission. This achieved 100% service availability and over 99% communication reliability in a real-world urban corridor.
- Low-latency dissemination: A communication protocol stack compliant with ETSI standards was established that demonstrated MEC processing fast and reliable enough to maintain notification latencies for warnings of just over 200 ms. This enabled CV drivers to respond appropriately without compromising safety or efficiency in the tested scenarios.

ITS applications:

- Dynamic strategy and prioritisation: A dynamic traffic strategy management system was developed that can calculate the optimal green wave priority for emergency vehicles. This has been proven to increase the probability of emergency vehicles getting a green light by 51.6% and significantly reduce overall traffic disruption by 53.8%. Successfully testing cooperative manoeuvres with CVs/CAVs contributes to reducing emergency response times along urban corridors.
- Cooperative VRU safety system: A VRU risk assessment and alerting system was tested that fuses AI cameras and vehicle data. This system has successfully reduced safety risks by increasing the safety margin (distance to collision) by around 45% and enabling smoother reactions, with deceleration intensity reduced by around 33%.
- Real-time data collection: A cooperative awareness system was implemented that successfully processed connected vehicle data. This allowed the Traffic Management System to compute accurate origin-destination and delay metrics for over 94% of vehicle trips, enabling real-time traffic monitoring. Additionally, successfully testing rerouting manoeuvres based on traffic alerts can help reduce congestion in dense urban areas.

Autonomous vehicle:

- CAV integration: Successfully integrated the L4 CAV to interpret infrastructure-generated DENMs, demonstrating 100% success in autonomously executing the required cooperative and safety manoeuvres (e.g. yielding to EVs and braking safely for VRUs).
- Safety protocol validation: The CAV's ability to perform fail-safe mechanisms, such as an emergency stop when connectivity is lost for more than five seconds, has been verified in compliance with defined regulatory requirements.

Recommendations for the effective deployment of PoDIUM technologies

Based on the execution, insights and evaluation of UC2, valuable lessons were learned, leading to the following recommendations for future deployment and research:

- Testing revealed that, while the hybrid communication architecture (5G SA and C-V2X) achieved safe and reliable performance, the notification latency of around 200 ms was higher than desired and more variable than expected. This could negatively impact the performance of time-critical services in more demanding scenarios.

To ensure that latency values approach the operational target of 100 ms, it is recommended to optimize the 5G network configuration by prioritizing QoS profiles for cooperative services and allocating sufficient bandwidth to critical traffic-management applications. This may involve fine-tuning network slicing parameters, ensuring dedicated resources for low-latency communication, and monitoring real-time traffic loads to dynamically adjust capacity. In addition, collaboration with mobile network operators should be pursued to guarantee that service-level agreements explicitly cover latency-sensitive CCAM use cases.

- Regulatory and operational permits: A significant hurdle was the difficulty of obtaining the necessary permits to operate a fully autonomous L4 vehicle (CAV) and conduct test manoeuvres on public roads in Barcelona's complex urban environment. This meant that functional validation of the automated responses had to be carried out on the controlled UTAC circuit.

Regulatory EU-level harmonisation for testing permits is crucial for establishing clear, standardized, and faster procedures for testing CAVs and advanced cooperative functionalities directly on public roads to fully capture real-world performance.

- Data accuracy in complex urban canyons: The accuracy of location-dependent KPIs was marginally impacted by two factors: 1) GPS signal degradation in dense urban canyons, and 2) minor inaccuracies in the TMC digital map model.

To address this, the use of highly accurate GNSS systems for both infrastructure and vehicles should be mandated. Furthermore, to ensure seamless and precise alignment with vehicle-derived positioning data and improve the overall spatial accuracy of the Digital Twin, the digital map used by the TMC must be updated to an HD map standard.

- Scenario and scalability testing: While the core UC2 scenarios were successfully validated, the PDI architecture was not fully tested under extreme load or stress conditions.

Future evaluations must explicitly include stress tests to assess the MEC's scalability limits and robustness when handling a high volume of messages. Testing should also be diversified to encompass more challenging urban operational design domains, such as multi-intersection management, dynamic lane merging and verification in adverse weather conditions.

4. Use Case 3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

4.1. Introduction to the UC

UC3 focuses on developing a system that allows vehicles and road users to collaborate with road operators, facilitating the implementation of real-time traffic management strategies for safer and smoother traffic flow.

The PDI system integrates internal and external data to generate a real-time traffic status overview for each road section, allowing it to calculate potential scenarios and traffic management strategies. In the event of an incident, the PDI swiftly responds by communicating with both approaching vehicles and the vehicle involved. To test this system, two scenarios are implemented:

- 1) Daily commuting service supported by traffic management.
- 2) Safety incidents across borders mitigated through a continuous, efficient, and resilient service.

The use case is implemented in a cross-border corridor to address the challenges of prolonged cellular network service interruptions caused by roaming between international operators. This issue is resolved by deploying RSUs utilizing C-V2X technology in the areas affected by these interruptions.

Three CVs participate in the demonstration, displaying traffic/manoeuvre recommendations from the Traffic Management Centre to their drivers via an HMI.

In addition, the use case features a CAV driving at speeds of up to 80 km/h in autonomous mode, autonomously responding to the recommendations.

In order to enhance the system, VRU protection is considered in the areas where pedestrian board the CAV which, in our scenario, is a shuttle transporting passengers.

Finally, the use case develops a business showcase for an on-demand shuttle service, focussing on commuter clients and packaging transportation

The involved partners are: AAE, ENIDE, i2CAT, IDIADA, ISFM, MILLA, RETE, TENAL and UPC.

The global architecture and its main functional components, which have already been described in D3.3 [3], are illustrated in Figure 56 for ease of reference in this document.

Update of situation in UC3: Due to the impossibility to obtain AD permits in Spain, the following changes in the UC3 demo plan have been implemented:

- 1) The Scenario 1 (on-demand commuting service) is only demonstrated at a closed circuit near Paris, and not real highways in Spain as planned.
- 2) The Scenario 2 is demonstrated in the C32 highway with the 3 CVs, emulating cross-border conditions and without the participation of the CAV.

Figure 56: UC3 functional diagram.

4.2. Completion of integration actions since the last deliverable

The following WP4 actions were completed in the period between the submission of D4.2 [5] and the present deliverable, as well as differences from the original plan, as impacted from the above-described situation.

Integrations

- OBU integration (hardware and software) in the MILLA shuttle was pending finalisation: As mentioned, the AD permits were not obtained for the circulation of the CAV shuttle in Spain. Therefore, the OBU integration was completed in France and tested during the AD demo that took place in November 2025 at the UTAC circuit.
- Route configuration in the Shuttle Passenger App (ENIDE) was pending: Since the Scenario 1 demo will not take place in Spain, the route configured was the test route inside the UTAC circuit, involving a starting point, one intermediary stop and an end point. This was demonstrated successfully on the 7th of November.

Pre-test conditions

Changes in the pre-test conditions as per the Update mentioned above:

- Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials / Highway permits for CAV circulation obtained: No AD permits were obtained for the CAV shuttle in Spain. Rest of permits were obtained successfully, where needed, e.g. for the installation of roadside units and for stopping a test vehicle on the side of the highway (Scenario 2).
- CAV is fully operational in SAE4: This was only tested in a closed circuit. Open highway tests where not possible to take place due to lack of AD permits in Spain. However, the SAE4 confidence level is high, for speeds up to 80km/h.
- There are in total 4 vehicle available: 3 vehicles (CVs) in Spain, 1 vehicle (CAV) in France.
- CVs and CAV fully equipped with OBUs and HMIs (tablets/laptops), and connected to internet and C-V2X: All 4 sets were tested on the respective vehicles.

Functional tests

- CV: HMI-OBU interface harmonisation was completed successfully.
- CAV: Automated Manoeuvres Testing as Response to PDI Instructions took place in the UTAC closed circuit near Paris, and the results were successful. (see " Update of situation in UC3" mentioned above).

Non-functional tests

- P_UC3-CAV_005 (CAM generation latency < 100 ms): A dataset of 1000 CAM messages were collected and their generation latency measured. The resulting statistical characterisation is: mean 49.19 ms, standard deviation 18.54 ms, min 35 ms, max 106 ms, 95% confidence interval for the mean [48.04 ms; 50.34 ms], and 95th percentile 86 ms. Based on these results, the measured behaviour is compliant with the specified latency requirement (< 100 ms).
- P_UC3-CAV_006: CVs are expected to meet the internal message-handling capacity (>10 messages/sec): We assessed the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) in a scenario featuring one OBU transmitting and one OBU receiving in the lab. Given their close proximity, there is negligible loss attributed to propagation factors. For this test, the channel has been configured with a resource grid of 5x10RB, and employing Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) values 5, 7 and 11. With MCS5, when transmitting 500 messages/sec, with message length of 200 bytes, the PDR was 100%, changing the message length to 500 bytes, the PDR was 80%. With MCS7, when transmitting 500 messages/sec, with message length of 200 bytes, the PDR was 100%, changing the message length to 500 bytes, the PDR was 93%. Finally, with MCS11, when transmitting 500 messages/sec, with message length of 200 bytes, the PDR was 100%, changing the message length to 500 bytes, the PDR was 100%. Based on these results, the measured behaviour is compliant with the requirement.
- P_UC3-NET_002: Original requirements for real-time video streaming (latency <100 ms, 1 Mbps throughput) were modified. Since video analytics are now handled at roadside Personal Computers (PCs), only processed data are transmitted to the MEC, significantly reducing bandwidth needs to less than 10 kbps. This requirement is now obsolete.
- P_UC3-NET_004: Tele-supervision performance (latency, throughput, and reliability): As the shuttle will no longer operate within the set up PDI (5G networks) in Spain, but only operates in France, through commercial 5G networks, this KPI is now obsolete. The telesupervision service works correctly for all MILLA CAVs. No further measurements are required.

4.3. Demonstration activities and data collection

UC validation has undergone multiple phases, including pre-tests (documented in deliverable D4.2 [5]), definitive tests to obtain the KPIs, and the final demonstration. The layout and the configuration of the different elements of the testbed are detailed in D4.2 [5].

The pre-tests focused on the verification and validation of individual components and subsystems. These activities included the use of simulation environments and controlled tests to ensure that each module operated correctly and that all interfaces were properly integrated within the overall system architecture. The main objective of the pre-tests was to identify and resolve integration issues, verify message exchanges, and confirm the correct functioning of the communication and processing chains.

In contrast, the final tests were conducted with the fully integrated system operating in real conditions. These tests aimed to validate the complete end-to-end performance of the platform, with all components (vehicles, communication infrastructure, MECs, and cloud services) working together. During the final tests, particular emphasis was placed on data collection and log recording to compute the KPIs defined in the project and prepare the final demonstration.

The definitive tests for obtaining the KPIs were carried out between 02.10.2025 and 20.11.2025. The final demonstration of UC3 took place on 20.11.2025 and consisted of two parts. First, a live demonstration was conducted on the highway with the connected vehicles, followed by a presentation of the installations and operational systems at the Autopistas Road Operation and Safety Centre. In addition, a separate demonstration of the CAV-related functionalities was performed at the UTAC test circuit in Paris.

Trip with Three Connected Vehicles (CVs) in the C-32 Testbed

The demonstration began with three CVs (Figure 57) operating in the C-32 testbed. One Autopista's service vehicle departed first and stopped on the highway shoulder to simulate an incident. The remaining two CVs, carrying PoDIUM project participants, followed and drove through the complete testbed circuit (Figure 58).

Figure 57: Connected vehicles on the day of the final demonstration.

Figure 58: Route followed by the vehicles during the final demonstration between the South Endpoint and the North Endpoint.

During this phase, the vehicles demonstrated the following functionalities:

1. Display of neighbouring vehicles through the CV HMI (Figure 59): Passengers in the two CVs could visualise nearby vehicles in real time via the HMI. Detection was achieved through:

- C-V2X V2V communication, used when the vehicles were within close range, receiving CAM messages directly.
- 5G network and RSU-assisted V2I2V communication, where CAM messages reached the MEC and were redistributed by the Awareness Distributor module.
- In case of duplicated information (e.g., direct V2V and MEC-forwarded), the HMI displayed the message received first and discarded the subsequent one.

Figure 59: Connected Vehicle HMI displaying neighbouring vehicles in the vicinity.

2. Visualisation of Traffic Management Strategies during the simulated Incident: The LDM HMI showed all triggered alerts and vehicles present in the area (Figure 60). Upon approaching the area with the stopped service vehicle, the CVs HMI received and displayed the traffic management strategies generated by the TMC.

These strategies were disseminated via DENM and IVIM messages over the 5G network and/or RSUs.

Figure 60: Connected Vehicle HMI showing driver alerts and warnings.

Figure 61: Connected Vehicle HMI showing driver alerts and warnings.

3. Seamless roaming between 5G mobile network operators simulating the cross-border situation: Both CVs experienced a seamless transition during roaming between the two mobile network operators.

- The roaming time was approximately 48 seconds.
- This seamlessness was enabled by the RSU deployment and the multiconnectivity management software, which handled concurrent connectivity with C-V2X (via RSUs) and 5G networks.

4. Integration of Virtual Vehicles through a Simulation Environment: The demonstration included the execution of multiple virtual vehicles within the same C-32 testbed scenario:

- Several virtual machines ran instances of the full ITS protocol stack and continuously transmitted CAM messages to the MECs, which stored them in their LDMs.
- Vehicle positions were generated using a SUMO-based simulation matching the C-32 layout.
- These virtual CVs were visible through the LDM HMI, displayed on tablets inside the CVs (Figure 62).

Figure 62: LDM HMI displaying multiple vehicles introduced through simulation.

Visit to the C32 Road Operation and Safety Centre (AAE-AUCAT) and Future Road Lab (Figure 63 and Figure 64)

Figure 63: Visit to the C32 Road Operation and Safety Centre (AAE-AUCAT).

Figure 64: Presentation of the Autopistas Future Road Lab.

Connected Autonomous Vehicle demonstration in UTAC circuit

In addition to the demonstration conducted on 20.11.2025 in the C-32 testbed, a complementary demonstration of the shuttle CAV (Figure 65) took place at the UTAC-Linas Montlhéry closed circuit in Paris (Figure 66). The demonstration has been executed during two phases:

- Pre demonstration phase was conducted from 27.10.2025 to 31.10.2025,
- Demonstration phase was conducted from 04.11.2025 to 7.11.2025.
 - 6.10.2025 for "Max speed limit" scenario and "Emergency stop" scenario,
 - 7.10.2025 for "On-demand service" scenario.

The KPIs have been saved mainly during the demonstration phase.

For UC3, the following traffic strategies (cooperative manoeuvres) have been conducted during the demonstration:

- "Max speed limit" scenario: To slow down autonomously the shuttle speed to 50 km/h or 30 km (+/- 10%) after reception of C-V2X message by the shuttle,
- "Emergency stop" scenario: To inform the C-V2X Infrastructure that the Shuttle is in emergency,
- "On-demand service" scenario: To experiment an autonomous and connected transport service with front-end, back-end, transport operations.

Figure 65: Milla's shuttle CAV.

Figure 66: Highway circuit followed by the Milla Shuttle at Utac-Linas Montlhéry closed circuit.

The mission profile of the experimental autonomous and connected transport service is described as follows:

- Route
 - Infrastructure: 99% of Highway, 1% of urban.
 - Total distance: 2.8 km
 - Number of stations: Three stations
 - One STARTING station.
 - One STOP station.
 - One TERMINUS station.

- Location: UTAC-Linas Montlhéry, highway circuit.
- Transport Means
 - Type: Autonomous, connected, electric vehicle "Shuttle", SAE Level 4.
- Transport Service
 - Type: Fixed-schedule transportation service.
 - Safety driver: Safety driver present physically in the shuttle.
 - Passengers: Spanish living lab- members only.
 - Tele supervision centre: MILLA- 320 Rue Fourny, BUC.
 - Day charging station: UTAC-Linas Montlhéry.
 - Night charging station: MILLA- 320 Rue Fourny, BUC.
 - Warehouse station: MILLA- 320 Rue Fourny, BUC.

All the on-demand service system and its execution step-by-step are shown in Figure 69.

<p>Weather conditions were at the limit of the ODD because of the fog presence on the circuit. Despite these conditions, the demonstration was successfully completed.</p>	
<p>Driver IHM and Passenger IHM with shuttle planner activated, during a driving in full AD mode</p>	
<p>Milla shuttle in operation (during demonstration): View from the driver space. The safety driver is physically present and, he does not control the steering wheel. The blue LED indicates that the shuttle is in full AD mode. The green LED indicates that no defect is raised by the autonomous system. The shuttle is ready to operate in full AD mode.</p>	
<p>Milla shuttle in operation (during demonstration): View from the Passenger space. We can observe the presence of the partners during the demonstration. Passenger IHM shows the Shuttle perception.</p>	

Figure 67: Test Day schedule for "On-demand service" scenario during demonstration.

Passenger App for on-demand services:

On 07.11.2025, Enide and Milla carried out a successful demonstration at the UTAC circuit to validate the on-demand services scenario, part of the UC3, evaluating the interaction between the passenger application (ENIDE) and the autonomous MILLA Shuttle, including all the intermediate steps and components.

The primary objective was to demonstrate the full communication chain end-to-end, from the Passenger app, to ENIDE backend/cloud, to MILLA ecosystem and fleet management through the dedicated proxy accessible by Virtual Private Network (VPN), provided by MILLA, and finally MILLA Shuttle

Preliminarily, several remote lab tests were done during the previous months, especially during the week of 27.10.2025 to ensure the communication and information flow among the main components previously described.

During the tests, even under especial weather conditions (heavy fog), the passenger application initiated two separate ride requests, each of which triggered the autonomous shuttle’s movement (in less than 5 seconds). Both rides consisted of laps on the highway circuit, including multiple predefined stops. Throughout these journeys, communication between all components operated smoothly. The passenger app accurately reflected the shuttle’s status, including real-time trip progression through the progress-bar feature. For additional information, check video in the PoDIUM project YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ui2gVB1U8cA>.

The successful completion of the two rides, each involving different segments and stops, demonstrates the robustness and maturity of the UC3 communication architecture and marks an important milestone in the development of the on-demand autonomous mobility service (Figure 68 and Figure 69).

Figure 68: Passenger check-in process. Activation of the shuttle journey after on-demand service requests start.

Figure 69: Passenger app: booking process (left); detail of the parcel management (centre); progress during the journey (right).

During the execution of the UC3 trials, multiple datasets were collected on the logging points shown in Figure 70 and stored in the project repository. Table 71 of the Annex outlines the whole set of logged parameters and the links to access them. This data has been collected in the logging points indicated in Figure 70 and following the guiding lines of D4.2 [4].

Figure 70: Logging points in the UC3's functional diagram according to D4.1 [4].

The dataset used for the computation of the KPIs is structured as follows:

- The logs for KPI_P_1 of UC3 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_P_1-ServiceAvailability: They contain one excel file of all messages interchanged in all MQTT brokers of the MECs of several test days.
- The logs for KPI_P_2 of UC3 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_P_2-UpdateLatency: They contain one excel file with the CAM messages transmitted from vehicles to MECs for one of the trial days, together with the plots presented in the next section.
- The logs for KPI_P_3 of UC3 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_P_3-NotificationLatency. They contain one excel file with the CAM messages transmitted from MECs to vehicles for one of the trial days, together with the plots presented in the next section.
- The logs for KPI_P_4 of UC3 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_P_4-ProcessingDelay. It contains one excel file with the timestamps of the Road Hazard Detection Time (captured in the TMC) and the POST Hazard Edge to Gateway, the time difference of which gives us the KPI measurements of processing time of a hazard within the MEC. Plots are also included in the Excel. The folder also contains the original logs.
- The logs for KPI_P_5 of UC3 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_P_5-ComReliability: They contain one excel file with the transmitted messages and received messages during the drive of several rounds in the testbed.
- The logs for KPI_UC3_1 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_1-ServiceTime. It contains three excel files. One includes a list of DENM incident alerts triggered by a vehicle, along with the measured time between when each DENM message is transmitted from the vehicle and when the corresponding relayed message is received back from the MEC. The other 2 files are related to the ServiceTime for "traffic strategies relay". One file (TMC_data) contains the empirical test measurements, which were eventually discarded. The other file (synthetic2) contains the

synthetic data generated, together with the relevant plots, as discussed in the section further below.

- The logs for KPI_UC3_2 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime: It contains two excel files, one with a list of ping requests/replies to measure the interruption times, and another with the inter-arrival time of consecutive CAM messages received at the MEC from a single vehicle.
- The logs for KPI_UC3_3 are located in the folder UC3_KPI_3-ShuttleSpeed: It contains one csv file with the shuttle "vehicle" data and tele supervision data.
- The logs for KPI_UC3_4 are stored in the UC3_KPI_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation folder. For the CAV, the folder includes a single csv file containing shuttle vehicle data and tele-supervision data for each scenario (max speed limit, emergency stop, and on-demand service). For the two CVs, the folder includes one subfolder per vehicle (IDIADA and AAE-i2cat), each containing multiple CSV and Excel files with the datasets generated across the different implementation stages.

4.4. Trial Results

In this section, we present the results of the Test Cases proposed for UC3 in D5.1 [4]. The results have been obtained through analysis of the previous data sets.

4.4.1. Test Case for KPI_P_1 Service Availability in UC3

Service Availability represents the percentage of time during which the service remains fully operational with respect to the total observation time. It is assessed during field trials carried out on the C-32 highway.

The availability is evaluated per component of the system architecture, including: Gateway (GW), Local Dynamic Map (LDM), TMC, VRU module, and Video Analytics module (VA).

Method of calculation

The system activity is monitored through the continuous recording of logs corresponding to all messages exchanged among the different architectural modules, together with specific monitoring tools for the communication network infrastructure. The system architecture is composed of: vehicle equipment (OBUs), communication infrastructure (5G networks and RSUs), C-ITS message handling (MEC gateways, LDMs), TMC, and VRU risk assessment.

Information exchanges rely on MQTT brokers deployed at the MECs and inside vehicles, or on Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API) interfaces. Every message transmitted through these communication paths is logged to ensure full traceability and to compute the other KPIs. A module is considered operational as long as it continues to publish messages through its corresponding interface.

The total operational time comprises approximately 4 hours of controlled test runs used for KPI computation, plus 2 hours of the final demonstration. The periods devoted exclusively to system integration, debugging or network configuration were not included in the availability calculation, as these activities fall outside the operational observation window defined for the KPI.

Downtime was computed as the cumulative duration of intervals in which any module failed to publish messages for more than five seconds. Following the execution of all KPI-oriented runs and the final demonstration, no downtime was detected in any module. Therefore, the service availability is 100%.

A key justification is that all data collected for the other KPIs and for the final demonstration was acquired without any interruption, proving that all modules remained fully operational at all times. Consequently, there is no need to process additional log data, since the behaviour of the system during the observation window already demonstrates full availability.

Table 23: TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC3.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC3			
Materials used	MEC components: GW, LDM, TMC, VRU. Roadside Cameras with Video Analytics (VA), data received by the MEC. RSUs. MQTT brokers and REST API communications.			
KPI	KPI_P_1 serviceAvailability in UC3			
Descriptive Statistics	Total time	Downtime	Availability	
	6 hours	0 s	100.0%	

Plots

As discussed above, during the entire testing period (KPI data collection and final demonstration), the service availability reached 100%, with no outages observed in any architectural component. As a result, a specific availability plot for the KPI is not required. Nevertheless, some system components were also monitored over longer periods to complement the KPI assessment:

- Figure 71 illustrates the availability of the northern 5G network. A process deployed on one RSU under 5G coverage periodically issued ping requests to an external server every 30 minutes. Periods of unavailability appear as zeros (black bar). No unavailability was recorded during the full week of data collection.

Figure 71: Delay in ms of ping requests from a node connected to the northern 5G network to an external server during the week from 27.10.25 to 31.10.25. Network unavailability would be seen as black bars.

- Figure 72 presents the tool developed for monitoring RSU activity and service availability. During the relevant test runs, all RSUs remained fully operational.
- Figure 73 shows the histogram of inter-arrival times between packets handled by the broker in MEC-ES1 during a 20.57-hour monitoring interval (30–31.11.25). No inter-arrival time exceeded 1200 ms, demonstrating uninterrupted operation throughout the period.
 - Inter-arrival times around 200 ms correspond to active testing phases.
 - Inter-arrival times around 1000 ms reflect idle periods without vehicles in the testbed; during these intervals, the MEC continued to send MAP (topology) Extended Messages (MAPEMs) at one message per second, confirming continuous operation.

Figure 72: Tool developed to monitor the 3 RSUs activity and service availability.

Figure 73: Availability of MEC-ES1. Histogram of packet inter-arrival times between the components of MEC-ES1 during a 20.57-hour observation period.

Conclusions

During the final testing phase, the service achieved 100% availability, with no observed outages in any platform component or architectural module. The verification criterion required a minimum availability of 95%, which was fully met.

The stability and robustness of the complete system ensured the successful evaluation and demonstration of the use case, and the uninterrupted message exchange during all KPI-collection runs and the final demo provides sufficient evidence, without the need for further data processing, that the service operated continuously and reliably.

4.4.2. Test Case for KPI_P_2 Update Latency in UC3

In UC3, the Update Latency is defined as the time elapsed between the transmission of a message by a vehicle and its availability in the MEC. This metric is measured from the moment the message first appears in the MQTT broker of the vehicle until it is received and registered in the MQTT broker of the MEC. The presence of the message in the MEC's broker indicates that it has become available to all MEC-hosted applications.

Method of calculation

Both the messages published in the vehicle's MQTT broker and the corresponding messages received in the MEC's MQTT broker are logged with precise timestamps. The Update Latency is computed as

the difference between these timestamps, i.e., the time elapsed from the moment the message appears in the vehicle broker until its corresponding appearance in the MEC broker.

Table 24: TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC3.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency			
Materials used	Vehicle equipment (OBUs), communication infrastructure (5G networks and RSUs), C-ITS message handling (MEC gateways) and MQTT brokers.			
KPI	KPI_P_2 updateLatency in UC3			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	20892	191.7 ms	49.0 ms	363.5 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	9061.0 ms	8.0 ms	[186.77, 196.63] ms	743 ms

Plots

Figure 74: Histogram of UC3 Update Latency (ms).

Figure 75: CDF of C3 Update Latency (ms).

Figure 74 presents the histogram of the Update Latency, while Figure 75 shows its CDF. Together with the results summarised in the previous table, the analysis indicates that the mean Update Latency is

191.7 ms. Although this value is higher than the ideal target of approximately 100 ms, it remains fully acceptable for the intended application. The dissemination of traffic management strategies is not a stringent real-time service, and therefore the observed latency comfortably satisfies operational needs.

The verification criterion established for this KPI required that the delay remain below 2.5 seconds, a threshold that was fully met across all measurements. Additionally, the 95th percentile latency is 743 ms, which also complies with the defined performance requirements.

In the histogram shown previously, a noticeable peak appears in the [600–800] ms latency range. To understand the origin of these higher delays, we analysed the transmission paths used to deliver CAM messages from the vehicles to the MEC. The system relies on two main communication paths:

- 5G path: CAM messages are generated in the vehicle’s on-board computer, transmitted via Wi-Fi to the vehicle’s 5G router, forwarded through the Uu interface to the Podium operator’s 5G gNB, and finally delivered through the 5G core network to the MEC.
- C-V2X path: CAM messages are generated in the vehicle’s computer and sent over Ethernet to the OBU. From there, they are transmitted via LTE-PC5 to the RSU. The RSUs are equipped with a cellular interface that enables them to reach the Podium MEC through the internet.

By analysing the latency associated with each path, we identified that one RSU (RSU1) was exhibiting degraded performance. Figure 76 compares the delays of consecutive CAM messages transmitted through RSU1 and RSU3. While RSU3 shows delays consistently between 200 ms and 350 ms, messages routed through RSU1 experience delays in the 650 ms to 800 ms range.

This behaviour explains the peak observed in the [600–800] ms latency interval of the histogram. Addressing this issue would require either restoring RSU1 to its factory software configuration or replacing it with a functioning unit.

Figure 76: Update latency (ms) for CAMs transmitted via RSU3 (left) and RSU1 (right). RSU1 exhibits noticeably degraded performance relative to RSU3.

Moreover, the histogram shows a small number of CAM messages experiencing delays of several seconds. A detailed investigation revealed that these large delays occurred when the vehicle reached the far end of the testbed and performed the turning manoeuvre. In these areas, 5G network coverage is weak, resulting in an unstable connection with frequent attach/detach cycles.

The root cause lies in the fact that ITS messages transmitted over 5G use a Transport Control Protocol (TCP)-based transport. While TCP guarantees reliability through retransmissions, it does so at the cost of potentially very long delays when the physical connection is temporarily lost. When a CAM message is generated during a disconnection event, TCP repeatedly retransmits the message until the

connection is restored. Even if the delay becomes several seconds long, TCP will still deliver the message, as its primary design goal is reliability rather than timeliness.

Figure 77 supports this explanation: throughout most of the trip along the highway, the Update Latency remains stable, but as soon as the vehicle enters either of the end zones with poor coverage, the latency increases sharply and exhibits high variance.

Mitigating this issue would require either improving network coverage in those areas or switching from TCP to User Datagram Protocol (UDP). UDP does not retransmit lost packets, so messages generated during periods of disconnection would be dropped rather than delayed. For CAM messages, this behaviour is actually preferable: the information is generated continuously, and receiving a CAM that is several seconds old provides no operational value. However, using UDP in this context is challenging because UDP is not Network Address Translator (NAT)-friendly, and mobile operators typically rely on NAT mechanisms as they provide private Internet Protocol (IP) addresses. This makes UDP transmission over cellular networks more complex.

Figure 77: Update Latency (ms) at the MEC for CAMs generated by a vehicle that traverses the corridor, reaches its northern endpoint, and subsequently re-enters the highway.

Conclusions

The results obtained for the update latency KPI show that the system performs well within the requirements of the use case. The average latency of 191.7 ms, although higher than the ideal target of around 100 ms, remains fully acceptable for a non-real-time traffic management application. Furthermore, all measurements stayed below the verification threshold of 2.5 seconds, and the 95th percentile latency of 743 ms also falls comfortably within the defined limits. These findings confirm that end-to-end message propagation from the vehicle to the MEC operates within the expected bounds and provides sufficient responsiveness for operational use.

The histogram analysis reveals a clear peak in the 600–800 ms range, traced back to degraded performance in one RSU (RSU1), whose delays were consistently much higher than those observed for RSU3. Restoring this RSU to its factory configuration or replacing it would eliminate this systematic source of latency. A small number of messages exhibited delays of several seconds, occurring exclusively in areas with poor 5G coverage. In these zones, frequent attach/detach cycles triggered TCP retransmissions, inherently generating long delays despite eventually guaranteeing delivery. This behaviour highlights the trade-off between timeliness and reliability in TCP-based Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) message transmission. While switching to UDP would reduce such excessive delays by discarding outdated messages, its deployment is constrained by NAT-related limitations in mobile networks.

In summary, the system meets the KPI targets and behaves robustly under normal conditions. Regarding scalability, the key requirement is the ability to deploy a sufficient number of RSUs to mitigate gaps in 5G coverage. In a cross-border scenario such as this one, characterised by relatively

long roaming periods, the system has shown good scalability, as only three RSUs were needed to support a roaming time of approximately 40–50 seconds. The results also indicate that the architecture remains reactive except in known coverage blind spots, and it provides high reliability thanks to the use of TCP, though this comes at the cost of increased latency during connectivity disruptions.

4.4.3. Test Case for KPI_P_3 Notification Latency in UC3

In UC3, the Notification Latency is defined as the time elapsed between the transmission of a message by the MEC and its availability in the vehicle. This metric is measured from the moment the message first appears in the MQTT broker of the MEC until it is received and registered in the MQTT broker of the vehicle. The presence of the message in the vehicles' broker indicates that it has become available to all vehicle-hosted applications.

Method of calculation

All messages appearing in the MQTT broker of the MEC (MCM, Collective Perception Message (CPM), DENM, Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message (IVIM)), ready to be transmitted in the downlink, and those received by the MQTT brokers of the vehicle are logged together with their respective timestamps. The Notification Latency is then computed as the time difference between the two occurrences, i.e., the time elapsed from the message's appearance in the MEC broker until its corresponding appearance in the vehicle's broker.

Table 25: TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC3.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency			
Materials used	Vehicle equipment (OBUs), communication infrastructure (5G networks and RSUs), C-ITS message handling (MEC gateways) and MQTT brokers.			
KPI	KPI_P_3 notificationLatency in UC3			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	8510	178.18 ms	74.00 ms	366.22 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	4571 ms	12 ms	[170.40, 185.97] ms	823.55 ms

Plots

Figure 78 presents the histogram of the Notification Latency, while Figure 79 shows its CDF. Together with the results summarised in the previous table, the analysis indicates that the mean Notification Latency is 178.18 ms. Although this value is higher than the ideal target of approximately 100 ms, it remains fully acceptable for the intended application.

Figure 78: Histogram of UC3 Notification Latency (ms).

Figure 79: CDF of UC3 Notification Latency (ms).

Conclusions

The results for the update latency KPI show that the system performs well within the requirements of the use case. The average latency of 178.18 ms is acceptable for non-real-time traffic-management functions, and all measurements remained below the 2.5-second verification threshold. The 95th-percentile value of 823.55 ms also lies comfortably within the defined limits, confirming that end-to-end message propagation from the vehicle to the MEC behaves as expected.

The conclusions are essentially the same as for the previous KPI on update latency: the service does not require strict real-time behaviour, and the measured delays fully meet operational needs. The system proves robust under normal conditions and scalable in the cross-border scenario, where only three RSUs were needed to bridge a roaming period of around 40–50 seconds. Reliability remains high, with temporary increases in latency only observed during known coverage gaps.

4.4.4. Test Case for KPI_P_4 Processing Delay in UC3

Processing delay is the processing time required between hazard detection and the CCAM message availability for CAV/CV to action, without accounting for transport delay. This is measured in the MEC.

Method of calculation

How to observe/measure/monitor:

- Timestamps during processing in services that are necessary:
 - Start point: the timestamp when the triggering event (hazard) was received by MEC/Cloud service.
 - End point: the timestamp of the alert indication (DENM) generated in the Gateway.
- The time does not count message latency outside the MEC.
- A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance over all the measurements represents the KPI value.

Test procedure sequence:

- The input and output of the MEC was logged in simulated test, launching a hazard on the road (within the TMC) and measuring the time until strategies were made available in the V2X Gateway.
 - TMC Input: Obstacle detected / manual hazard.
 - TMC Output: DENM json (alert) generated.

- Both log entries should be identified and then their timestamps are used to calculate the time deltas for every notification produced.

Target Value: Processing Delay < [50ms, 2.5s]. The target values depend on the particular UC, since more responsive times are required for certain situations such as manoeuvre coordination and less responsive for traffic management.

Table 26: TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC3.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay			
Materials used	The entire MEC.			
KPI	KPI_P_4 processingDelay in UC3			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	24	39 ms	41 ms	6.21 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	45 ms	20 ms	[36.5, 41.5] ms	44.75 ms

Plots

Figure 80: Histogram of UC3 Processing Delay (ms).

Figure 81: CDF of UC3 Processing Delay (ms).

Conclusions

The results for the processing-delay KPI show that the MEC-side reaction time performs well within the requirements defined for UC3. For UC3 (Traffic management) the target was set to < 2,5s. With an average processing delay of 39 ms and a 95th-percentile value of 44.75 ms, all measured values lie comfortably inside the acceptable target range, and even achieving the more restrictive target of < 50 ms, demonstrating that the internal MEC processing pipeline operates efficiently under real test conditions. The narrow dispersion (standard deviation of 6.2 ms) further confirms stable behaviour, with no anomalous peaks and a maximum recorded delay of just 45 ms. Since this KPI isolates processing time from network transport effects, the results indicate that the MEC's internal logic, from hazard detection to DENM generation, performs reliably and with sufficient responsiveness for cooperative hazard-notification scenarios. Overall, the system meets UC3 operational requirements with considerable margin, validating that the MEC-based processing chain is robust, deterministic, and suitable for deployment in real highway environments.

4.4.5. Test Case for KPI_P_5 Com Reliability in UC3

In UC3, the Communication Reliability KPI is derived from measurements of the platform's ability to relay messages between the vehicles and the MEC, in both transmission directions. The metric is computed as the fraction of successfully delivered messages over the total number of transmitted messages, providing an estimation of the overall reliability of the communication process.

Method of calculation

All messages appearing in the MQTT broker of the MEC and those received by the MQTT broker of the vehicle are logged together with their respective timestamps. The Communication Reliability is then computed as the ratio between the number of messages successfully received and the number of messages transmitted in each communication direction, providing a quantitative measure of the reliability of the message exchange between the vehicle and the MEC.

Table 27: TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC3.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability			
Materials used	Vehicle equipment (OBUs), communication infrastructure (5G networks and RSUs), C-ITS message handling (MEC gateways) and MQTT brokers.			
KPI	KPI_P_5 comReliability in UC3			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	TX Messages	Rx Messages	Packet Delivery Ratio
	7016	7016	6402	91,25%

Conclusions

A total of 7016 samples were logged during the tests associated with this KPI. As shown in the dataset, 6402 out of 7016 transmitted messages were successfully received, resulting in a Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) of 91.25%. The validation criterion for this KPI establishes a target reliability range of > 90% up to 99.99%, depending on the criticality level of the specific operational context. With a measured PDR of 91.25%, the system clearly meets the required performance threshold. Although the result lies in the lower end of the admissible range, the impact is limited due to the characteristics of the data flow and the operational scenario.

In particular, the application relies on periodic messages, meaning that any single packet loss is quickly compensated by subsequent transmissions carrying updated information. This significantly mitigates the impact of occasional losses on the global system behaviour. Moreover, highway traffic management strategies do not impose stringent latency constraints, which makes the system tolerant to minor variations in message delivery performance.

The test area comprises a highway section covered by two cellular networks, with a short central area where roaming between operators occurs. This transition zone is complemented by three RSUs, ensuring continuity of communication. The solution shows strong scalability potential, since additional RSUs would only be needed in specific locations where cellular coverage is limited or absent. This targeted deployment approach allows the system to adapt efficiently to different highway layouts and network conditions without compromising communication performance.

4.4.6. Test Case for KPI_UC3_1 ServiceTime

The Service Time is defined as the interval between the detection of an incident, or any other trigger event requiring an update of the traffic strategy or alert, and the moment when the corresponding incident notification or new traffic instructions ("manoeuvres") are received by the CVs. This interval represents the end-to-end latency of the service chain, covering all stages involved in updating the traffic strategy, including detection, processing, decision-making, and dissemination.

This KPI has been evaluated in two situations: first, when the incident is detected onboard the vehicle and the corresponding alert (DENM) is relayed using a Vehicle-to-Infrastructure-to-Vehicle (V2I2V) approach; and second, when the incident is detected at the MEC, which computes the traffic strategy and disseminates it using an Infrastructure-to-Vehicle (I2V) approach.

1- KPI calculation for incident alert relay (V2I2V)

This total time includes the following successive steps:

- Traffic state perception update time: Time elapsed from the moment an incident occurs until the MEC becomes aware of it (a vehicle detects the incident and sends a DENM to the MEC).
- Traffic strategy decision time: Time required to compute and update the global traffic strategy at the Global TMC. If the MEC receives a DENM from a vehicle, it simply forwards this DENM to **alert** the rest of the vehicles.
- Notification relay: Once the MEC has the message ready, this is the time required to forward it from the MEC to the vehicles and ensure it becomes available in each vehicle's MQTT broker in the OBU and onboard PC.

Method of calculation

All messages exchanged throughout the process (from the trigger event detection to the delivery of notifications or updated traffic strategies to the vehicles) are logged with their corresponding timestamps at the relevant system components (e.g., vehicle's MQTT broker, MEC's MQTT broker, and TMC).

The measurement comprises the following phases:

- Incident notification via a DENM generated in the vehicle: Measured through the timestamps in the message logs of the vehicles (OBUs) and MECs.
- Alert forwarding: Measured in the MECs brokers through the timestamps of the incoming DENM and outgoing DENM.
- Notification relay: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the MECs and vehicles (OBUs).

The Service Time is calculated as the difference between the timestamps:

- Starting time: The transmission of the DENM from the vehicle (timestamp in vehicle OBU).
- End time: Reception in the vehicles of the relayed DENM (timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs).

Target < 2 seconds total end-to-end time.

Table 28: TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime for incident alert relay (V2I2V).

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime			
Materials used	Vehicle equipment (OBUs), communication infrastructure (5G networks and RSUs), C-ITS message handling (MEC gateways), LDMS and MQTT brokers.			
KPI	KPI_UC3_1 ServiceTime			
V2I2V incident alert relay	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	101	288.83 ms	122.00 ms	509.35 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	3197 ms	27 ms	[188.28, 389.38] ms	1488 ms

Plots: Service Time for incident alert relay (V2I2V)

Figure 82 shows the histogram and Figure 83 the CDF of the service time measured for V2I2V incident alert relaying, i.e., the time elapsed between the transmission of a DENM alert by the vehicle and the reception of the corresponding relayed message from the MEC. This KPI evaluates the system's ability to process and return safety-critical information within the latency bounds expected for cooperative hazard notification. The verification criterion requires that the service time remains below 2 seconds, which is the target performance range for this KPI.

Across the 101 recorded samples, the measured service times show a favourable distribution. The mean value is 288.23 ms, which is well below the 2-second threshold, indicating that under normal conditions the system consistently provides fast end-to-end processing. The 95th percentile is 1488 ms, also comfortably within the requirement, demonstrating that even under less favourable network or processing conditions the relaying mechanism achieves compliant performance.

A small number of larger delays observed in the tail of the distribution are attributed to occasional abrupt connectivity disruptions, which can temporarily affect the transmission of the alert message. These events are uncommon but may occur when the vehicle momentarily loses cellular coverage. Despite these outliers, all values remain under the 2-second target, confirming that the KPI is fully met.

Figure 82: Histogram of UC3 service time for incident alert relay (V2I2V) (ms).

Figure 83: CDF of UC3 service time for incident alert relay (V2I2V) (ms).

Conclusions

The results for the incident alert relay (V2I2V) time show that the platform meets the verification criteria defined in Annex 2. The average relay time is 288.23 ms, and the 95th percentile reaches 1488 ms, both comfortably within the 2-second target. This indicates that the system is reactive enough to deliver incident notifications to connected vehicles within the required timeframe for the considered highway-management use cases.

The measurements also show stable performance, pointing to a reliable V2I2V communication process even when network conditions vary. In addition, the architecture based on MEC processing and the combined use of 5G and C-V2X can scale to higher numbers of messages or vehicles, since the workflow remains lightweight and does not rely on ultra-low-latency constraints.

Overall, the KPI results confirm that the platform can detect incidents and relay alerts to vehicles within the expected delay, meeting the operational needs of the scenario.

2- KPI calculation for strategy relay (I2V)

This total time includes the following successive steps:

- Traffic state perception update time: Time elapsed from the moment an incident occurs until the MEC becomes aware of it. The MEC identifies the incident based on CAM data received from vehicles (stopped vehicle at 0km/h).
- Traffic strategy decision time: Time required to compute and update the global traffic strategy at the Global TMC. The TMC analyses the situation, defines a "hazard", and decides to trigger a specific traffic management strategy (speed reduction, lane blocked advice, etc.).
- Notification relay: Once the MEC has the message ready, this is the time required to forward it from the MEC to the vehicles and ensure it becomes available in each vehicle’s MQTT broker in the OBU and onboard PC.

Method of calculation

All messages exchanged throughout the process are logged with their corresponding timestamps at the relevant system components (e.g., vehicle's MQTT broker, MEC's MQTT broker, and TMC).

The Service Time is calculated as the difference between the timestamp of the trigger event (the detection of a hazard by the TMC) and the timestamp when the corresponding strategy is received by the vehicles.

The measurement comprises the following phases:

- Traffic state perception and update time: Measured via timestamps for each updated "traffic state" within the TMC.
- Traffic strategy decision time: Measured via timestamps of the Traffic Strategies calculated, stored and emitted by the TMC.
- Notification relay: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the MECs and vehicles (OBUs).

The Service Time is calculated as the difference between the timestamps:

- Starting time: The transmission of the CAM from the vehicle (timestamp in vehicle OBU).
- End times: Strategy relay (vehicles receive the new strategy): Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs).

Target < 6 seconds total end-to-end time.

Since it was not possible calculate consistent values in real-life field tests, we devised a synthetic KPI measurement consisting of the sum of 3 data samples:

Total E2E Service time = Update Latency from CVs to MEC (subsample of KPI_P_2 measured data) + Processing delay within MEC (synthetic values generated based on KPI_P_4 measured data) + Notification Latency from MEC to CV (subsample of KPI_P_3 data)

Table 29: TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime for a Strategy relay (I2V).

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime			
Materials used	The entire MEC, communication infrastructure (5G networks and RSUs), and the connected vehicles (OBUs)			
KPI	KPI_UC3_1 ServiceTime			
Strategy relay	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	8000	584 ms	384 ms	538 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	4908 ms	77 ms	[573 ms, 596 ms]	1631 ms

Plots: Service Time for strategy relay (I2V)

Figure 84 presents a histogram of the UC3 service time for strategy relay, showing how frequently different delay ranges occurred during the tests. Most measurements fall within the 0–400 ms range, with additional notable concentrations around 800–1,000 ms, while occurrences above 1,200 ms become progressively rarer. This distribution indicates that the majority of relayed strategies were processed within sub-second timescales, with only a small tail of higher delays.

Figure 85 shows the corresponding CDF. The curve rises steeply up to around 800 ms, where nearly 90% of all samples are already included, and then gradually approaches 100% as it reaches the maximum observed values above 3,000 ms. This confirms that the system delivers strategy relays quickly in most cases, with only a limited set of outliers contributing to longer delays.

Figure 84: Histogram of UC3 service time for strategy relay (I2V) (ms).

Figure 85: CDF of UC3 service time for strategy relay (I2V) (ms).

Conclusions

The evaluation of the strategy-relay (I2V) service time shows that the system performs well within the expected operational bounds for UC3. With a median delay of 384 ms and a mean of 584 ms, the majority of strategy updates reach the connected vehicles in well under one second, and the 95th percentile of 1,631 ms remains comfortably below the 6-second threshold defined for the use case. The histogram and CDF confirm this distribution: most samples are concentrated between 0 and 1,000 ms, with only a long but sparsely populated tail extending to the maximum observed value of 4.9 seconds, still inside the allowed limit. These results satisfy the success criterion that at least 80% of all strategy relays must remain below 6 seconds, indicating a PASS for the KPI. From a scalability perspective, the relatively tight clustering of delays below one second suggests that the system maintains stable performance under the tested load, while the consistency of delivery times demonstrates robust end-to-end reactivity and reliability across MEC processing, TMC logic, and vehicle communications.

4.4.7. Test Case for KPI_UC3_2 CrossBorderInterruptionTime

One of the defining characteristics of the Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) domain is that vehicles can connect using two main types of communication technologies. The first is short-range communication, based on IEEE 802.11p (now somewhat outdated) or on C-V2X, which is currently the

most widely adopted. The second option relies on general-purpose cellular networks, which were not originally designed for V2X communication but provide much broader coverage.

In our use case, we designed a scenario where the primary communication network for vehicles is the latest generation of cellular technology, 5G. However, even such advanced networks are subject to temporary disconnection periods. These may occur due to local coverage limitations or due to the time required for the network to process a roaming transition, as happens in cross-border scenarios.

To reproduce this behaviour, we simulated a cross-border environment in which all vehicles were required to roam from one mobile network operator to another. The aim of the use case was to design an alternative communication path, based on C-V2X, capable of bridging these temporary connectivity gaps. The goal was not to reduce the roaming outage duration itself, but to ensure that the system remained fully operational and reliable throughout these interruptions thanks to the complementary C-V2X infrastructure.

Method of calculation

The interruption time is defined as the period during which a vehicle is unable to access the Internet due to the absence of 5G network service. To measure this parameter, we developed a script that continuously sends ping requests to an external Internet server throughout the entire test, corresponding to one full lap of the circuit. All ping responses were logged and subsequently analysed to identify and quantify the time intervals during which no connection was available.

A sample is defined as a single inter-operator roaming event. Within one complete lap of the test circuit, two such roaming events occur, one while travelling southbound and another while travelling northbound. These transitions generate the primary service interruption periods observed in the tests.

In addition to these major events, several shorter interruptions, referred to as micro-gaps, may occur. These micro-gaps can result from intra-operator mobility processes, such as inter-gNB handovers, sector changes within the same base station, or localised coverage holes unrelated to the roaming boundary. Since the objective of this KPI is to quantify roaming-related service loss, micro-gaps were not included in the calculation.

Table 30: TC_KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime			
Materials used	The computers of the vehicles accessing the cellular networks through the 5G routers. The two 5G networks. One computer in Internet as a target for the "ping" command.			
KPI	KPI_UC3_2 CrossBorderInterruptionTime			
Cross-Border Interruption time due to the roaming process	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	28	52.78 s	48.06 s	22.68 s
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	168.23 s	48.05 s	[43.99, 61.58] s	54.08 s
Inter-arrival time of consecutive CAM messages	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	8529	223.74 ms	200.00 ms	359.43 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	21632 ms	0 ms	[216.11, 231.37] ms	422.00 ms

Plots

Figure 86 presents the histogram of the cross-border interruption time due to the roaming process between both 5G network operators, while Figure 87 shows its CDF. Together with the results

summarised in the previous table, the analysis indicates that the mean cross-border interruption time is slightly below 53 seconds, with observed values ranging from a minimum of 48 seconds to a maximum of 168 seconds. Apart from this single occurrence of a 168-second interruption, all remaining roaming events between the two cellular operators were managed smoothly, thanks to the presence of the three RSUs deployed in the area where the roaming transitions take place.

Figure 86: Histogram of UC3 Cross-Border Interruption time (seconds).

Figure 87: CDF of UC3 Cross-Border Interruption time (seconds).

Figure 88 shows the histogram and Figure 89 the CDF of the inter-arrival time of consecutive CAM messages received at the MECs from a single vehicle. These plots are used to assess whether the parallelization of 5G and C-V2X ensures seamless connectivity. The verification criterion for cross-border interruption time requires that inter-arrival gaps remain below 500 ms during the roaming period. This requirement reflects the expected system behaviour in which a vehicle, upon losing connectivity with its primary operator, temporarily relies on C-V2X RSUs to continue transmitting messages until cellular coverage is re-established.

The measured statistics indicate a stable and reliable performance within the cross-border section. The mean inter-arrival time is 223.74 ms, and the 95th percentile is 359.43 ms, both well below the 500 ms limit, thus fulfilling the KPI requirement. These values confirm that, under normal roaming conditions, the system maintains continuous CAM message delivery with no significant disruptions.

Two edge cases also appear in the dataset. A maximum inter-arrival time of approximately 21 seconds is observed, which results from an abrupt modem disconnection occurring outside the RSU coverage area, an occasional situation that does not reflect the expected behaviour within the cross-border zone. Conversely, the minimum inter-arrival time is 0 ms. This occurs immediately after a physical reconnection event, when all CAM messages accumulated in the TCP buffer are released consecutively, producing back-to-back arrivals with no temporal separation.

Figure 88: Histogram of the inter-arrival time (ms) of consecutive CAM messages received at the MEC from a single vehicle.

Figure 89: CDF of UC3 inter-arrival time of consecutive CAM messages received at the MEC from a single vehicle (ms).

Conclusions

The cross-border interruption time refers to a specific test condition aimed at verifying that the system remains reliable even when 5G communication is temporarily interrupted. Within this context, we implemented and validated an alternative network of RSUs to cope with such disconnections.

Across multiple test campaigns, the measured roaming interruption time between the two operators remained consistently around 48 seconds, with a single outlier reaching 168 seconds. This longer delay is primarily attributable to the fact that the core networks of both operators rely on an open-source implementation of Open5GS, which currently exhibits relatively long attachment times during roaming

procedures. Since reducing the roaming duration was not an objective of the project, this limitation is considered acceptable within the project’s scope.

The initial pass criteria required roaming times of <30 seconds when transitioning from abroad to the home country and <90 seconds in the reverse direction. In our final deployment, both networks operated as private 5G systems, meaning that no "home" or "abroad" distinction existed. Therefore, an average threshold of <60 seconds can be applied. With a measured average slightly below 53 seconds, the deployment complies with this requirement.

To mitigate the impact of these temporary interruptions, the adopted strategy was to deploy C-V2X RSUs in the areas where roaming-related outages are known to occur. This solution is inherently scalable, as these zones are relatively few and well defined, which allows targeted deployments without requiring major infrastructure expansion. Under this configuration, the second verification criterion for the cross-border interruption time, which requires service interruption gaps shorter than 500 ms when considering the combined use of C-V2X and 5G dual connectivity, is also fulfilled as the 95th percentile remains in 422 ms.

Overall, the statistical distribution of inter-arrival times demonstrates that the combined 5G and C-V2X communication setup effectively guarantees continuous ITS messages dissemination during roaming transitions, meeting the interruption-time criterion and ensuring seamless connectivity across the cross-border segment.

4.4.8. Test Case for KPI_UC3_3 ShuttleSpeed

Test if Milla shuttle is able to achieve 80 km/h in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions.

Method of calculation

The success of individual test runs is evaluated during the tests at the UTAC-Linas Montlhéry on highway closed circuit (Paris) via the "max speed limit" scenario.

This test scenario has been executed during two phases: Pre demonstration phase has been done from 27.10.2025 to 31.10.2025 and, demonstration phase was conducted on the 6.10.2025. The KPIs have been saved during the two phases. The measure tolerance is +/-10%.

All the test procedure sequence is described in the section 4.4.9.

Table 31: TC_KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed			
Materials used	Milla CAV including Milla native autonomous system with 5G network communication and Cohda OBU integrated with FlexStack. Communication infrastructure via orange public 5G network and virtual RSUs (JSON files in absence of physical MEC infrastructure) on highway closed circuit at UTAC-Linas Montlhéry.			
KPI	KPI_UC3_3 ShuttleSpeed			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	5	72.28 km/h	72,29 km/h	0.04 km/h
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	72.36 km/h	72.18 km/h	[72.24, 72.32] km/h	72.42 km/h

Plot

Figure 90: Boxplot of the CAV max speed with the traffic strategy "max speed limit" scenario. Value in Km/h.

Conclusions

To guarantee the execution of the tests in safe condition and to ensure the insurance coverage of the autonomous operations, we have limited the shuttle max speed at 72km/h (80km +/-10%) during the demonstration.

The Table 31 shows that during the test runs, each of five test samples, were marked as successful. The verification criterion requires to achieve 80 km/h +/-10% in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions, thus, the KPI UC3_3 ShuttleSpeed for the use case is met.

4.4.9. Test Case for KPI_UC3_4 TrafficStrategiesImplementation

The aim of this is to evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies by:

- The CAV (autonomously).
- The CV drivers (manually).

Once the message is received by the vehicle (via OBU and displayed in the HMI), the CV drivers react based on the indicated strategy (manoeuvre) and the CAV autonomously implements the indicated strategy.

As there are two types of receiving vehicles, this KPI has been evaluated in two situations: first, with the CAV; and second, with the CV.

1- KPI calculation with the CAV

The test procedure sequence has been launched as follows on the closed circuit:

1) Normal situation:

"On-demand" service scenario

- The Milla Shuttle receives a mission from Enide Application.
- The mission received, is validated by tele supervision centre, the safety driver and traffic management centre to ensure operations in safe conditions, in compliance with ODD and legislation.
- The Shuttle initiates at the origin points of the route, in full AD mode.
- The Shuttle accelerates until it reaches a speed of 80 km/h +/-10%, in full AD mode.

"Max speed limit" scenario

- The Milla Shuttle receives a mission from tele supervision centre, the safety driver and traffic management centre to ensure operations in safe conditions, in compliance with ODD and legislation.
- The Shuttle initiates at the origin points of the route, in full AD mode.
- The Shuttle accelerates until it reaches a speed of 80 km/h +/-10%, in full AD mode.

"Emergency stop" scenario

- The Milla Shuttle is running at a speed of 80km/h (+/-10%), in full AD mode.
- 2) Reception of the C-V2X message (due to absence of physical MEC infrastructure, a simulator of traffic strategies that provides the same JSON files as the real system has been used):

"On-demand service" scenario

- No C-V2X message is received by the Shuttle for this scenario.

"Max speed limit" scenario

- The Shuttle receives IVIM with speedLimitMax=50 km/h or 30 km/h.

"Emergency stop" scenario

- No C-V2X message is received by the Shuttle for this scenario.
- 3) React to the Traffic strategy accordingly:

"On-demand service" scenario

- The shuttle operates on the route in fully autonomous mode and:
 - It automatically stops at the stations to be served (Starting station, Stop station, Terminus station).
 - If necessary, the Shuttle reacts autonomously to any event.

"Max speed limit" scenario

- The Shuttle slows down autonomously to a speed of 50 km/h or 30km/h (+/-10%).

"Emergency stop" scenario

- No C-V2X message is received by the Shuttle for this scenario.
 - Due to an induced internal technical failure, the shuttle is forced to make an emergency stop by pulling over onto the emergency lane of the UTAC highway circuit.
 - CAM messages (positioning, localisation) are automatically sent from Shuttle to C-V2X Infrastructure with information for the TMC.
- 4) Return in Normal situation:

"On-demand service" scenario

- When the shuttle stops at the terminal station, the mission received by the shuttle ends.

"Max speed limit" scenario

- The Shuttle continue to circulate at 50km/h or 30km/h (+/-10%) in full AD mode till the next stop station.

"Emergency stop" scenario

- Once the TMC has been informed by CAM messages, the shuttle is available for the application of TMC operational procedures for a return to normal traffic conditions on the Highway.

Method of calculation for the CAV

Data loggers capture the "start and end of manoeuvre".

- Start of manoeuvre: Timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and then displayed in the HMI.
- End of manoeuvre: Timestamp of the Logged speeds of the CAV shuttle as stored in the OBU/PC, when vehicle speed is first-time equal to the new speed limit.

The reaction time KPI measurements are the time elapsed between the timestamps marking the start and end of the manoeuvre.

Targets for the CAV

For CAVs, the first objective is to evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies, that is, to verify whether the CAV successfully executes the cooperative manoeuvres defined in the "on-demand service", "maximum speed limit", and "emergency stop" scenarios. The second objective is to confirm that the CAV's reaction time to the indicated strategy is below 5 seconds.

CAV results

Table 32: Cooperative Manoeuvre-CAV success ratio: Data from the CAV in AD mode for the traffic strategies "on-demand service" scenario, "max speed limit" scenario and "emergency stop" scenario.

TC Identifier	Cooperative-Manoeuvre- CAV (success ratio)			
Materials used	Milla CAV including Milla native autonomous system with 5G network communication and Cohda OBU integrated with FlexStack. Communication infrastructure via orange public 5G network and virtual RSUs (due to absence of physical MEC infrastructure, a simulator of traffic strategies that provides the same JSON files as the real system has been used).			
KPI	Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV Success			
Descriptive Statistics	# tests	# successful manoeuvres	# failed manoeuvres	Success rate
	13	13	0	100%

Table 33: TC_KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation reaction time: Data from the CAV in AD mode for the traffic strategies "max speed limit" scenario.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation (reaction time)			
Materials used	Milla CAV including Milla native autonomous system with 5G network communication and Cohda OBU integrated with FlexStack. Communication infrastructure via orange public 5G network and virtual RSUs (due to absence of physical MEC infrastructure, a simulator of traffic strategies that provides the same JSON files as the real system has been used).			
KPI	KPI_UC3_4 TrafficStrategiesImplementation delay			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	4	4.61 s	4.55 s	0.226 s
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	4.93 s	4.41 s	[4.25, 4.97] s	4.88 s

Plot for the CAV

Figure 91: Boxplot of the CAV reaction time (in milliseconds) for the traffic strategy “max speed limit” scenario.

Conclusions for the CAV

As seen in Table 33 during the test runs, thirteen manoeuvres were marked as successful, resulting in a success rate of 100%. Thus, the Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV for the use case is met.

The closed circuits provide favourable conditions for performing cooperative manoeuvre "max speed limit", minimizing uncontrolled situations and events (Table 36 and Figure 91). The traffic strategy execution time is as expected.

2- KPI calculation with the CV

The referred traffic strategies that are transmitted to the vehicles are "Reduce max speed to new speed limit X km/h", using an IVIM message. What we are considering in this KPI is the required time for the driver to adjust his speed to the new limit in a safe way. Tests were performed in highway C32, in real traffic conditions during the day hours.

The test procedure sequence has been launched as follows:

- CVs are circulating on the highway with the respective drivers, in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).
- The vehicles receive CCAM messages to reduce their speed, as prescribed by the new speed limit announced by the Platform.
 - The vehicles react to the new traffic strategy: The CV drivers read the message on their in-vehicle HMI screens and slow down their vehicles accordingly.
 - In this particular case, the speed changes are from original speed (100 Km/h) to the target speed of 80 Km/h.
- Data loggers capture the "start and end of manoeuvre".
 - Start of manoeuvre: Timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and then displayed in the HMI.
 - End of manoeuvre: Timestamp of the Logged speeds of the CVs as stored in the OBU/PC, when vehicle speed is first-time equal to the new speed limit.
- The KPI measurements are the time elapsed between the timestamps marking the start and end of the manoeuvre.

Method of calculation for the CV

- Capturing the timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and displayed in the HMI.
- Capturing by the logged speeds of the CVs as stored in the TMC/LDM.

Target for the CV

- Delay of CV drivers applying indicated strategy < 10s.

CV results

In this particular case, the speed changes are from original speed (near 100 km/h) to the target speed of 80 km/h, and tests were done using two CVs.

Table 34: TC_KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation: Data from the CVs with human drivers

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation			
Materials used	For the scenarios with CV, two vehicles were involved in the test, being both of them CV. Each one has a laptop running the ITS client connected to infrastructure via 5G (modem) and CV2X (Cohda wireless OBU).			
KPI	KPI_UC3_4 TrafficStrategiesImplementation			
Descriptive Statistics CV number 1	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	12	16.67 s	16.98 s	8.21 s
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	29.97 s	5.04 s	[12.02, 21.32] s	28.18 s
Descriptive Statistics CV number 2	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	8	38.9 s	18 s	45 s
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	129 s	3.2s	[1.29, 76.49] s	107.3 s

For reference, Table 35 shows the analysed data for the 2n CV (i2CAT/AAE).

Table 35: Delay samples for traffic strategies implementations.

Round	Start speed (IVIM received)	End Speed (CAM transmitted)	Delay IVIM-CAM	Delay in seconds
1	88.2	79.9	00:01:07,381	67
2	84.1	80.2	00:00:03,240	3.2
3	94.0	79.9	00:00:04,950	4
4	94.1	79.8	00:00:06,811	6.8
5	101.3	80.0	00:02:09,386	129
6	102.6	79.6	00:01:04,986	65
7	92.4	79.3	00:00:08,956	9
8	96.0	79.9	00:00:27,318	27

The results show significant variability in the time required for drivers to implement the "reduce speed to 80 km/h" strategy after receiving the IVIM message. While the median manoeuvre time is 18 seconds, indicating that in half of the test drivers reacted relatively quickly, the mean of 39 s and the large standard deviation (45 s) reflect a wide dispersion of driver responses under real traffic conditions. Individual samples ranged from 3.2 s, well within the target, to a maximum of 129 s, where surrounding traffic, initial speed, and driver caution likely contributed to slower compliance.

Out of the eight measured rounds for CV2, three tests (rounds 2, 3, and 4) achieved the target of < 10 seconds, while the remaining manoeuvres exceeded the requirement. This is consistent with empirical expectations, which show that driver behaviour introduces substantial human variability, unlike the automated vehicle’s consistent and prompt responses. The results highlight that, while the technical delivery of the traffic management strategies (from identified hazard to the CV’s HMI) is fast and reliable, the actual implementation by human drivers is highly dependent on traffic context, starting speed, and driver interpretation of safety margins. In real-world operation, such variability must be considered when designing cooperative strategies involving manual-driving vehicles.

Plots for the CV

Figure 92: Boxplot of the two CVs reaction time when receiving one IVIM with the traffic strategy to reduce speed. Value in seconds.

Conclusions for the CV

In the C32 testbed, since the tests were conducted on open roads, the time required to implement the prescribed traffic strategies varies significantly depending on traffic conditions and driver attention. Under no traffic or light traffic conditions, manoeuvres can typically be completed in < 10 seconds. However, under moderate traffic or if the driver does not observe the HMI display, manoeuvres may take 30 seconds or even more to be executed safely. This variability reflects the influence of real-world traffic dynamics on driver response times.

Empirical observations during testing revealed that the visual speed-limit alert alone was not always sufficient to immediately draw the driver’s attention, especially in busy highway conditions where visual workload is already high. When an additional auditory cue was used, drivers reacted more promptly, suggesting that a sound alert, or ideally a voice prompt, would significantly improve noticeability and response consistency. It was also noted that accurately identifying the exact timestamps for "start" and "end" of the manoeuvre was challenging, introducing an element of human error in the analysis, particularly when interpreting when the driver first perceived the IVIM message and when the speed stabilised at the target limit.

Importantly, this test was not designed to evaluate compliance likelihood, nor HMI design, which, while satisfactory for an innovation project, would require further refinement before any operational deployment. Instead, the objective was to confirm that connected-vehicle strategies targeted at human drivers are indeed received, understood, and implemented in real traffic conditions, even if response times vary significantly across individuals and contexts. The results validate that the strategy mechanisms function as intended not just with CAVs but also with human drivers, while highlighting areas where driver-interaction design could enhance overall performance.

4.5. Conclusions

In D2.1 [1], we identified the following **potential needs**, which have been successfully addressed during the project's development:

- Rely on Digital Twin Technology to establish a macroscopic global perception of traffic conditions: The UC3 architecture has developed a Digital Twin, which consists of a continuously updated Local Dynamic Map (LDM). This database is continuously refreshed with real-time data gathered from CAM, DENM and CPM messages transmitted by vehicles. Using this comprehensive data, the Traffic Management Centre (TMC) formulates traffic strategies and communicates them to CVs and CAVs.
- Data integration and processing from multiple sources: The current test bed collects data from HD traffic cameras (supported by AI Video Analytics), C-ITS messages from CAV/CVs and the position of VRUs through VAM (VRU Awareness Message) messages. All this information is processed inside the TMC and a VRU module to detect potential collisions with pedestrians.
- Obtaining accurate and real-time traffic information for decision-making: Traffic cameras capture road events in near real-time, while C-ITS messages, which inform about vehicle positions, speed and status, are transmitted every 100ms with delays of less than 100ms. Additionally, a 3rd-party floating car data service is leveraged to provide continuous traffic status throughout the highway, even where no cameras or connected vehicles are present. This information, fused together, ensures enhanced real-time traffic status for effective decision-making.

The use case introduces a scenario where cellular service, the primary radio technology for transmitting C-ITS messages, experiences discontinuity due to roaming between two different operators, simulating a cross-border situation. Typical roaming times between operators range from 60 to 90 seconds. To address this service gap, RSUs equipped with C-V2X technology are deployed in the affected area. All vehicles continuously transmit and receive C-ITS messages using both technologies, C-V2X and cellular (5G/4G).

Additionally, as in some areas there will inevitably be interruption of the communication, the LDM provides an additional module for short time vehicle's trajectory estimation. This feature permits applications consuming data from the LDM to obtain the more precise estimated positions than the last seen position of the vehicle.

Definition of real-time traffic control strategies based on macroscopic perception: The Local TMC module analyses the traffic data mentioned above, and creates a local perception per highway sub-section. If any hazard (e.g. stopped vehicle) or congestion is detected, appropriate traffic strategies are generated by the TMC. If the incident affected more than 1 highway section (each section handled by its own Local TMC, located in a different MEC), then the Global TMC module creates a macroscopic traffic view handles the coordination of traffic strategies across multiple sections.

Additionally, coordination of traffic strategies was implemented across country borders, where different Global TMCs (different road operators) might be active. In such case, when an incident happens across the border that might affect the traffic flow on the other side of the border, relevant incident and strategy data are shared cross border, from one Global TMC to the other.

- Adaptation of local recommendations for different types of vehicles and road users: The traffic strategies are translated to manoeuvre recommendations and sent to the vehicles. These are, in turn, displayed to the drivers (via HMI) of human-driven connected vehicles, as well as directly inserted into the AD computer of automated vehicles. In case of VRUs, if a collision risk is detected, an alert is sent to the VRU's OBU.

- Optimally exchange ETSI C-ITS messages such as CAM, DENM, IVIM, VAM, CPM, and MCM using two radio communication technologies (cellular 5G and C-V2X): Cellular networks are the primary radio technology for transmitting C-ITS messages due to their extensive coverage. However, there is no standardized solution for transmitting C-ITS messages over IP networks. We propose two solutions, each implemented by a different operator in our living lab. On the other hand, cellular networks can experience service gaps, either due to roaming issues, as seen in our test bed, or because of lack of coverage. To address this, we deployed an architecture that uses both cellular networks and C-V2X technology simultaneously. This ensures connectivity in areas with service gaps, provided RSUs are deployed. Additionally, the architecture facilitates interoperability between vehicles using either technology through an awareness distributor, which optimally forwards relevant information to the required vehicles. It also consolidates multiple CAM messages into one or a few CPMs, improving efficiency.

To fulfil these needs, we anticipated several **potential challenges**, as outlined in D2.1 [1], which have been effectively managed:

- **Data Quality and Accuracy:** The accuracy and quality of data from multiple sources, such as high-definition cameras, vehicles, and third-party services: As it has been explained before, the test bed has successfully deployed HD cameras and vehicles that are able to continuously communicate with the infrastructure through two radio technologies. The cameras' Video Analytics functionality was tested multiple times in terms of correctly capturing traffic flows as well as stopped vehicles. The accuracy of the geolocation of these stationary vehicles using this functionality proved to be rather dependent on the placement of the cameras (too low, not in the centre of the lane), making it necessary further development and finetuning to ensure a high-fidelity video analytics. The data quality and accuracy received from CVs (CAMs, DENMs) were deemed very high, providing a very trustworthy source of data, complementing the already integrated 3rd-party floating car data service with the TMC.
- **Scalability and Granularity:** Determining the appropriate deployment and granularity of roadside PDI's based on macroscopic perceptions of traffic from internal and external data may pose challenges in terms of scalability and accuracy of recommendations: From a communication perspective, scalability is achieved through the use of cellular networks as the primary radio technology for vehicle-to-infrastructure communication, offering nowadays near-total coverage on major roads and highways. Deploying C-V2X RSUs in the whole length of would not be feasible. Instead, RSUs are strategically deployed in areas where cellular networks cannot provide service, such as during operator roaming or in small zones lacking radio coverage (or potentially on other "hotspots"). From the point of view of MEC servers needed to be deployed, the granularity has been defined as "1 MEC per section" of the highway. Each MEC has a local TMC, LDM, GW, and other services. Each local TMC coordinated with other sections via a Global TMC. This setup is highly scalable and can be replicated infinitely across all the stretch of the highway, as well as to any other highway. The length of each section can be dimensioned based on the typical traffic flow of connected vehicles (in our C32 testbed, each of the 3 sections was arbitrarily defined at around 3-5km), and based on traffic cameras present on the section (e.g. up to 4 cameras, in our case we only tested with 2 cameras per section). The technical performance of the system should be stress-tested to verify, on the one hand, how many cameras it can handle and, on the other, and much more importantly, whether it can manage hundreds or thousands of CVs, thus adapting the server specs for each MEC.
- **Cross-Border Coordination:** Coordinating and aligning traffic control strategies across the cross-border corridor, may pose challenges in terms of regulatory, technical, and operational aspects: Two challenges were faced: a) 5G service roaming while crossing the border means that C-ITS messages cannot be sent and received for a couple of kms. This was overcome by installing C-V2X RSUs (see also below). b) when a traffic incident / congestion happens beyond the border, vehicles approaching the border (but that have not yet crossed) need to be notified. In a normal

situation each side of the border is handled by a different Operator and therefore a difference TMC system. To resolve this, we have proposed and implemented a simplified data exchange between Operators, using the "Global TMC" modules on each of the MECs. The data exchanged is essentially incident data (e.g. stopped vehicle, congestion, roadworks, etc.) as well as the currently applicable traffic strategies at any given moment in time, so that both Operators' TMCs can automatically harmonise. We propose that such data exchange interfaces are standardised not just for highway operators within the same country but also across EU countries.

- **Service availability:** ensuring "always-on" connectivity between vehicles and PDI, either through 5G or PC5 C-V2X: From a communication perspective, cellular networks are the primary radio technology, offering near-total coverage on major roads and highways. However, for areas with lack of service, we propose deploying C-V2X RSUs. We demonstrated that this dual-radio technology approach effectively addresses traffic management needs. Moreover, when some inevitable communication gap is present, the LDM is able to estimate the position of known objects during a short period of time, approximately 5 seconds.
- **Low latency for safety-relevant situations:** There are no safety-relevant situations in UC3 that require low latency. As shown above, DENM alerts and traffic strategies (e.g. IVIM, MCM messages launched by the TMC) take only take about 1.5 s to be processed and reach the CVs.

Overall, we have successfully achieved the **strategic goals** defined in D2.1 [1]. Below are the conclusions regarding their attainment, based on the results obtained so far

- **Advanced traffic strategies to ensure safe traffic conditions:** UC3 successfully demonstrated that safety-oriented strategies, such as speed reduction, distance increase, lane-avoidance instructions, and hazard alerts (DENM), can be generated and delivered reliably through the MEC platform. These strategies were triggered and propagated within the required time bounds, supporting safer responses to roadside events and detected obstacles.
- **Local recommendations to vehicles to optimize traffic flow:** The system provided timely and context-aware recommendations to connected vehicles, including controlled speed adjustments and distance-keeping instructions, helping stabilise traffic flow during abnormal or potentially risky situations. UC3 showed that such localised cooperative guidance is feasible and can enhance traffic smoothness with or without vehicle automation.
- **Enhancing cross-border cooperation between Spain and France:** UC3 validated a technical architecture capable of supporting continuous CCAM services across borders, with the MEC, RSUs, and communication protocols functioning in a way that can be extended to cross-national operation. While regulatory issues limited full-scale vehicle testing, the technological building blocks for cross-border cooperation were successfully verified.
- **To achieve a collaborative approach to improve traffic conditions across the border:** By enabling the exchange of hazard alerts and strategy updates between infrastructure and vehicles, UC3 demonstrated the capacity for a collaborative, multi-stakeholder traffic management ecosystem. This approach supports shared situational awareness that can be extended to neighbouring countries once administrative barriers are resolved.
- **Make informed decisions on traffic control strategies:** The integration of roadside camera analytics, LDM information, and CAV telemetry enabled to generate precise and timely traffic strategies matched to real-time roadway conditions. This confirms that the system can support informed, data-driven decisions for operational traffic management.
- **Congestion reduction in highways:** The validated strategies, especially speed harmonisation and distance-increase recommendations, show strong potential for reducing congestion linked to sudden slowdowns or unexpected obstacles. UC3 demonstrated that cooperative roadside-to-vehicle guidance can mitigate traffic disturbances and help maintain more stable flow conditions. The impact could be further validated via simulation of multiple-vehicle scenarios, in future projects.

Finally, through the development of this use case, the project has accomplished the following **key technological advancements**.

Communications:

- A complete V2X communication protocol stack was implemented in full compliance with ETSI standards, including GeoNetworking, the Basic Transport Protocol (BTP), security functions, and all C-ITS message types used in the project. This stack was deployed both in the vehicle and in the MEC. Cohda Wireless MK6 OBUs and RSUs were used as C-V2X radio interfaces, but their native protocol stack was bypassed so that our custom implementation could be executed end-to-end. This allowed full control of the communication pipeline and ensured standard-compliant message handling across the entire V2X chain.
- Two alternative mechanisms were designed and implemented for transmitting C-ITS messages, with GeoNetworking and BTP headers, over IP networks and, specifically, over 5G. The first solution uses MQTT, where vehicles subscribe to a broker and may switch to another when entering a new region, requiring some logic on the vehicle side. The second solution relies on a TCP socket, with each vehicle managed directly by the MEC. This approach increases the MEC load but keeps the vehicle simpler and allows message content to be tailored per vehicle. Both solutions were validated in the trials.
- A gateway was developed to combine and coordinate the transmission of C-ITS messages over both C-V2X and 5G networks. It enables parallel or fallback delivery depending on network availability, ensuring continuous message dissemination to vehicles. The gateway handles protocol translation, message formatting, and filtering of messages across both interfaces. This dual-path approach increases robustness and allows seamless operation during coverage gaps or roaming situations.
- An ETSI ITS-compliant simulator was developed, in which each vehicle is instantiated as an independent virtual machine running the open-source FlexStack protocol implementation [10]. This architecture allows every virtual vehicle to transmit and receive real ITS messages, enabling highly realistic communication behaviour within controlled environments. The simulator integrates SUMO to dynamically retrieve the position of each vehicle, ensuring accurate mobility modelling and message generation. Its ability to run full protocol stacks per vehicle makes it suitable for use in testbeds supporting hardware-in-the-loop or broader X-in-the-Loop (XiL) methodologies. This approach provides a powerful tool for evaluating C-ITS components and services under reproducible conditions.

ITS applications:

- A Local Dynamic Map (LDM) was implemented to store relevant road and traffic data and to generate short-term predictions of nearby vehicle positions during network interruptions. This ensures that essential situational information remains available even when updates temporarily stop. The LDM follows the ETSI standard data model for interoperability. A full-featured version runs on the MEC, supporting richer data and processing, while a lightweight version is deployed in the vehicle to maintain local awareness with minimal resource usage.
- A cooperative awareness system was developed to compress the information extracted from multiple uplink CAM messages, which is stored in the LDM, and aggregate it into CPM messages. This approach reduces the number of individual transmissions and lowers the overall load on the traffic channel, while still providing a consistent and efficient representation of the surrounding traffic environment.
- A Traffic Management Centre was further enhanced to operate as a real-time decision and strategy engine, integrating not just roadside perception (from AI cameras), but also from Connected and Automated Vehicles in order to generate context-aware traffic strategies such as speed reductions, distance-increase commands, lane-avoid recommendations, and hazard

alerts. The TMC demonstrated reliable end-to-end performance within UC3, confirming its capability to support cooperative traffic management on high-speed highway environments and to serve as a scalable core component for future CCAM deployments.

- A VRU risk-assessment and warning system was developed, including an ETSI ITS protocol stack capable of running on Android devices. This enables smartphones to generate and transmit VAM messages over their own internet connection, which are then sent to the MEC. The MEC can trigger DENM alerts to the relevant road users and also send CPMs back to the smartphone. Once decoded, these CPMs allow the device to compute local collision warnings. Collision-risk assessment can therefore be performed either centrally at the MEC or directly on the smartphone, offering flexibility and resilience.

Autonomous vehicle:

- A new OBU configuration solution embedded an open-source FlexStack communication protocol, has been developed to allow to the CAV shuttle to communicate with the ITS Infrastructure via DENM, IVIM, CAM. The open-source FlexStack communication protocol enables to offer an OBU configuration solution, which is functional, flexible, less expensive. Hardware integration and testing completed, confirming the effectiveness of this solution.
- New cooperative manoeuvres (traffic strategies) have been developed to allow to the CAV shuttle to operate autonomously in more safe conditions in urban region (50km/h) and highway region (80 km/h). The exchange of information from the ITS infrastructure (maximum speed limit scenario, emergency stop scenario) in one case and the on-demand service application in the other, made it possible to manage two different and complementary configurations of cooperative manoeuvres for the CAV shuttle. The tests carried out confirmed the positive contributions in terms of fluidity, safety and adaptability that these two configuration solutions bring to cooperative connected automated mobility.
- The on-demand service passenger app was developed to address mobility gaps in areas where traditional public transport is limited or inefficient, particularly in rural, peri-urban, and cross-border regions, offering flexible, user-driven transport services that can be booked in real time via a mobile interface. The app allows booking of the shuttle, schedules and plans the journey, informs the passenger about the status and gives information about statistics of the use (that could be the bases for additional features as loyalty programs based on sustainability and rewards). The pilot tests confirmed the app's effectiveness in addressing real mobility needs through a user-centric design.

Recommendations for the effective deployment of PoDIUM technologies

This section outlines the main recommendations and lessons drawn from the development and testing of the PoDIUM platform, highlighting practical considerations to support future deployments.

- The challenges encountered in UC3 underscore the need for a more harmonised European regulatory framework to support CAV testing and cross-border CCAM deployments. As demonstrated in the Spanish Living Lab, incompatible national rules on experimental plates and vehicle insurance prevented the lawful circulation of the MILLA CAV, despite extensive efforts to comply with both Spanish and French requirements. To avoid similar barriers in future projects, we recommend establishing EU-level harmonisation of temporary registration schemes, mutual recognition of experimental vehicle plates, and dedicated bilateral agreements that enable cross-border operation of research and test vehicles. In parallel, clearer procedures for obtaining permits and EU-wide insurance solutions, such as VIN-based coverage valid across Member States, would remove current administrative bottlenecks and accelerate real-world CAV testing. These improvements would create a more predictable regulatory environment and support the safe, efficient deployment of automated mobility services across Europe.

- From Autopistas' perspective, the effective deployment of PoDIUM technologies requires prioritising robust integration between roadside infrastructure, MEC platforms, and traffic-management systems, ensuring that strategy updates and hazard alerts remain reliable under real traffic loads. Early coordination with regulators is essential to avoid delays linked to permits, data policies, or cross-border operational constraints. We recommend strengthening standardisation of interfaces and message formats to simplify large-scale rollout, improving monitoring tools to ensure system observability, and securing stable 5G connectivity, ideally with redundancy, to guarantee consistent service performance. Finally, close collaboration with public authorities and other operators will be key to achieving interoperability and enabling phased expansion from pilot corridors to nationwide deployments.
- For an effective real-world deployment of PoDIUM technologies, full interoperability across all participating systems and stakeholders is essential. While each individual technology, mobile networks, cloud platforms, RSUs/OBUs, and road operator systems, is mature and reliable on its own, integration becomes challenging when they must operate together in a highly mobile environment. Practical issues can arise, such as ASN.1 encoding mismatches between providers, unpredictable handover latencies across 4G/5G/5G-SA, inconsistent data fields (timestamps, GPS, frequency), or LTE-PC5 congestion in dense areas. Additional difficulties include correlating large volumes of heterogeneous real-time data, coordinating certificate revocation processes, managing RF interference or coverage gaps, and the current lack of robust tools for end-to-end V2X traffic monitoring. Overcoming these interoperability challenges is crucial to ensure seamless operation and dependable performance in deployment scenarios.
- When transmitting ITS messages over IP and cellular networks, temporary disconnections can cause TCP-based mechanisms, either MQTT subscriptions or MEC-managed sockets, to buffer packets, delaying newer and more relevant information. Since outdated messages provide no value once fresher data is available, alternatives such as using UDP should be evaluated, provided that mechanisms are added to discard stale packets and prioritise recent ones. The main challenge is that UDP is less NAT-friendly, especially in mobile networks using private IPv4 addressing.
- The use of an open-source ETSI ITS protocol stack such as FlexStack [10] provides a high degree of flexibility, enabling full access to and modification of any field within the various ITS protocols. This openness greatly facilitates experimentation, debugging, and adaptation to project-specific needs. Its multi-platform compatibility makes it highly desirable for research and deployment activities, as the same implementation can run across heterogeneous environments. In our work, FlexStack has been successfully integrated into Cohda Wireless OBUs, deployed within MEC nodes, executed on smartphones for VRU applications, and used to build a connected-vehicle simulator in which vehicles broadcast real ITS messages. This broad applicability across diverse platforms demonstrates its value as a versatile and scalable solution for C-ITS developments.
- To ensure the sustainability, scalability and reliability of the CCAM, we recommend continuing the deployment of the technologies validated and proven during the project:
 - The successful cooperative manoeuvres demonstrate the functional maturity of the ecosystem, as well as the robustness of the V2X exchanges necessary for the dynamic coordination of CAVs and infrastructure.
 - The use of an OBU configuration solution based on an open-source communication protocol has proven particularly relevant, ensuring the interoperability, transparency and ease of maintenance of the system.
 - The use of a connected autonomous shuttle, fully integrated into the system, is an important asset in accelerating operational adoption and promoting the evolution towards an intelligent, reliable and scalable mobility service.

5. Use Case 4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

5.1. Introduction to the UC

UC4 demonstrates that the PDI provides CAVs with more valuable information compared to single-sensor vehicles, enabling them to perform manoeuvres that actively protect VRUs.

The use case takes place at the intersection of Corso Spezia and Via Ventimiglia in Turin, Italy. This intersection comprises a main road flanked by auxiliary roads on either side, with pedestrian crossings available in all directions through clearly marked lanes. The site is characterized by heavy traffic from both vehicles and VRUs, as numerous vehicles are parked and continuously circulating throughout the area. Located in a hospital district, the intersection sits near four hospitals within a few blocks. Traffic light infrastructure is installed at the intersection, with real-time data available from the municipal authority via standard Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message (SPATEM) and MAPEM messages.

The RSU is installed at the target intersection in Corso Spezia. On the MEC, previously provided by TIM, a C-ITS broker, a Digital Twin, a fusion module and a VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistance (VIMA) were installed.

The CAV prototype utilizes a Maserati Ghibli integrated with the PoDIUM on-board system to obtain trusted and highly reliable information regarding VRUs, including pedestrians and cyclists, at intersections via the PoDIUM infrastructure-based platform.

In addition to the existing AD Electronic Control Unit (ECU), the system comprises:

- A Links V2X OBU responsible for vehicle positioning and bidirectional communication between PoDIUM and the vehicle
- The Main PoDIUM ECU containing CRF's software applications, which synthesize vehicle dynamics, sensing, and V2X data to support the driver or AD function
- A CRF on-board display presenting the PoDIUM-specific HMI
- Most prototype components are housed on a metal rack located in the vehicle boot

UC4 explores the following scenarios:

- Scenario 1: Straight.
- Scenario 2: Right Turn.
- Scenario 3: Left Turn.

The global architecture and its main functional components, which have already been described in D3.3 [3], are illustrated in Figure 93 for ease of reference in this document.

Figure 93: UC4 functional diagram.

5.2. Completion of integration actions since the last deliverable

The following WP4 actions were completed in the period between the submission of D4.2 [5] and the present deliverable.

Integrations

- PC5 was integrated to the RSU as planned update. This update was necessary and was executed in parallel to a mitigation action in order to overcome some limitations arose regarding the permissions to access MEC with the installed SIM modules in the RSU. The result was verified and tested together with the OBU.
- A new version of VIMA was produced in order to track the trigger CPMs and their time of generation and so to be able to perform the calculation of some of the KPIs. VIMA logs have been recorded using that version.
- The trust computing software was integrated into the OBU and RSU hardware.
- The V2X OBU communicates with the PoDIUM infrastructure through a newly integrated PC5 interface, supporting both direct short-range and cellular network communications. This PC5 technology leverages 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)-standardized 4G LTE or 5G cellular networks to enable message exchange among vehicles, pedestrians, and roadside traffic management systems, including traffic signals. The system typically operates on the 5.9 GHz frequency band, which is officially allocated for ITS applications in most countries.
- Additionally, a new RSU has been deployed at the Corso Spezia intersection, also equipped with PC5 connectivity capabilities.
- The CPM detection functionality complements the final VIMA version. By generating timely warnings, it enables the system to calculate KPIs that measure VIMA's processing time.

- The integrity software architecture, originally defined by the Trusted Computing Group (TCG), integrates the Linux Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) module, Trusted Platform Module (TPM) 2.0, and a generic attestation protocol. For PoDIUM, this architecture was adapted by enabling IMA and TPM 2.0 to assess system trust during boot, while a custom attestation protocol performs continuous integrity verification during runtime. This work led to the creation of EMBRAVE, an open-source software solution that consolidates all attestation protocol components.

Non-functional tests

- CAV_007 CAV shall be equipped with C-V2X communication (PC5 and Uu). The OBU was also updated with PC5 connectivity.
- SYA_005 and SYA_006 [UC4] When and where possible software integrity verification shall be implemented in a privacy-preserving manner to avoid identification and linking. The final OBU hardware is equipped with a TPM and the required software to achieve both requirements.

Planned activities: adjustments and mitigation actions

- A new RSU version was installed because the Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) card in the previous unit could not establish proper connectivity with the Service Edge Node (SEN). Prior to replacement, a temporary solution was implemented using another RSU with a compatible SIM card as a bridge to link the original RSU to the SEN. Other mitigation action variant was to forward video to be processed in a LINK's node with SEN access. This mitigation action helped to perform integration tests of the other components with the previous RSU version which had overheating problems during summer.
- Due to multiple technical issues and bugs encountered during testing, in order to avoid an increased cost of using the project's vehicle too frequently, a vehicle was rented to conduct dedicated tests focusing exclusively on OBU performance and application debug.
- The initial UC4_KPI_3 on Crossing Manoeuvre Optimization could not be calculated with sufficient confidence, as the CAV manoeuvres were very often influenced by the traffic and presence of several surrounding vehicles. In fact, the KPI basic evaluation needs an isolated system with just the CAV, the VRUs and a few vehicles, not congested situations. Instead, a more meaningful KPI was introduced, which suits better for these kinds of scenarios: in traffic situations, V2X can still assist the driver providing information of potential VRU crossing, while on board sensors' field of view may be obstructed by other obstacles in the middle or the VRU about to cross may be outside the field of view. Therefore, UC4_KPI_3 was replaced with Crossing Manoeuvre Assistance, defined and evaluated in section 5.4.12.

5.3. Demonstration activities and data collection

UC validation has undergone multiple phases, including pre-tests (documented in deliverable D4.2 [5]), definitive tests to obtain the KPIs, and the final demonstration. The layout and the configuration of the different elements of the testbed are detailed in D4.2 [5].

The aspects that differentiate the pre-tests and the definitive tests are: During the pre-test, some workarounds were running in order to cope with unexpected situations, such as those described in the mitigation actions. Many pre-tests were performed in a rented CV equipped with the V2X OBU. On those tests all other logs were gathered differently from vehicle's log. Many of these tests were also useful to calculate some of the KPIs, such as platform KPIs, positioning in urban environment or those not related directly with the vehicle application itself. The definitive test to obtain the KPIs directly related with UC4 scenarios were performed in the following dates: 6.11.25, 12.11.25 and 17.11.25.

Each scenario was repeated several times to obtain meaningful statistics:

- Scenario 1 "right" was repeated 40 times.

- Scenario 2 "straight" was repeated a total of 31 times.
- Scenario 3 "left" was linked logistically with the straight, since the vehicle had to return to the start point passing by the crosspoint by doing a left turn. It was repeated 34 times.
- Scenario 4 "Remote Attestation" was repeated a total of 1000 times.

Figure 94 shows all the route paths around the test site in via Ventimiglia and Corso Spezia. The traces were made during the tests; positions and GNSS traces were recorded for later study and to check the behaviour of the fixes over time, given the demanding environment since the southern part of the plot is characterized by buildings, covering the skyview. The crosspoint was used for all three manoeuvre scenarios, so it was possible to record a combination of straight and left turn scenarios in a single run and turn right scenario alone with a return travel through the southern part of the map.

Figure 94: Samples of all possible paths in the test site of UC4.

In Figure 95 a photo of the RSU installed on one of the corners of the crosspoint. A pole was installed specifically to support the RSU and camera/LIDAR (above the RSU in the picture).

Figure 95: UC4 RSU installed in the crosspoint.

Figure 96 is a scheme that allows non technical users to understand the fusion through truthfulness concept and the data flow over the VIMA application. It was developed for a demonstration at EUCAD25 conference.

The final demonstration was done on the date 15 October 2025 in the crosspoint premises, in via Ventimiglia and corso Spezia, after intensive pre-demo sessions the days and weeks before.

A Demo booth was present in the parking located a few meters away from the crosspoint (Figure 97 and Figure 98). The Italia LL partners explained the system during the demo. The streaming from a live webcam from the vehicle cockpit was shown on a large screen at the booth.

Figure 97 left shows the explanation of the vehicle internal interface in real time via streaming. On the right, there is an explanation of the live moving objects detected by the RSU Camera and LIDAR sensors, displayed on a visualizer developed for debugging purposes.

Figure 96: UC4 schematic summary of VIMA application.

Figure 97: UC4 demo explanation in booth.

Figure 98: LL demo participants.

During the execution of the UC4 trials, multiple datasets were collected and stored in a repository.

Table 72 of the Annex outlines the whole set of logged parameters and the links to access them. This data has been collected in the logging points indicated in Figure 99 and following the guiding lines of D4.2 [4].

Figure 99: Logging points in the UC4's functional diagram according to D4.1 [4].

The dataset used for the computation of the KPIs is structured as follows:

- The logs of CAV for KPI_P_1-5 are located in the folder UC4_KPI_P_1-5.
- Regarding KPI_P_6-9, the logs are located in folder UC4_KPI_P_6-9.
- The logs of CAV for KPI_UC4_1 are located in the folder UC4_KPI_1_CAV.
- The logs from OBU side for KPI_UC4_2 are located in the folder UC4_KPI_2_OBU.
- The logs of CAV for KPI_UC4_3 are located in the folder UC4_KPI_3_CAV.
- The logs of MEC side for KPI_UC4_4 are located in the folder UC4_KPI_4_MEC.

5.4. Trial Results

In this section, we present the results of the Test Cases proposed for UC3 in D5.1 [4]. The results have been obtained through analysis of the previous data sets.

5.4.1. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_1 Service Availability in UC4

The percentage of time that the different services are up and functioning with respect of the observation time. It measures the availability of the devices and their software together. For UC4 it represents the time of activity of the services with respect to the total run time. It can be applied to all services present in the systems, such as OBU and RSU and SEN.

Method of calculation

Tests were conducted on 11.11.25 and 17.11.25, using the complete asset configuration: CAV, OBU, RSU, and SEN. All system logs were captured and stored in the cloud for subsequent analysis.

A Python script was developed to automatically detect message exchange gaps in the recorded logs. The script reads each log file line by line, extracts and parses message timestamps, and calculates the time difference between consecutive timestamps. Any gap exceeding the defined threshold of 1.0 second is flagged as a potential communication failure. This threshold was selected based on the system requirement that the OBU and the SEN must exchange messages at 1-second intervals, meaning any deviation beyond this duration indicates a performance degradation or communication issue.

Table 36: TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC4			
Materials used	RSU, OBU, SEN separately			
KPI	KPI_P_1 service Availability in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Total Availability	Non-Availability Gap	Overall Availability
	15	41 m 56 s	0 s	100%

Conclusions

The overall OBU service availability is optimal, maintaining 100% uptime throughout testing with no service interruptions. This metric was calculated across 15 complete UC4 test runs utilizing the full system architecture: a CAV, an OBU, an RSU, the C-ITS message exchange system, 5G network, and SEN.

Service availability was also analysed for the RSU and SEN components specifically. Both demonstrated strong performance, with the RSU operating for 4 hours and the SEN for 3 hours and 19 minutes. However, the SEN experienced a brief 23-second service gap during the test run conducted on November 17th, resulting in 99.8% of service availability. Considering all these results above the threshold of 95%, the KPI has reached the target.

5.4.2. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_2 Update Latency in UC4

Describes the amount of time a message takes to be uploaded into the SEN from the vehicle or from the RSU. It accounts for the time a sensor updates its information into the PoDIUM platform.

Method of calculation

The measurements have been done according to Work Package (WP) requirements. Logs have been recorded in OBU and SEN nodes; then messages have been matched on both logs. Then their messages timestamps were operated to obtain the difference. The requirement here is the complete synchronization between OBU and SEN clocks. Messages on the path OBU towards SEN correspond to update latency, while messages coming from SEN correspond to notification latency. A part of the logs recorded were used for these tests since the nodes were not synchronized all the runs. All messages contributed to the KPI, such as CAM, and CPM.

In parallel, measurements on the same transmission paths were recorded using Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) protocol. The timestamp was recorded every time and then every transmission delay from OBU to SEN and SEN to OBU were recorded.

Table 37: TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC4			
Materials used	RSU, OBU, sensors, CAV, SEN			
KPI	KPI_P_2 updateLatency in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	700	47.07 ms	39 ms	28.16 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	168 ms	4 ms	[23, 139] ms	133 ms

Plots

Figure 100: KPI_P_2_updateLatency in UC4.

Figure 101: KPI_P_2_updateLatency using ICMP in UC4.

We have plotted either the KPI recorded via C-ITS message transmissions in the respective brokers (in OBU and SEN) (Figure 100) and the KPI 2 measured via ICMP at low level (Figure 101). The ICMP transmission paths are compatible with the 5G expected timings; the 95% of values are within 13ms. This would be the minimum time for messages for upper levels, such as the KPI_P_2.

Conclusions

The update latency was recorded as specified earlier in the project and obtained results compatible with the high bandwidth available of 5G transmissions, benefitting of the nearest path from OBU and SEN infrastructure. A typical update latency of 47 ms allows the UC4 application VIMA to receive sensor data in a timely manner. The 95th percentile is 133 ms. By examining the tail of the CDF, the last percentage is made by some outlier data, well separated by the 90% of the data. The verification criterion states that the range should be between 50 ms and 2500 ms, so our 95th percentile is validated, reaching the target.

5.4.3. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_3 Notification Latency in UC4

Describes the amount of time that a message needs to be downloaded from the SEN node to the OBU or the RSU. It accounts for the time the PoDIUM platform uses to notify a OBU with a warning or C-ITS message.

The measurements have been done as in KPI_P_2 according to WP4 requirements. Logs have been recorded in SEN and OBU nodes; then messages have been matched on both logs. Then their messages timestamps were operated to obtain the difference. The messages coming from SEN correspond to notification latency. A part of the logs recorded were used for these tests since the nodes were not synchronized all the runs. All messages contributed to the KPI, such as CAM, and CPM.

As for KPI_P_2, paths were recorded using also ICMP protocol. The timestamp was recorded every time and then every transmission delay from OBU to SEN and SEN to OBU were recorded.

Method of calculation

Same as previous KPI.

Table 38: TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC4			
Materials used	RSU, OBU, sensors, CAV, SEN			
KPI	KPI_P_3 notificationLatency in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	220	18 ms	13 ms	19.03 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	145 ms	5 ms	[6, 72] ms	58.05 ms

Plots

Figure 102: KPI_P_3_NotificationLatency in UC4.

Figure 103: KPI_P_3_NotificationLatency in UC4 measured by means of ICMP.

We have plotted either the KPI recorded via C-ITS message transmissions in the respective brokers (in OBU and SEN) (Figure 102) and the KPI 3 measured via ICMP at low level (Figure 103). The ICMP transmission paths are compatible with the 5G expected timings; the 95% of values are within 10ms. This would be the minimum time for messages for upper levels, such as the KPI_P_3.

Conclusions

The notification latency was measured and it is compatible with the high bandwidth available of 5G transmissions, A typical notification latency of 18 ms allows the UC4 vehicle to receive warnings as soon as few tens of milliseconds after the warning has been generated. The 95th percentile of this time is 58 ms. The verification criterion states that the range should be between 50 ms and 2500 ms, so our 95th percentile is validated, reaching the target.

5.4.4. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_4 Processing Delay in UC4

The processing delay relates with the time required for the service to produce an output warning. In UC4 there is a KPI specifically related with the VIMA application, so the processing delay reported here regards the time required to generate a DENM message based on the arrival of a trigger CPM.

Method of calculation

Both messages were traced and the time difference between both is printed directly in the SEN log.

Table 39: TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC4			
Materials used	SEN			
KPI	KPI_P_4 processingDelay in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	12744	40.58 ms	39 ms	14.92
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	255	9	[19, 71] ms	63 ms

Plot

Figure 104: KPI_P_4 processingDelay in UC4.

As the plot depicts and the table describes, the processing delay of the UC4 capability to process CPMs to produce a DENM, there is a large quantity of CPMs reported in a single date of tests; all these CPMs did not generate an actual DENM, but were processed together with the rest of the DT snapshot in order to generate the risk condition that can trigger the DENM. A CPM is produced every 300 ms, so not all those CPMs generated a warning in the vehicle.

Conclusions

The result of the processing delay of this part of the application is within an optimal limit, since 63 ms as 95th percentile is as low as a propagation delay of the warning message going towards the VRU or the CAV. The maximum value of 255 ms warrants specific attention, as it is likely caused by dense traffic situations or a high volume of detected objects. These measurements reflect two hours of experimentation during morning traffic, which represents the peak density of the day. As the validation criterion defines the acceptance range as 50 ms to 2.5 s, this KPI has successfully met the target.

5.4.5. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_5 Com Reliability in UC4

Communication reliability is assessed by measuring the message reception rate, specifically, the proportion of SEN transmissions successfully received by the OBU.

Method of calculation

A Python script has been developed to count the messages received from the OBU in each run, read the hashes, and compare them to those of the messages transmitted from the SEN. The ratio of the received and the transmitted messages gives a good perspective on the reliability of the communication system via broker.

Table 40: TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC4			
Materials used	OBU, SEN			
KPI	KPI_P_5 comReliability in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	# Messages exchanged	# Messages lost	# Overall reliability
	15	65781	0	100%

Conclusions

The overall reliability of the communication system is 100%, as the OBU received all messages transmitted from the SEN without any loss.

5.4.6. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_6 Sealed Object in UC4

This KPI demonstrates the correct integration of the TPM on OBUs and RSUs, testing its Sealing and Unsealing functionalities.

Method of calculation

The KPI was measured by simulating a file to be protected with an internal TPM key (sealing) and its subsequent decryption (unsealing). A properly integrated TPM must be able to perform these operations successfully. Testing sealing and unsealing functions with the currently integrated TPM.

The system was tested by repeating the unsealing function of the TPM several times over a sealed secret. A successful unsealing is considered success, otherwise FAIL.

The test is considered success if 99% of the tests are success.

Table 41: TC_KPI_P_6-SealedObject in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_6-SealedObject in UC4			
Materials used	OBU/RSU hardware			
KPI	KPI_P_6 SealedObject in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# Tests	# Success	# Fail	Successful tests
	10	10	0	100%

Conclusions

All tests were successful, in line with the expectation of >99% success. This demonstrates the correct integration and functioning of the TPM on the platform.

5.4.7. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_7 Load Boot Time in UC4

During the boot phase, the IMA measures the hash value of all executed files and uses it to extend the TPM's PCR10, potentially resulting in an increase in the boot phase. This KPI evaluates how much the OBU/RSU boot time increases when the software integrity architecture is enabled.

Method of calculation

Starting from a powered-off OBU/RSU without the Software Integrity Architecture (SIA), it is powered on until the system has finished booting. The kernel boot time is read using the system-analyse command. The same process is then performed from an OBU/RSU with SIA enabled.

The KPI is considered passed if the increase in boot time, due to the SIA, is less than 30%.

Table 42: TC_KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime in UC4			
Materials used	OBU/RSU hardware			
KPI	TC_KPI_P_7 LoadBootTime in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean without SIA	Mean with SIA	Increase
	10	2.835 s	4.107 s	44.864 %

Conclusions

The initially set KPI was not met because the increase in boot time with SIA enabled is 44.864%, which is higher than the set limit of 30%. However, the increase in boot time remains marginal in relation to the platform's operation and does not affect its functioning.

5.4.8. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_8 Load Run Time in UC4

This KPI measures the load on the CPU and memory due to the Attestation framework. The Agent running on the OBU/RSU adds a memory and computation load that should not overload the system.

Method of calculation

The OBU/RSU is left in the steady state for 15 minutes, then the CPU and memory usage are read with the *htop* command, which provides the RAM used and the average CPU load over 15 minutes.

The EMBRAVE Attester is run on the OBU/RSU for 15 minutes, then the CPU and memory usage, with the attestation load, is collected in the same way.

The KPI is considered passed if the difference between the CPU percentage is < 10% and the difference between the memory percentage is < 20%.

Table 43: TC_KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime in UC4			
Materials used	OBU/RSU hardware			
KPI	KPI_P_8 LoadRunTime in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	CPU usage (steady state)	Memory usage (steady state)	CPU difference	Memory difference
	1.5%	2.40%	3.75%	0.12%
	CPU usage (attestation)	Memory usage (attestation)		
	5.25%	2.52%		

Conclusions

The KPI is passed, as the difference in CPU % and memory % are, respectively, 3.75% and 0.12%, which is well below 10% and 20%. These figures highlight how the EMBRAVE attestation framework is extremely light in terms of computational and memory load on OBU/RSU.

5.4.9. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_9 Remote Attestation in UC4

This KPI measures the performance of the Remote Attestation protocol.

Method of calculation

The attestation protocol is performed repeatedly by the MEC to attest the OBU, measuring the latency of the protocol from the start of attestation to the issuance of trust status. 1000 repetitions are performed and the data is collected by the remote attester (RSU/MEC).

The KPI is considered passed if the protocol duration is less than 3s.

Table 44: TC_KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation in UC4			
Materials used	OBU and a laptop as RSU/MEC			
KPI	KPI_P_9 RemoteAttestation in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	1000	1.303 s	1.286 s	0.057 s
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	1.732 s	1.145 s	[1.257, 1.462] s	1.401 s

Plot

Figure 105: KPI_P_9 Remote Attestation times distribution.

Conclusions

The KPI has been passed. The data shows that the attestation time is well below 3 seconds, as the maximum is 1.732 seconds enabling periodic certification that does not slow down the system.

5.4.10. Test Case for KPI_UC4_1 VIMA_detection_performance in UC4

This KPI evaluates the reliability of the VIMA application in detecting VRUs who violate the intersection by crossing during a red traffic light. In scenario 1.2, the vehicle approaches the intersection in a straight path while a VRU disregards the traffic signal, creating a potential collision risk. The application is expected to issue a warning to the driver about the VRU’s hazardous action. The KPI metrics is based on a confusion matrix (True/False Positives/Negatives) and evaluates:

- PI1.1: Probability of detection (%): true positives over total expected positives.
- PI1.2: False positive rate (%): false pop-up over total expected negatives.
- PI1.3: Accuracy (%): correct matching (positive/negative) over total.
- PI1.4: Precision (%): All true positives over all detections (alias detection reliability).

Method of calculation

The received DENMs at CAV were compared with the experimental evidence, using annotations written during the field tests but also with the DENM issued by the Podium infrastructure. For this scope, the OBU podium logs were considered, decoded and analysed. On every run, the conditions were checked whether the CPM describing the pedestrian was present, if the DENM was generated by infrastructure, and if DENM was relevant for the vehicle situation. A DENM is generated whenever a trajectory conflict is estimated by the VIMA application at the MEC. Hereafter, detection of trajectory conflicts are reported. The only true negative case was due to the obstruction of the roadside camera field of view by physical obstacles so that the roadside sensors could not see the VRU. As we’re evaluating the algorithm not the physical installations, this case is considered as an expected negative for DENM generation.

Figure 106: True negative condition for run at 11.11.25.

Table 45: TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4: DENM generation.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Materials used	CAV, OBU, RSU, Sensors			
KPI	KPI_UC4_1 VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# true positive	# true negative	# false negative	# false positive
	23	1	5	0
	Probability of Detection	False Positive Rate	Accuracy	Precision
	85 %	0 %	86 %	100 %

DENM relevance

Whenever a DENM is generated by the application, a warning is provided to the driver if the DENM event, from its EventPosition, is deemed relevant for the vehicle motion.

Table 46 reports the relevance for the vehicle system based on vehicle dynamics with respect to the event position included in the generated message.

Table 46: TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4: Relevance of DENM for the vehicle.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Materials used	CAV, OBU, RSU, Sensors			
KPI	KPI_UC4_1 VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# true positive	# true negative	# false negative	# false positive
	20	1	7	0
	Probability of Detection	False Positive Rate	Accuracy	Precision
	74 %	0 %	75 %	100 %

The reason for a higher error rate (translating in lower probability of detection and accuracy) is due to some specific cases in which the DENM was generated by the Podium application, but with a mismatched event position, not corresponding to the estimated VRU position. In those cases, the vehicle dynamics which is correctly estimated, was compared with a wrong DENM position not corresponding to the Ground Truth of the VRU crossing.

DENM and CPM

The in-vehicle ADAS/AD system, on Podium main PC, receives from the V2X OBU (that performs the relevance checks for DENM, CPM and other V2X messages) a set of obstacles obtained from relevant CPM and DENM. For all those scenarios in which the DENM was not reported to the ADAS/AD ECU as wrongly deemed not relevant (the false negatives of previous table) we checked if a relevant CPM obstacle was sent by the V2X OBU to the ADAS/AD ECU, corresponding to the pedestrian crossing. The check was performed in post processing looking at the CPM trajectory with respect to its crossing path and the vehicle trajectory.

Table 47: TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4: Awareness on vehicle (including CPM relevant obstacle).

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Materials used	CAV, OBU, RSU, Sensors			
KPI	KPI_UC4_1 VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# true positive	# true negative	# false negative	# false positive
	27	1	0	0
	Probability of Detection	False Positive Rate	Accuracy	Precision
	100 %	0 %	100 %	100 %

We found that in all the False Negative cases of the previous table (where no DENM notifications were generated) the On-Board system, as well as the driver, was aware of the VRU from the CPM. Here, it is worth mentioning, that detections from vehicle’s own sensors are intentionally excluded, because we’re evaluating the mere contribution of V2X.

Bench tests

All the tests related with this KPI up to here were performed using real vehicles, either LINKS rented vehicle and project vehicle. Given that the small number of runs did not allow to reach a high target value of performance and since there were no other dates for vehicle availability to perform other experiments, some bench experiments were run, using the same OBU equipment and the infrastructure, with the only difference of using a GNSS trace file as the emulated position of the vehicle. GNSS trace was recorded from the previous experiments and the pedestrians were really detected while crossing the pedestrian lane under consideration. The results are summarized in Table 49.

Table 48: TC KPI UC4 1 VIMA detection performance in UC4 using bench tests.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Materials used	OBU, RSU			
KPI	KPI_UC4_1 VIMA_detection_performance in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# true positive	# true negative	# false negative	# false positive
	14	0	0	0
DENM Generation	Probability of Detection	False Positive Rate	Accuracy	Precision
	100 %	0 %	100 %	100 %
Descriptive Statistics	# true positive	# true negative	# false negative	# false positive
	14	0	0	0
DENM Relevant	Probability of Detection	False Positive Rate	Accuracy	Precision
	100 %	0 %	100 %	100 %
Descriptive Statistics	# true positive	# true negative	# false negative	# false positive
	14	0	0	0
CPM Relevant	Probability of Detection	False Positive Rate	Accuracy	Precision
	100 %	0 %	100 %	100 %

Conclusions

The detection performance of VIMA, considering the detection of a trajectory conflict DENM generation, was close to the target under the real conditions. In the few false cases VIMA did not generate a DENM or generated DENM with mismatched position, but all the time VIMA generated correct and relevant CPM. So in all the cases of hazardous situation due to VRU crossing, the ADAS/AD system of the CAV received relevant V2X messages informing of a relevant hazard onboard.

5.4.11. Test Case for KPI_UC4_2 Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban in UC4

The positioning accuracy is a challenging target in urban environment due to the low number of visible satellites and the necessity of activating other auxiliary strategies to improve the precision. The accuracy is the maximum uncertainty or discrepancy in distance units that the position might have from the real vehicle position.

Method of calculation

The ETSI common data dictionary specifications, implemented inside the OBU, determine that the position accuracy must be transmitted on every CAM message produced by the vehicle. This accuracy is already calculated and estimated by the GNSS receiver as a result of the fusion of different local

sensor data, such as 3 axes gyroscopes and 3 axes accelerations. The accuracy is propagated via CAM messages in the semimajor axis in centimetre units. It represents the maximum distance of an ellipse containing the 95% of the possible position solutions of the receiver in the current fix. This quantity was used as direct calculation to characterize this KPI. During UC4 tests, the CAM messages were recorded (and also their NMEA traces) and so the KPI was calculated from this data. The traces were filtered removing the stopped moments before the experiments, since being the vehicle still, the sensor’s noise obscures the zero-acceleration readings and the position tends to be less precise. In fact, the fixes produced in the moving vehicle have a lower mean and percentile values than the static ones. Here moving values are reported.

Table 49: TC_KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban in UC4			
Materials used	OBU.			
KPI	KPI_UC4_2 Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	15075	29.15 cm	26 cm	21.22
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	217 cm	1 cm	[9, 81] cm	57 cm

Plot

Figure 107: KPI_UC4_2 Vehicle Positioning Accuracy.

The plot shows semimajor and semiminor axes values in centimetres. The difference reflects how Semimajor axis represents an upper bound of the precision uncertainty.

Conclusions

As discussed in the methodology, the fixes tend to be more uncertain as the vehicle remains static. A further integration with a speed sensor would have reached an even better accuracy. However, the precision reached with the considered hardware was optimal for UC4 purposes. Actually, the vehicle position recorded by the camera was used to calibrate the positioning accuracy of the camera and Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) sensor, and the objects seen in the vehicle HMI were visualized in their correct positions as expected from the driver’s perspective. The KPI validation data states that 20

cm were necessary to pass the KPI test; but actually, in UC4 the 57 cm were enough to run all trials stably.

The test done without RTK in the test site were successful but resulted in demonstrating a strong dependency of the receiver on the availability of RTK corrections, in synergy with the GNSS sensors' fusion functionality, since the test site is characterized by the so-called urban canyons, so even if the inertial sensors are useful, a corrected positioning solution is necessary where better sky visibility conditions are present. The results say that 68% of the values are within 50 cm and the 90% is below 1.5 m. This is still a result very near the validation criterion of 1.5 m for the 95th percentile.

5.4.12. Test Case for KPI_UC4_3 VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_ optimization in UC4

This KPI evaluates the capability of the V2X system to assist in crossing manoeuvres by providing early detection and full assistance coverage at the intersection, related to VRU presence, compared to on-board perception systems (e.g., camera). The objective is to measure how much earlier V2X can perceive VRUs relative to the vehicle's distance from the intersection, ensuring improved safety and decision-making during crossing. The target is 100% coverage in the areas covered by the onboard sensors, and extend the assistance by at least 25%, measured in terms of distance to the traffic light stop line.

Method of calculation

The KPI is computed by dividing the approach to the intersection into distance bins (e.g., 0–5 m, 5–10 m, ...). For each interval, the system checks whether at least one VRU object is detected by CPM or by the sensor. If detection occurs, the interval is marked as "covered"; if not, it is marked as "not covered".

After processing all test cases, the detection rate for each distance range is calculated by counting how often coverage was achieved and expressing it as a percentage of the total cases in that range. This method provides a clear comparison of how early and consistently V2X and sensor systems detect VRUs during the approach to the intersection.

Table 50: TC_KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_assistance in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_assistance in UC4			
Materials used	CAV, OBU, RSU, Sensors.			
KPI	KPI_UC4_3 VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_assistance in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# tests	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	19	52.96 m	53.14 m	19.74 m
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	83.07 m	26.31 m	[36.87, 69.05] m	78.45 m

Plot

Histogram in Figure 108 shows the VRU detection rate (% of detections over all the trials) as a function of the vehicle's distance to the intersection. Two detection sources are compared:

- CPM: Collective Perception Messages transmitted from the infrastructure and received by CAV.
- Sensor: On-board vision-based detection.

The results show that V2X achieves detection at significantly greater distances (up to 80 m), whereas the sensor detects VRUs only within approximately 30 m. Even considering a threshold of >90% of

positive detections, the distance of 100% CPM received (25-30 m) is almost twice the distance at which sensors have detected VRU (10-15 m).

Figure 108: Reception of VRU object by on board front sensor and by CPM, over all samples.

Conclusions

The KPI analysis demonstrates that V2X technology significantly enhances crossing manoeuvre assistance by enabling earlier detection of VRUs compared to on-board sensor systems. This extended perception range provides a critical safety advantage, allowing more time for decision-making and manoeuvre execution.

5.4.13. Test Case for KPI_UC4_4 VIMA_timing in UC4

The KPI evaluates the time required by the VIMA to complete the full process of risk assessment and the IVIM transmission in the event of a detected collision risk. Specifically, the measurement begins when VIMA starts computing the risk and ends when, after confirming the presence of danger, it transmits the IVIM to the vehicle. This indicator reflects the system’s overall responsiveness and its ability to deliver timely warnings to ensure road safety.

Method of calculation

The duration of each operating cycle was determined by calculating the difference between the timestamp marking the start of the risk calculation process and the timestamp corresponding to the moment the IVIM was transmitted. This approach made it possible to accurately measure the total processing time required by VIMA to complete a full risk detection and communication cycle.

Table 51: TC_KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing in UC4.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing in UC4			
Materials used	VIMA logs In order to perform this calculation, it was necessary to record the start and end times of the operation cycle, which were displayed directly by the VIMA algorithm. Therefore, no sources external to VIMA were used for this calculation.			
KPI	KPI_UC4_4 VIMA_timing in UC4			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	1056	4.41 ms	4 ms	1.36 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	16 ms	2 ms	[3, 8] ms	6 ms

Plot

Figure 109: Distribution of the time required by the VIMA to end all of its operations per each trigger.

Conclusions

VIMA demonstrated very low and highly consistent operating times. Although a few isolated samples showed processing times up to four times higher than the average, these instances were rare and not statistically significant. The 95th percentile was measured at 6 ms, only about 1.6 ms above the average value, confirming that the system operates with high speed and stability. Overall, these results indicate that VIMA performs its functions both rapidly and reliably over time.

The measured delay between the camera frame and the CPM generation is within 50 ms; as a result of this, and recalling the values of KPI_P_2 and KPI_P_3 the sum of worst-case update latency, notification latency together with the VIMA timing and the CPM generation delay, the reaction time considering sensor update, VIMA processing and notification to the CAV becomes 247 ms; this fits into the target reaction time considered of 300 ms.

5.5. Conclusions

In D2.1 [1] (page 16), we identified the following **potential needs**, which have been successfully addressed during the project's development:

- To set up a complex and realistic traffic environment for testing, comprising a mix of vehicles with different connectivity levels, conventional vehicles, and VRUs. This was possible through the Digital Twin running in the MEC and the fixed infrastructure sensors and app that feed data into it.
- To achieve advanced levels of accuracy and reliability to comply with the close-to-market-ready objective. UC4 used strategies for precise positioning in a mass-market hardware; also detection positioning was enforced by fusion, reaching the precision required for the UC manoeuvres.
- To set up an edge server for deploying the Digital Twin, with the capability of processing large amounts of data in real time,

- Availability of a commercial 5G network, to provide a realistic and reliable communication infrastructure. The SEN solution given by TIM was the proper environment to host the applications with also low latency
- To comply with the ETSI C-ITS messages specification.

To fulfil these needs, we anticipated several **potential challenges**, as outlined in D2.1 [1] (page 17), which have been effectively managed:

- Ensuring trustworthiness and truthfulness of data: this involves implementing advanced concepts of trust, such as TPM and the integrity primitives and protocols, and requires fusing information from multiple and heterogeneous sources to enhance truthfulness.
- Compliance with hybrid communications, including short-range and cellular communication.
- Ensuring seamless communication and interoperability between different communication technologies and this has been faced using an implementation of the current standards.

Overall, we have successfully achieved the **strategic goals** defined in D2.1 [1] (page 15). Below are the conclusions regarding their attainment, based on the results obtained so far

- Enable cooperative perception for CAVs by equipping vehicles, RSUs and VRUs with the required software and hardware capabilities to perceive reliable data from integral sources.
- Enhancing situational awareness and ODDs of CAVs via a Digital Twin service running on the MEC. The sensor data being shared and elaborated in the MEC side and then sent to the vehicles, enhances the vehicle situational awareness.
- Enhancing trust in the information received from the PDI. The concept of truthfulness, developed via redundancy and data fusion reliability produces enhanced CPM and therefore there is more reliable information available for vehicles and for applications, such as VIMA.
- Compliance with hybrid communication approach: short-range ad-hoc communication and cellular communication. The availability and reliability calculated for 5G interfaces is high and the presence of alternative LTE-PC5 short range communication increases the total reliability.
- Ensuring authenticity and integrity of C-ITS messages according to C-ROADS specifications. This was done due the availability of the security handling capability of the ITS messages. Also on the part of integrity, the OBU has been equipped with the attestation mechanism to validate the integrity of the software running on it considering the OBU as a sealed object protected by attestation mechanism.

Finally, through the development of this use case, the project has accomplished the following **key technological advancements**.

Communications:

- ETSI-compliant protocol stack (GeoNetworking, BTP, C-ITS) on the OBU for seamless communication.
- Gateway that combines the transmission of C-ITS messages over C-V2X and 5G networks, carrying also precise positioning strategies.
- A gateway ensuring low latency and robust data exchange between the intra-vehicle network and the external system, including C-ITS messages and precise positioning data.
- Seamless interaction with 5G MEC applications via SEN platform services, ensuring adequate response times for real-time decision-making.

ITS applications:

- Infrastructure-based awareness and assistance system, based on a Digital Twin and a dedicated VRU intersection movement assist application, providing collective perception data, warnings and recommendations to CAVs approaching an intersection.

- A VRU aware intersection manoeuvre assistant application that provides timely assistance to the CAV via C-ITS messages to use the crosspoint considering priority of vulnerable road users.
- An OBU that behaves as a sealed object, complying with the Trust Computing Group specifications monitoring the integrity of its software.

Autonomous vehicle:

- An on-board communication unit (OBU) with trust computing capabilities that allows protection of OBU applications and infrastructure data upstream against integrity attacks on C-ITS stations.
- Precise positioning strategies for CAV sub-meter localization utilizing mass market hardware.
- On-board applications, on the electronic control unit of the vehicle, performing V2X and sensors data fusion and assisting the driver or the automated driving function with enhanced awareness of VRUs and other road users at urban intersections.

Recommendations for the effective deployment of PoDIUM technologies

This section outlines the main recommendations and lessons drawn from the development and testing of the PoDIUM platform, highlighting practical considerations to support future deployments.

- A living lab in a public road, characterised by mid-heavy traffic volumes of pedestrian and vehicles, is very useful for collective perception assessment, but it needs to be complemented with track measurements controlling the VRU crossing and the CAV manoeuvres.

6. Use Case 5: Risk Management in Highway Tunnel

6.1. Introduction to the UC

UC5 "Risk Management in Highway Tunnel" represents the motorway use case of the Italian Living Lab. It is implemented on the A22 "Autostrada del Brennero", specifically on a road segment that includes the tunnel near the city of Bolzano. Using roadside sensors and vehicles' data (CAM and CPM messages from connected vehicles), a dedicated application within the PoDIUM platform computes and maintains a risk index of the current status of the tunnel with real traffic and sends its feedback to CAVs to help them make a safer decision. More specifically, UC5 scenarios demonstrate that approaching CAVs can receive DENM messages for roadwork warnings and hazard notifications, activate Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (C-ACC) for cut-in manoeuvre management via CAM, and perform cooperative perception, essential for highly automated driving, through CPM exchange with neighboring vehicles. To account for GNSS denied environments such as highway tunnels, UC5 also deployed positioning solutions, including a data-fusion-based dead reckoning system on board the CAV and a V2I-based system to locate vehicles inside the tunnel.

Scenarios of UC5 include:

- Road Works Warning applied to Cooperative ACC.
- Traffic Jam Ahead Warning, one CAV, repeated 18 times.
- AD Operational Design Domain in presence of Traffic Jam.

The global architecture and its main functional components, which have already been described in D3.3 [3], are illustrated in Figure 110 for ease of reference in this document.

Figure 110: UC5 functional diagram.

6.2. Completion of integration actions since the last deliverable

Following the initial integration of the Risk Assessment module with the C-ITS framework, the system has been optimized to achieve higher accuracy.

Additionally, the issue of mismatched message IDs, which occurred when risk assessments used existing C-ITS messages to generate refined outputs, has been addressed. This ensures that vehicles will not receive contradictory warning information. The improved integration also enables the broadcast of messages through adjacent RSUs located beyond the pilot site, providing relevant warnings to incoming traffic approaching the tunnel.

These enhancements collectively improve the reliability, timeliness, and coverage of cooperative risk warnings for CAVs in the tunnel environment.

The vehicle detection algorithm at the road infrastructure system has also been improved, and its results were compared with aggregated data provided by the road operator.

Despite partial sensor coverage of the road operator, this comparison allowed a robust assessment of detection accuracy and confirmed a high level of agreement between the Risk Assessment module outputs and observed traffic conditions. This validation supports the effectiveness of the system.

During the last reporting period, several efforts have been put in the availability of the RSU sensors in the Tusch tunnel. On the side of integrations, some preliminary tests were done interconnecting the Digital Twin and the risk management module with A22 operator infrastructure. The RSU with camera runs the required algorithms to perform preliminary measurements on vehicle counting and to calculate risk management condition.

Almost all road tests on UC5 scenarios had been completed at the time of D4.2 submission. In November, one additional test session in the Tusch tunnel was performed, with the aim to verify the whole Podium system, with messages generated from the risk management module.

Planned activities: adjustments and mitigation actions

The second camera was planned to be installed in the tunnel, but there was not a suitable slot for installation available, so the measurements have been done with the first RSU without problems, since the second camera is used to track the number of vehicles out of the tunnel, having counted the vehicles entering the tunnel with the first camera. In any case the Risk Management calculations were based on the information produced by the first camera and this does not affect the rest of the process chain. Already from the start, the focus has been on assessing CAV positioning in tunnel and comparing it with the performance outside the tunnel. While the dead reckoning solution was fine for the intended scenarios, the V2I based positioning solution (trilateration) was very challenging in terms of RSU placement. Among the test sessions performed in the Living Lab, specific positioning trials were performed in controlled scenarios, to change configuration of RSUs and run the vehicle use cases.

Indeed, the RSU's could not be placed inside the tunnel, but were installed at its exit and did not cover the intended stretch. Therefore, the tests with trilateration positioning systems and Podium scenarios were performed in a test track (Bolzano Safety Park) disabling the GNSS on the CAV. Even in this controlled environment and with carefully chosen positions of RSU's, the experiments did not yield the expected performance

An additional experiment was planned during the final project phase in a BRE closed area to explore potential performance improvements. However, the last test session could not be executed because some RSUs at the Tusch tunnel exit could not be removed due to traffic and safety constraints.

Despite this, the absence of these trials did not affect the overall evaluation for three reasons: first, previous tests had already indicated limited expectations for performance gains in this configuration; second, the data fusion-based approach employed for the tunnel scenarios demonstrated satisfactory performance for the intended use case; and third, RSUs were already deployed at distances below 100

meters, denser than the vendor’s recommended 200–250 meters, while still respecting the physical width constraints of the tunnel.

The main limitation of the system is imposed by the tunnel geometry. As a two-lane tunnel, its width is too narrow to allow accurate trilateration with the current tools. Even with a dense RSU deployment, accuracy remained limited, and increasing the number of RSUs further would not be cost-effective.

6.3. Demonstration activities and data collection

UC validation has undergone multiple phases, including pre-tests (documented in deliverable D4.2 [5]), definitive tests to obtain the KPIs, and the final demonstration. Figure 111 shows the different sites where tests were performed, the specific layout and the configuration of the different elements of the testbed are detailed in D4.2 [5].

Figure 111: Sites of the experimental activity of UC5.

The pre-tests were done without the vehicle but assessing the compatibility of messages and the proper generation on the part of the Risk Management in Tunnel (RMT). Almost all road tests on UC5 scenarios had been completed at the time of D4.2 submission.

Following the last integration steps, lab-based testing was done at the beginning of November 2025 between LINKS and BRE to verify the interoperability between the A22 Traffic Control Centre and Digital Twin, so that high quality DENM messages could be triggered by the RMT and then sent out by the ITS-G5 RSUs.

After this trial, one additional road test session in the Tusch tunnel was performed utilizing CRF CAV, with the aim to verify the whole integrated system.

The demonstration of UC5 was performed by means of video recordings, including one official demonstration video (snapshots in Figure 112), produced by A22 in collaboration with CRF and representing the technical work of all UC5 partners. The demo video was presented at the Italian LL event on 15.10.25 (Figure 113) and is available online.

Figure 112: Snapshots from the Podium UC5 demonstration video.

Figure 113: UC5 presentation at the Italian LL event.

In order to illustrate both technical and user experience details, additional video recordings of the road tests were utilized and shown at the event during CRF presentation, describing step by step what happens at the CAV in each scenario (Figure 114).

Figure 114: Step-by-step demonstration of scenarios.

Hereafter, the trials performed in each scenario after the debug phase, i.e. in the final configuration.

- Scenario 1: Road Works Warning applied to Cooperative ACC.
 - 1.1 Single CAV approaching roadworks, repeated 18 times.
 - 1.2 CAV and CV in car follow, repeated 13 times.
 - 1.3 CV cuts in, CAV gives way, repeated 13 times.
- Scenario 2: Traffic Jam Ahead Warning, one CAV, repeated 18 times.

- Scenario 3: AD Operational Design Domain in presence of Traffic Jam.
 - 3.1 Traffic Jam Alert, CV and CAV, ODD keep, repeated 14 times.
 - 3.2 Traffic Jam Alert, CV and CAV, ODD exit, repeated 13 times.

During the execution of the UC5 trials, multiple datasets were collected and stored in a repository.

Table 73 of the Annex outlines the whole set of logged parameters and the links to access them. This data has been collected in the logging points indicated in Figure 115 and following the guiding lines of D4.2 [4].

The dataset used for the computation of the KPIs is structured as follows:

- The logs for KPI_P_1-5 in UC5 are located in the folder UC5_KPI_P.
- The logs of CAV for KPI_UC5_1 and 3 are located in the folder UC5_DUT.
- The logs of RSU for KPI_UC5_2 are located in the folder UC5_KPI_2_RSU.

Figure 115: Logging points in the UC5's functional diagram according to D4.1 [4].

6.4. Trial Results

In this section, we present the results of the Test Cases proposed for UC3 in D5.1 [4]. The results have been obtained through analysis of the previous data sets.

6.4.1. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_1 Service Availability in UC5

The percentage of time that the different services are up and functioning with respect to the observation time. It measures the availability of the devices and their software together. For UC5 it represents the time of activity of the DT with respect to the total run time.

Method of calculation

Tests were conducted on 6.11.25, using the complete asset configuration: CAV, RSUs, sensors and Cloud DT. All DT logs were captured and stored in the cloud for subsequent analysis. As no logs were captured in the RSU during the test, only the DT availability was calculated during the tests.

A Python script was developed to automatically detect message exchange gaps in the recorded logs. The script reads each log file line by line, extracts and parses message timestamps, and calculates the time difference between consecutive timestamps. Any gap exceeding the defined threshold of 25.0 seconds is flagged as a potential communication failure. The threshold is the minimum time for log lines produced in the DT. Two sets of continuous tests were performed.

Table 52: TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability in UC5			
Materials used	Digital Twin - Risk Manager service log			
KPI	KPI_P_1 serviceAvailability in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Total Availability	Non-Availability Gaps	Overall Availability
	2	3 h	0 s	100%

Conclusions

The overall DT service availability is optimal, maintaining 100% uptime throughout testing with no service interruptions. This metric was calculated across 2 complete UC5 test runs utilizing the full system architecture: a CAV, a RSU, the C-ITS message exchange system, 5G network, and SEN.

6.4.2. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_2 Update Latency in UC5

The UC5 the update latency represents the delay of a CPM message from the RSU to the DT,

Method of calculation

The calculation has been done as in UC4, using logs from Cloud DT and from the RSU, messages timestamps were corrected since the RSU had a clock dealignment with respect to the DT. Deltas are then calculated, characterized and then plotted.

Table 53: TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency in UC5			
Materials used	Digital Twin			
KPI	KPI_P_2 updateLatency in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	15970	32.07 ms	38 ms	8.97 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	277 ms	9 ms	[26, 55] ms	52 ms

Plot

Figure 116: Distribution of the update latency for UC5.

Conclusions

The times required for CPM messages to propagate from the RSU sensor to the DT is within the cloud access times, since the DT is in a cloud infrastructure and not in a 5G infrastructure MEC node. Given that the verification criterion matches the 95th percentile we can say that the target is met.

6.4.3. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_3 Notification Latency in UC5

The notification latency in this UC represents the time required for the DENMs to reach the vehicle. Notifications are not meant to be required in ms scale since the reaction time for this kind of applications is above the order of hundreds of milliseconds.

Method of calculation

In the case of UC5 no OBU provided by LINKS was present in the vehicle, so no OBU logs were present, but instead alternative tests were done with an equivalent OBU having access to the same cloud infrastructure via 4G, which is the default on the road.

Table 54: TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency			
Materials used	Cloud Digital Twin, OBU			
KPI	KPI_P_3 notificationLatency in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	144	209 ms	177.5 ms	109.4 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	451 ms	48 ms	[66.5, 414.4] ms	406 ms

Conclusions

The values are very variable as the standard deviation suggests; this is expected since the transport of messages happens over public network over high mobility on a highway scenario. The delay required by this kind of application allows this variability, the target validation criterion matches the delay calculated.

6.4.4. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_4 Processing Delay in UC5

The processing delay is the amount of time required for the Risk Management in Tunnel (RMT) to complete a calculation of the risk status of the tunnel based on the current available information in the DT.

Method of calculation

In the UC5 the RMT logs were used to calculate this value, considering an input DENM coming from the road operator and the corresponding answer DENM with the modified status after calculating the updated risk status. Both logged messages are considered the start and end bounds of the processing time. Logs belong to the same host so both timestamps are synchronized.

Table 55: TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay			
Materials used	Cloud Digital Twin			
KPI	KPI_P_4 processingDelay in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	989	2.76 ms	3 ms	1.29 ms
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	8 ms	0 ms	[0, 5] ms	4.6 ms

Plot

Figure 117: Distribution of processingDelay for UC5.

It can be observed the concentration of the possible values on fixed millisecond ticks. This is due to the time resolution used, since all timestamps in logs were taken in milliseconds, and the small differences are conditioned by this resolution. However, the time can be characterized with the data available; sometimes even less than 1 ms is enough and sometimes 8 ms are required.

Conclusions

As for the processing delay in this use case, we can say that the delay in processing RMT status is satisfactory, since its reaction time is low even if the timing of UC5 applications is not critical. The target of 50 ms at most has been met.

6.4.5. Test Case for TC_KPI_P_5 Com Reliability in UC5

The communication reliability in the UC5 counts the number of ITS messages transferred effectively under the mobile channel to the vehicle, considering that some might be lost in the channel or in routing these messages at high level.

Method of calculation

Logs during the tests were captured of cloud and OBU, as considered in the KPI_P_3 calculated above. Both logs were matched by their first column and then verified that all messages were found in the destination. Only 144 messages were used since the UC5 risk management notifies DENMs to the vehicle with low periodicity.

Table 56: TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability in UC5		
Materials used	OBU, Cloud Digital Twin		
KPI	KPI_P_5 comReliability in UC5		
Descriptive Statistics	# Messages exchanged	# Messages lost	# Overall reliability
	144	0	100%

Conclusions

Considering the infrastructure in use, and the robustness of the protocols involved in the transmission of the messages, the overall reliability is of 100%. This is a natural consequence of the high-level protocols, which rely on TCP and their queue management. The transmissions might be affected by physical media but compensated by queuing in the higher protocols, as observed in notification delay. The KPI according to the validation criteria is passed.

6.4.6. Test Case for KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5

Accurate positioning is a fundamental requirement for V2X applications, particularly for cooperative assistive and automated functions such as C-ACC and lane-level warning systems. These applications depend on the vehicle's ability to determine its exact position on the road and, more importantly, within the correct lane.

A lateral accuracy of less than 1.5 meters is critical for lane-level awareness, enabling the vehicle to correctly interpret V2X messages such as lane closure information and make safe, context-aware decisions. This precision is essential for the ODD of highly automated driving systems.

In challenging environments such as tunnels, alternative positioning solutions (e.g., trilateration or localization solutions) must maintain sufficient accuracy to ensure continuity of service and safety.

Method of calculation

Positioning accuracy was evaluated by comparing the ground truth trajectory with the trajectory estimated by the developed positioning solution (Figure 118). The analysis was performed in a local reference frame, computing for each point the longitudinal and lateral residuals relative to the vehicle's direction of travel. The difference from the corresponding point on the ground truth trajectory was calculated and decomposed into:

- **Longitudinal error:** difference along the forward direction of travel.
- **Lateral error:** difference orthogonal to the forward direction, which is crucial for lane-level accuracy.

Figure 118: longitudinal and lateral residuals method, to assess the GNSS positioning error.

These following metrics provide a comprehensive view of system lateral performance, capturing both average accuracy and variability under different conditions. The positioning system relies on sensors and GNSS, but in the tunnel it works with the signals available (dead-reckoning).

Vehicle position accuracy: Inside tunnel

Table 57: TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral inside tunnel.

TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral				
TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral			
Materials used	Positioning inside tunnel: Sensors, GNSS			
KPI	KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	29191	7.4 cm	0.56 cm	26.8 cm
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	288.7 cm	0.0 cm	[0.02, 124.28] cm	56.93 cm

Table 58: TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal inside tunnel.

TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal				
TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal			
Materials used	Positioning inside tunnel: SENSORS, GNSS			
KPI	KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	29191	92.13 cm	71.57 cm	120.7 cm
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	770.6 cm	0.0 cm	[2.76, 364.2] cm	289.86 cm

Plots

Figure 119: Distribution and CDF of vehicle position accuracy lateral inside the tunnel for UC5.

Figure 120: Distribution and CDF of vehicle position accuracy longitudinal inside the tunnel for UC5.

Vehicle position accuracy: Outside tunnel with RTK corrections

Table 59: TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral outside tunnel with RTK corrections.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral outside tunnel with RTK corrections			
Materials used	Positioning inside tunnel: SENSORS, GNSS			
KPI	KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	333996	47.54 cm	23.23 cm	68.77 cm
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	740.21 cm	0.0 cm	[0.14, 296.7] cm	133.6 cm

Table 60: TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal outside tunnel with RTK corrections.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal outside tunnel with RTK corrections			
Materials used	Positioning inside tunnel: SENSORS, GNSS			
KPI	KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	333996	95.97 cm	96.15 cm	49.65 cm
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	617.09 cm	0.0 cm	[14.1, 197.3] cm	166.4 cm

Plots

Figure 121: Distribution and CDF of vehicle position accuracy lateral outside tunnel with RTK corrections for UC5.

Figure 122: Distribution and CDF of vehicle position accuracy longitudinal outside tunnel with RTK corrections for UC5.

Vehicle position accuracy: Outside tunnel without RTK corrections

Table 61: TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral outside tunnel without RTK corrections.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Lateral outside tunnel without RTK corrections			
Materials used	Positioning inside tunnel: SENSORS, GNSS			
KPI	KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	333996	69.5 cm	18.21 cm	118.62 cm
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	740 cm	0.0 cm	[1.8, 331.29] cm	304.24 cm

Table 62: TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal outside tunnel without RTK corrections.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5: Longitudinal outside tunnel without RTK corrections			
Materials used	Positioning inside tunnel: SENSORS, GNSS			
KPI	KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	333996	95 cm	95.28 cm	48.87 cm
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	488.16 cm	0.0 cm	[13.65, 195.02] cm	164.94 cm

Plots

Figure 123: Distribution and CDF of vehicle position accuracy lateral outside tunnel without RTK corrections for UC5.

Figure 124: Distribution and CDF of vehicle position accuracy longitudinal outside tunnel without RTK corrections for UC5.

For the lateral position, which is the most critical in our scenarios, we can see good shape of cumulative distribution function and good average values as a whole, which is what we experienced in the cooperative manoeuvres and hazard warning tests: the lane-level position was always good and suitable for the scenarios. However, in the graphs we see some anomaly cases, which broaden the confidence interval.

In tunnel positioning meets the target of 1.5m @2 sigma (95%) being 1.24 m the maximum value within the 95% confidence interval. Out of tunnel positioning does not meet the same target of 0.2 m @2 sigma, due to some cases in which the data fusion algorithm mismatched the lane-level positioning. The reason can be the fact that the highway A22 is in the middle of the mountains, with GNSS degradation, for which degraded GNSS caused noise in the data fusion algorithm. The difference of performance in tunnel with respect to the outside, can be due to the weighing factors of GNSS and sensors in the algorithm, whereby the sensors are predominant in tunnel. On the other hand, we have also to be cautious in the comparison, because the tool used for ground truth, another precise positioning system, had slightly different performance in tunnel with respect to outside.

Conclusions

The positioning solution of the connected vehicle must maintain lane-level accuracy under all operating conditions, including challenging environments such as tunnels, and regardless of the availability of RTK corrections. This requirement is fundamental to guarantee the reliability of safety-critical and cooperative V2X applications.

As confirmed by the KPI analysis, the lateral positioning error consistently remained within the lane-level threshold throughout the entire test campaign near the tunnels and inside the tunnels where driving scenarios were performed. It presented some degradation cases in the overall data acquisition.

This demonstrates the goodness of our solution to run cooperative and automated use cases also in GNSS-degraded conditions, thanks to the sensor-based positioning support, which yields precise localization even when RTK corrections are not available. The acquisitions went beyond the demo scenarios to gather as many data as possible for statistics. In some cases, the GNSS degradation was not properly compensated by the relative localization. This could be solved by further optimising the data fusion (weighing better GNSS and sensors). Overall, these cases did not affect the living lab demos.

During all tests, V2X applications operated seamlessly, without any functional disruptions or performance degradation, both in open-sky and tunnel conditions. This continuity of service highlights the high quality of the positioning system and its capability to support advanced connected vehicle use cases, ensuring safety and efficiency in real-world deployments.

6.4.7. Test Case for KPI_UC5_2 Vehicle_counting_accuracy in UCS

The vehicle counting accuracy measures the accuracy of the measurements of different types of vehicles with the RSU sensors, considering also the vehicle classification. The accuracy must be measured with respect to a precise reference counter.

Method of calculation

At the moment when the vehicle counting was to be measured, the logs from the ground-truth counters could not be aligned with the time periods during which the RSU sensor could be tested. In fact, the reference counters produced only full-day totals, whereas the RSU tests could be run for limited time windows. As a result, the reference counts and the test counts could not be directly compared.

To address this issue, the tests were performed using a set of recorded stream files. These streams were processed with the complete detection model running on an x86 machine in batch mode, which served as the reference counter. The test counting, instead, was executed with the embedded (compact) model designed to run on the RSU hardware, in fast real-time mode, acknowledging that some sensor frames might be skipped during Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) processing on the RSU.

Table 63: TC_KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy in UC5				
Materials used	RSU and a x86 powered desktop PC				
KPI	KPI_UC5_2 Vehicle_counting_accuracy in UC5				
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Count (all)	Count (Bus)	Count (PassenCar)	Count (Truck)
	12 runs	340	10	313	17
		Detection accuracy (all)	Detection accuracy (Bus)	Detection accuracy (PassenCar)	Detection accuracy (Truck)
		91.15%	100%	91.15%	81%

Conclusions

As remarked before, the vehicle counting produced output for different types of vehicles. The table shows an overall vehicle counting accuracy of 91.15% across 12 test runs. When analysing individual categories, passenger cars achieve a comparable accuracy of 91.15%, while buses reach 100%. However, the bus accuracy should be interpreted with caution due to the very limited sample size (of only 10 instances). This is given only to the rate at which buses can be seen on the road. Truck detection shows noticeably lower performance, with an accuracy of 81%, suggesting that the model may face greater challenges with heavier vehicles or that the available dataset might be less representative. In general, the distribution of samples is highly unbalanced, 313 passenger cars, compared to only 17 trucks and 10 buses, which limits the statistical robustness of class-specific metrics. Overall, the system demonstrates good performance, matching the 90% target for this KPI.

6.4.8. Test Case for KPI_UC5_3 Extended_perception_accuracy in UC5

This KPI evaluates the capability of the Sensor Fusion module to maintain accurate object tracking when combining on-board sensor detections with V2X information received through CPM (Figure 125). The focus is on assessing the impact of GNSS positioning degradation and V2V communication latency on the matching and tracking of objects detected by sensors versus those received via CPM. Reliable object fusion under these conditions is essential for cooperative perception and safety-critical applications. The target tolerance is set to <10% deviation between V2X-based and sensor-based object positions.

Figure 125: CAV merges detections received by the CV with its own detections.

Method of calculation

Tests were conducted under controlled conditions along the motorway (open sky) to ensure high GNSS accuracy for ground truth. The reference system used a Sensor Fusion module with RTK positioning

and V2V messages at 10 Hz. The algorithm under validation combines RTK with Dead Reckoning to compensate for GNSS degradation.

For both modules, the number of fused objects was monitored, and error time was calculated whenever mismatches occurred between the fused object counts of the two modules.

Precondition checks for KPI evaluation: V2V Communication Latency (CAM) and Measurement Age (CPM)

A precondition for KPI evaluation is to ensure that the data being analysed reflects the actual system behaviour under valid operating conditions. Communication latency (CAM) and measurement age (CPM) play a critical role in this because delayed data can distort the timing of events and lead to incorrect conclusions about system performance. Therefore, filtering out data with unacceptable latency is not just a matter of analytical rigor, it aligns the evaluation process with the actual logic of the application, ensuring that KPIs measure true performance rather than errors caused by stale inputs. In the following table the two measures are reported:

Table 64: Communication latency (CAM) (ms) versus Measurement Age (CPM) (ms).

	Communication Latency (CAM) [ms]	Measurement Age (CPM) [ms]
Nb samples	82170	82170
Mean	15.51	32.61
Median	16.19	32.97
Std	2.31	3.36
Max	18.88	39.15
Min	9.91	22.32
Lower bound (CI 95 th)	14.37	30.95
Upper bound (CI 95 th)	16.66	34.28
95th Percentile	18.24	37.35

As can be seen from the data, the latency (15 ms on average) over all the data as well as the measurement age (between 22 and 39 with 32 ms on average) are aligned with our expectations, so we could proceed with the evaluation of CPM compared to on board detections.

Performance Evaluation

The KPI was evaluated using error time, representing the duration for which the number of fused objects differed between the two modules (RTK vs RTK+DR). Table 65 shows the percentages of mismatch which represent the total error time for all samples between the two sensor fusion modules.

Table 65: TC_KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy in UC5.

TC Identifier	TC_KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy in UC5			
Materials used	CAV, CV, Sensors			
KPI	KPI_UC5_3 Extended_perception_accuracy in UC5			
Descriptive Statistics	# samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	82170	0.82%	0.32%	1.35%
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
	5.26%	0.04%	[0.15%, 0.97%]	4.08%

Table 66 explains across the 19 tests, the percentage error of the extended perception module relative to total test time.

Table 66: Percentage error of the Extended Perception module relative to total test duration across 19 test cases.

Total travelled time (s)	Error time on Extended Perception module (s)	Error (%)
108.50	1.05	0.97%
114.95	0.95	0.83%
250.85	1.60	0.64%
238.95	0.10	0.04%
213.00	0.25	0.12%
247.30	0.25	0.10%
152.40	0.15	0.10%
255.80	10.10	3.95%
180.80	0.20	0.11%
138.30	0.55	0.40%
291.90	0.80	0.27%
203.00	1.20	0.59%
114.35	0.10	0.09%
295.55	0.55	0.19%
585.95	1.90	0.32%
210.55	0.25	0.12%
160.00	1.95	1.03%
281.55	14.80	5.26%
64.75	0.25	0.39%

Plots

The KPI Extended Perception Accuracy shows very good performance overall. Across more than 82,000 samples, the average error is below 1%. In summary, the extended perception module demonstrates high reliability and stability, meeting accuracy expectations for cooperative perception scenarios.

Figure 126: Box plot illustrating the distribution of error percentages.

Analysis with GNSS degradation

A GNSS degradation scenario was simulated by introducing a constant positional offset of 4 meters, equivalent to the lane width on the A22 motorway, into the GNSS RTK signal used as ground truth. The analysis focused on the number of objects fused by the Sensor Fusion (SF) module under two conditions:

1. **Degraded GNSS:** Comparison of fused object counts using GNSS with a 4 m offset against the ground truth (RTK).
2. **Degraded GNSS with Dead Reckoning (DR):** Comparison of fused object counts using the degraded GNSS corrected by the DR algorithm against the ground truth.

The Dead Reckoning solution successfully mitigated the lateral error introduced by GNSS degradation, reducing it from 4 m to approximately 0.5 m relative to the ground truth, as Figure 127 shows.

Figure 127: Example of error between positioning solutions over time.

Table 67: Statistical comparison of positioning error between degraded GNSS and GNSS corrected with Dead Reckoning.

	Degraded GNSS	Degraded GNSS + DR solution
Nb samples	82170	82170
Mean	10.08%	0.51%
Median	9.34%	0.09%
Std	3.78%	1.21%
Max	18.38%	5.24%
Min	4.09%	0.00%
Lower bound (CI 95 th)	8.21%	-0.09%
Upper bound (CI 95 th)	11.95%	1.10%
95th Percentile	16.92%	2.31%

Table 67 summarizes the statistical evaluation performed for both tested solutions. Results indicate that the configuration using degraded GNSS alone fails to meet the defined target, while the integration of Dead Reckoning significantly improves performance by reducing positional error and enhancing object fusion consistency.

Table 68: Comparison of error time and percentage error between degraded GNSS and GNSS corrected with Dead Reckoning across 19 test cases.

Total travelled time (s)	GNSS Degraded		Degraded GNSS + DR solution	
	Error time (s)	Error (%)	Error time (s)	Error (%)
108.50	9.00	8.30%	0.05	0.05%
114.95	4.70	4.09%	0.05	0.04%
250.85	17.30	6.90%	1.20	0.48%
238.95	14.55	6.09%	0.10	0.04%
213.00	11.75	5.52%	0.20	0.09%
247.30	33.45	13.53%	0.00	0.00%
152.40	18.10	11.88%	1.25	0.82%
255.80	18.40	7.27%	5.05	1.99%
180.80	24.80	13.72%	0.25	0.14%
138.30	11.75	8.50%	0.00	0.00%
291.90	48.90	16.76%	0.50	0.17%
203.00	16.50	8.12%	0.35	0.17%
114.35	13.95	12.21%	0.00	0.00%
295.55	27.60	9.34%	0.00	0.00%
585.95	75.75	12.96%	1.25	0.21%
210.55	13.60	6.46%	0.35	0.17%
160.00	22.30	11.74%	0.05	0.03%
281.55	29.95	9.81%	16.00	5.24%
64.75	11.90	18.38%	0.00	0.00%

Analysis with varying CPM Reception Frequency

The impact of V2V reception frequency on the Sensor Fusion Module performance was analysed by progressively varying the V2V message reception period, with the aim of identifying the critical frequency at which the Sensor Fusion Module can no longer operate reliably. During this evaluation, the positioning input was provided by the GNSS RTK combined with Dead Reckoning, ensuring the absence of GNSS degradation and isolating the effect of V2V frequency variations on the sensor fusion process. As result, the critical frequency is about 3.3 Hz.

Figure 128: Impact of V2V message reception frequency on Sensor Fusion performance.

Conclusions

The evaluation confirms that the Sensor Fusion module achieves high accuracy under normal conditions, with an average error below 1%, meeting the KPI target. When GNSS degradation is introduced, performance drops significantly (mean error >10%), but the integration of Dead Reckoning effectively compensates for this. Additionally, the analysis of V2V message frequency shows that reliable operation is maintained down to approximately 3.3 Hz. Overall, the system demonstrates robustness and resilience, ensuring accurate object fusion and extended perception for cooperative driving scenarios.

6.5. Conclusions

In D2.1 [1] (page 16), we identified the following **potential needs**, which have been successfully addressed during the project's development:

- **Accurate risk quantification:** The system effectively assesses the risk level inside the tunnel by integrating multiple parameters, providing actionable insights for operators and automated systems.
- **Real-time data collection:** Sensors, vehicle data acquisition systems, and RSUs provide a reliable digital representation of the tunnel environment in real time.
- **Precise positioning:** Advanced positioning technologies coupled with on-board data fusion ensure accurate absolute positioning of vehicles within the tunnel, critical for navigation and safety functions.
- **Risk mitigation mechanisms:** The system can trigger warnings and CV can act upon them with risk-reducing manoeuvres automatically, enhancing operational safety.
- **Standards compliance:** Communication protocols and messaging align with ETSI C-ITS specifications, ensuring interoperability with connected vehicles and infrastructure.

To fulfil these needs, we anticipated several **potential challenges**, as outlined in D2.1 [1] (page 17), which have been effectively managed:

- **Data integration:** Multi-source data, including sensor and vehicle inputs, has been successfully fused to build a comprehensive digital twin of the tunnel environment.

- Accuracy of risk assessment: Dynamic risk evaluation considers multiple parameters, supported by robust data validation.
- Communication reliability: Stable and reliable communication between infrastructure, vehicles, and RSUs has been established, overcoming the challenging tunnel environment.
- Regulatory compliance: Originally the system should comply with Directive 2004/96/EC. During the project course, the test site was changed to a tunnel which is shorter than 500m, so this point is no longer a challenge.
- Infrastructure deployment: RSUs, sensors have been successfully deployed; positioning systems where only partially road tested on the pilot side due to some legal and technical constraint.

Overall, we have successfully achieved the **strategic goals** defined in D2.1 [1] (page 15). Below are the conclusions regarding their attainment, based on the results obtained so far

- Enhancing tunnel safety: Integration of real-time risk assessment improves overall tunnel safety by giving warning to CVs.
- Adaptive automation for CAVs: Risk quantification enables CAVs to adapt their automation level in advance, improving safety and efficiency
- Improve risk assessment: The system provides accurate and real-time information on tunnel risks, enhancing situational awareness using an innovative solution.
- Trustworthy communication: TPM-based solutions ensure secure and reliable communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and RSUs.

Finally, through the development of this use case, the project has accomplished the following **key technological advancements**.

Communications:

- Reliable in-tunnel C-V2X communication between infrastructure, vehicles, and RSUs.
- Secure and trustworthy communication protocols using Trusted Platform Module (TPM) technology.
- Compliance with ETSI C-ITS message standards for interoperability.

ITS applications:

- Real-time risk assessment system integrating multi-source data to generate a digital twin of the tunnel environment.
- Dynamic risk-level quantification enabling automated safety interventions.
- Context-aware warnings and risk-mitigating actions based on validated sensor and vehicle data, increasing the quality of the exiting C-ITS messages.

Autonomous vehicle:

- Precise in-tunnel vehicle positioning ensuring accurate navigation and automated control.
- Anticipated information for CAVs based on real-time tunnel risk levels.
- Integration with ITS systems enabling informed decision-making and enhanced safety in tunnels.
- Supported dynamic risk management strategies that can trigger automated responses in CAVs for lane changes or speed adjustments.
- On-board positioning system using dead reckoning based on maps and lane detection as well as V2I trilateration techniques for lane-level localization of the vehicle inside the tunnel, and GNSS with Real Time kinematics in open sky conditions.
- Development of a vehicle-based collective perception complying with ETSI standard and data fusion system to obtain extended perception even inside the tunnel.

- Integration of positioning system, V2I hazard warning and V2V collective perception and data fusion into CAV prototype for Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (C-ACC) and SAE L4 Operational Design Domain in tunnel scenarios.

Recommendations for the effective deployment of PoDIUM technologies

This section outlines the main recommendations and lessons drawn from the development and testing of the PoDIUM platform, highlighting practical considerations to support future deployments.

- Positioning systems based on V2I trilateration are highly dependent on the relative position of the roadside units. Along the highway, especially in tunnels there is little margin to install them.
- Our positioning system based on multiple sources was calibrated and optimized for the transition from open sky to the tunnel environment. Extensive tests along the A22 showed a good performance in these transition cases, but still some cases of moderate GNSS signal degradation happened, in environments characterized by narrow valleys. These cases, as well as the so-called urban canyons should be addressed when calibrating such a positioning system for production.
- Experiments on the data fusion of CPMs and sensors gave good results in the operational conditions of the Living Lab (10 CPM per second). Through simulations, possible degradation effects were evident when exchanging CPM less frequently (threshold of acceptable error found at around 3 CPM per second). Further studies should be performed, with different kind of data fusion systems involved, to consolidate the value of minimum frequency of CPM fulfilling the cooperative use cases.

7. Conclusions

The technical evaluation and large-scale demonstrations carried out across the PoDIUM Use Cases have confirmed the maturity, robustness and deployment potential of the proposed CCAM platform. Across urban, highway, tunnel and cross-border environments, the PoDIUM architecture has consistently proven its capability to integrate multi-connectivity communications, MEC-based edge processing, Digital Twin services and cooperative perception into a coherent and interoperable PDI. The overall results validate that the project objectives have been successfully achieved and that the developed solutions are ready to support advanced CCAM services in real traffic conditions.

A key outcome of the project is the demonstrated reliability and availability of hybrid communication architectures combining 5G, ad-hoc and C-V2X. In all operational environments, PoDIUM achieved near-continuous service availability with communication reliability exceeding 99% in urban scenarios and remaining robust also in highway and tunnel environments. The dual-radio approach proved essential for managing coverage gaps, roaming interruptions and heterogeneous network conditions. Edge processing on MEC nodes enabled end-to-end latencies ranging from sub-second to approximately 1.5 seconds depending on the service, which was sufficient to support time-critical applications such as emergency vehicle prioritisation, VRU collision warnings and automated cooperative manoeuvres. These performance figures clearly demonstrate that PoDIUM fulfils the stringent performance requirements of safety-critical CCAM services.

The cooperative perception framework implemented in PoDIUM has demonstrated robust and consistent benefits across a wide range of operational environments. The results confirm that both infrastructure-supported deployments and lightweight configurations relying exclusively on vehicle-based sensors can achieve reliable performance. By fusing data from connected vehicles, roadside sensors, AI-based video analytics and third-party traffic services, accurate and trustworthy Digital Twins were generated both at local and macroscopic levels. The LDM and TMC modules enabled reliable detection of hazards, congestion and VRU presence, and supported the generation of context-aware traffic strategies and safety warnings. In urban environments, the system successfully enhanced situational awareness in occluded areas and complex intersections, while on highways it enabled macroscopic traffic management and cross-border coordination. In more constrained environments, such as tunnels or areas with limited radio propagation, real-time digital representations of traffic and risk conditions were successfully maintained despite challenging communication and positioning conditions.

The project delivered measurable improvements in both safety and traffic efficiency. In urban emergency scenarios, PoDIUM increased the probability of emergency vehicles receiving green lights by more than 50% while reducing overall traffic disruption by over 53%. VRU protection services achieved safety margin improvements of approximately 45% and reduced deceleration intensity by around 33% in collision-risk scenarios. Cooperative traffic management functions enabled stable traffic flow and context-aware speed and distance recommendations on highways, showing strong potential for congestion mitigation. In environments with elevated safety risk, such as tunnels or dense urban intersections, real-time risk assessment and warning dissemination significantly enhanced operational safety for both human-driven and automated vehicles. These quantitative results confirm that PoDIUM delivers tangible benefits beyond conventional, non-cooperative traffic management approaches.

A major technical achievement of the project is the successful integration of CAVs into infrastructure-driven cooperative services. Fully automated SAE-L4 vehicles demonstrated 100% success rates in executing cooperative manoeuvres in controlled environments, including yielding to emergency vehicles, reacting to VRU warnings and performing fail-safe behaviours under connectivity loss. The demonstrations confirmed that infrastructure-generated perception and recommendations can be reliably interpreted and acted upon by automated driving systems, even in complex traffic situations. The use of open-source ETSI ITS protocol stacks proved to be especially valuable, enabling flexible integration across OBUs, RSUs, MEC servers, smartphones and simulators. This openness ensured full

control of the communication pipeline, facilitated debugging and significantly enhanced interoperability across heterogeneous platforms.

From a system-level perspective, PoDIUM validated a scalable and modular architecture based on distributed MEC nodes and coordinated TMCs. The "one MEC per road section" approach, combined with local and global traffic management logic, demonstrated strong scalability potential for nationwide or cross-border deployment. The successful exchange of traffic strategies and incident data between operators confirmed the feasibility of cooperative traffic management across administrative boundaries. At the same time, the trials revealed that regulatory and administrative barriers remain one of the main bottlenecks for large-scale deployment, particularly regarding experimental vehicle permits, insurance and cross-border testing of automated driving functions.

Several cross-cutting technological lessons were learned during the project. Hardware-based support for packet duplication and deduplication was shown to be essential for high-throughput multi-connectivity scheduling. While transport-layer solutions are effective for traffic steering and load balancing, redundancy scheduling for safety-critical services benefits significantly from hardware acceleration. Furthermore, the use of standardised ETSI messages as interfaces between infrastructure and vehicle components proved crucial for ensuring interoperability and simplifying system integration. Non-standardised message formats were found to complicate integration and long-term maintainability, especially when multiple stakeholders and platforms are involved.

Despite the high maturity reached, some limitations and areas for further improvement were identified. In dense urban environments and complex intersections, positioning accuracy was sometimes affected by GNSS degradation and minor inconsistencies in digital map models. In highway scenarios, system scalability under extreme message loads was not fully stress-tested. In constrained environments such as tunnels, further long-duration validation of positioning, sensing and communication solutions would strengthen confidence in large-scale deployment. These aspects do not compromise the validity of the results obtained, but they clearly define directions for future pilots and pre-commercial rollouts.

Based on the overall findings of the project, several recommendations can be formulated for future deployments of PoDIUM technologies and similar CCAM platforms. First, further optimisation of MEC processing pipelines and 5G Quality-of-Service mechanisms is recommended to reduce latency variability for time-critical safety services. Prioritisation of C-ITS traffic across the mobile core network should be systematically enforced. Second, EU-level regulatory harmonisation is urgently needed to enable efficient cross-border and large-scale testing of Connected and Automated Vehicles. Harmonised procedures for experimental vehicle registration, insurance and testing permits would remove major administrative barriers and accelerate real-world validation.

Third, strict adherence to ETSI standards and further standardisation of operator-to-operator interfaces is essential to ensure interoperability across Europe. Cooperative traffic management across borders will only be viable at scale if Global TMC data exchange interfaces are harmonised at European level. Fourth, resilient communication architectures based on dual 5G and C-V2X connectivity should be maintained and further extended, with strategic deployment of RSUs in roaming zones, coverage gaps and safety-critical locations. Fifth, the systematic use of high-definition maps and enhanced positioning technologies is strongly recommended to support Digital Twin accuracy and reliable location-dependent KPIs across all environments.

In addition, future large-scale pilots should explicitly include stress and scalability testing with high numbers of connected vehicles, sensors and cooperative services to validate MEC performance under extreme loads. The use of open-source ETSI ITS stacks should be encouraged to ensure long-term maintainability, transparency and flexibility of deployed systems. Finally, early and continuous involvement of road operators, municipalities, emergency services and regulators is essential to streamline operational integration, data governance and societal acceptance.

Overall, the PoDIUM project has successfully demonstrated that cooperative, multi-connectivity-based CCAM services are technically mature and capable of delivering significant safety and efficiency benefits in real traffic environments. The validated technologies provide a solid foundation for the next generation of intelligent, connected and automated mobility services in Europe. With targeted regulatory improvements, further large-scale validation and continued optimisation of edge computing and communication infrastructures, the PoDIUM platform is well positioned to move from pilot deployment towards pre-commercial and commercial operation.

8. References

- [1] PoDIUM, "D2.1 - PoDIUM use cases description and specifications", 2023.
- [2] PoDIUM, "D2.2 - PoDIUM platform requirements and specifications", 2023.
- [3] PoDIUM, "D3.3 - Final report on the PoDIUM platform developments", 2025.
- [4] PoDIUM, "D4.1 - Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLs and development of data collection tools", 2024.
- [5] PoDIUM, "D4.2 - PoDIUM LLs integration and pre-evaluation testing report", 2025.
- [6] PoDIUM, "D5.1 - PoDIUM evaluation methodology", 2024.
- [7] PoDIUM, "D6.4 - Std. activities, EU policies and regulations recommendations", 2025.
- [8] FESTA Handbook V8, September 2021. <https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/FESTA-Handbook-Version-8.pdf>.
- [9] ETSI TS 101 539-2 V1.1.1. Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); V2X Applications; Part 2: Intersection Collision Risk Warning (ICRW) application requirements specification, 2018-06.
- [10] FlexStack(R) Community Edition. 2025. <https://flexstack.eu> (Accessed: November 2025).
- [11] Instruction 1/2009, of February 10, 2009, of the Catalan Data Protection Agency, on the processing of personal data by cameras for video surveillance purposes.
- [12] Royal Decree 311/2022, of May 3, regulating the National Security Scheme / Real Decreto 311/2022, de 3 de mayo, por el que se regula el Esquema Nacional de Seguridad.

9. Annex 1: Logged data

Table 69: UC1's logged data repository links.

Files in the dataset	
Log folder/file	Link to the repository
UC1_KPI_1_CAV	https://zenodo.org/records/17232171
UC1_KPI_2_VRU	
UC1_KPI_3	
UC1_KPI_P1_P4	
UC1_KPI_P2	
UC1_KPI_P3_P5	

Table 70: UC2's logged data repository links.

Files in the dataset	
Log data type	Link to the repository
UC2_TMS_Strategy	https://zenodo.org/records/17986728
UC2_VRU_Risk management	
UC2_CITS_Gateway	
UC2_CAV	

Table 71: UC3's logged data repository links.

Files in the dataset	
Log data type	Link to the repository
UC3_KPI_P1-ServiceAvailability	https://zenodo.org/records/17979993
UC3_KPI_P2-UpdateLatency	
UC3_KPI_P3-NotificationLatency	
UC3_KPI_P4-NotificationLatency	
UC3_KPI_P5-ComReliability	
UC3_KPI_1-ServiceTime	
UC3_KPI_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime	
UC3_KPI_3-ShuttleSpeed	
UC3_KPI_4-TrafficStragegiesImplementation	

Table 72: UC4's logged data repository links.

Files in the dataset	
Log data type	Link to the repository
UC4_KPI_P_1-5	https://zenodo.org/records/17986399
UC4_KPI_P_6-9	
UC4_KPI_1_CAV	
UC4_KPI_2_OBU	
UC4_KPI_3_CAV	
UC4_KPI_4_MEC	

Table 73: UC5's logged data repository links.

Files in the dataset	
Log data type	Link to the repository
UC5_KPI_P	https://zenodo.org/records/17986658
UC5_DUT	
UC5_KPI_2_RSU	

10. Annex 2: KPI's definitions and Test Cases to assess them

This annex provides aggregated tables of the updated version of the PoDIUM KPIs, as outlined in Annex 1 of deliverable D5.1 [4], along with the specifications of the Test Cases (TC) used to assess them, in accordance with chapters 4 and 5 of the same deliverable D5.1.

Table 74: KPI_P_1 Service availability.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability
Description	Service Availability, percentage of time the service is working with respect to the observation time. Evaluated during demonstrations/experiments.
Context / Use Case	Platform. Applies to all computing entities that run services within use cases.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Logging/monitoring of services is necessary to know where the services are down and for how long. A set of acceptable causes of outages might be necessary, such as power outage, maintenance windows, etc. Monitoring might be done externally to services and every service is evaluated individually.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sum up of all the unacceptable outage time in logs. Obtain the elapsed time of the experiment/demo (observation time). Calculate the service percentage.
How to Evaluate	Target Value range: Service Availability > [95%, 99.5%].
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_1_serviceAvailability
Test purpose	Obtain measurements to calculate service availability.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during other tests executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Logs should contain a line every 10 seconds of the service working.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When other tests or demos are running, every service involved should emit logs while running. Logs are obtained and stored at the end of the test. The logs should be processed to obtain the amount of outage time, accumulating the time slots reported in the log and the time of the missing slots or time of unacceptable outage.
Verification criteria	The result availability percentage for service <i>i</i> is: $R_i (\%) = (1 - \text{outageTime}/\text{observationTime}) * 100$ If the mean R for all services is \geq KPI target value then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 75: KPI_P_2 Update latency.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_2-updateLatency
Description	Latency of update messages to the DT with sensors/collective perception/data. It is the time gap between the event detection and its availability in a service DT (in cloud or MEC servers).
Context / Use Case	Platform. Applies to every update (in uplink), such as VRU crossing with incoming vehicle, sensor information updating digital twins.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In MEC or Cloud computing entities.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensors record timestamped events, such as road events, (i. e., the incoming of an emergency vehicle in UC2, or irregular crossing of VRU in UC4, or dangerous goods detection on UC5). The delays must be calculated between the nearest point of detection of the event and its reception timestamps into the MEC/Cloud DT that receives this data. A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance over all the measurements represents the KPI value.
How to Evaluate	The target values depend on the particular UC, since more responsive times are required for certain situations such as manoeuvre coordination and less responsive for traffic management. Target value range: Update Latency < [50ms, 2.5s].
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency
Test purpose	Obtain measurements to calculate update latency of the platform.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during other tests executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Two log entries, one that identifies the detection of the event (possibly with the timestamp of detection in the past) and another log entry that declares its input into the DT. The first log entry is taken in the nearest point of detection; the second is in the nearest point of consumption in DT.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When other tests or demos are running, the sensor software logs every single detection event with its the detection time. Correspondingly, the DT interface in input will log the detection input. Logs are collected. The detection and digital twin input messages should be correlated in the logs, perhaps by a join field to process both logs together.
Verification criteria	The calculation of the CDF of the all the time deltas (DT timestamp – detection timestamp) and obtain the 95% percentile. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 76: KPI_P_3 Notification latency.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_3-notificationLatency
Description	Latency of notification messages from a service in the platform (MEC, Cloud) to arrive to its final consumer (CV, VRU).
Context / Use Case	Platform. Any time gap from the generation of a warning/notification/indication to the final provision of indication to the CV, CAV, VRU.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In MEC/Cloud computing entities and message consumers (CV, VRUs, etc).
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse the messages generated within computing entities in the edge or cloud and those received in messages consumers. Notification transmission and consumption timestamps are recorded. The time gap between these two timestamps are the notification latency values. The consumption might occur in ADAS ECU, HMI, or Mobile terminal for VRUs. A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance over all the measurements represents the KPI value.
How to Evaluate	The target values depend on the particular UC. Target value range: Notification Latency < [50ms, 2.5s].
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency
Test purpose	Obtain measurements to calculate the latency of the platform to notify a road user regarding a road event.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during other tests executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Two log entries, one that identifies the end of the computation of a notification message (DENM, IVIM, CPM) and another log entry that records its reception in the road user (CAV or VRU). The first log entry is taken in the nearest point of computation; the second is in the nearest point of consumption in the road user.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The output of the final C-ITS application must be logged and also the CAV / VRU OBUs. Both log entries should be identified and, then, their timestamps are used to calculate the time deltas for every notification produced.
Verification criteria	The calculation of the CDF of the all the time deltas (Road User timestamp - notification generation timestamp) and obtain the 95% percentile. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 77: KPI_P_4 Processing delay.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_4-processingDelay
Description	The processing time required between event (obstacle, VRU, road event) detection and the CCAM message availability for CAV to action, without accounting for transport delay.
Context / Use Case	Platform, in scenarios where road events are detected, processed and transmitted to generate vehicle actions/notifications on CAVs, CVs and VRUs. It measures how fast the PDI generates notifications based on existing information, to be communicated to and consumed by users.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Within processing entities where the inputs from the road side are received and processed to produce an output notification.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Timestamps during processing in services are necessary, that is, the timestamp when the triggering event was received by MEC/Cloud service and the timestamp of the warning/response/manoeuvre indication generated. These time delays do not count delay due to transport. A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance over all the measurements represents the KPI value.
How to Evaluate	The target values depend on the particular UC, since more responsive times are required for certain situations such as manoeuvre coordination and less responsive for traffic management. Target value range: Processing Delay < [50ms, 2.5s].
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay
Test purpose	Obtain the measurements to calculate the latency of the platform to generate a notification as a result of a road event.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during other tests executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Two log entries are required in the final C-ITS application in MEC or cloud. Ideally the second and first log entries of TC_KPI_P_2 and 3 respectively are enough, since they contain the timestamps that determine time passed between the detection of an event and the corresponding notification generated. Both messages are required to be linked by a join field that correlates the event with its notification and so both logs are joint together.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The output of the final C-ITS application must be logged and also the CAV / VRU OBUs. Both log entries should be identified and then their timestamps are used to calculate the time deltas for every notification produced.
Verification criteria	The calculation of the CDF of the all the time deltas (Road User timestamp - notification generation timestamp) and obtain the 95% percentile. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 78: KPI_P_5 Communication reliability.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_5-comReliability
Description	Communication message reliability. It describes how reliable is the PDI to deliver the messages to the users/vehicles/VRUs.
Context / Use Case	Platform, in scenarios where redundant messages are sent with the same information in order to reach the target users/vehicles, and vice versa (from sensors/vehicles to edge/cloud).
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In vehicles, and computing entities sending and receiving CCAM messages.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Logging the sending and reception of CCAM messages and comparing the amount of them with the sent messages for every sensor/RSU/vehicle/computing entity. A maximum value [or 95% percentile of acceptance] over all the measurements represents the KPI value. It requires that endpoints are logging input and output CCAM messages and be able to identify them uniquely on both ends.
How to Evaluate	<p>The target values depend on the particular UC, since different reliability times are required for certain critical or non-critical situations.</p> <p>Target value range: Communication Reliability > [90%, 99.99%]</p>
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability
Test purpose	Obtain the measurements to estimate how much reliable is the platform relaying messages between interfaces.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during use case executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are running.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>For the most critical interfaces in the system, a logging should be performed at both sides of the interface.</p> <p>Both messages are required to be linked by a join field that correlates the outgoing and incoming message in the interface.</p>
Test procedure sequence	All messages matched in both logs are counted and all messages not matched at all are counted too. This is done for every use case run.
Verification criteria	The ratio between received messages and sent messages is calculated. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 79: KPI_P_6 Sealed object.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_6-SealedObject
Description	This KPI represents the capability of the platform to protect sensible data/objects through the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) and its sealing/unsealing features.
Context / Use Case	Platform, in UCs where security is implemented.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In OBUs and RSUs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once the developers of the applications have defined the files to be protected, i.e., encrypted with a symmetric key stored into the TPM, the KPI is observed directly in OBUs and RSUs. Sealed objects must be decrypted and used by applications running in OBUs and RSUs only in trusted states.
How to Evaluate	Testing the sealing and unsealing functions in different trusted and untrusted states. It must be possible to decrypt them for use only in trusted states. Target value: Successful tests percentage > 99%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_6-SealedObject
Test purpose	This test measures the capability of the platform to protect sensible data/objects through the TPM and its sealing/unsealing features.
Pre-test conditions	Having defined a trusted status and one or more sensitive files to be unsealed.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	For each test, an entry defines the status of the system during that test (trusted or untrusted) and the result of unsealing (success or failure).
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For each test, the status of the system (trusted or untrusted) is logged, and a protected file is unsealed. If this operation is successful, 'success' is logged, otherwise 'failure' is logged. The test is repeated several times with different system status.
Verification criteria	It must be possible to unseal with success only in trusted state so, the unsealing success rate for trusted status is: $R_{\text{unsealing_trusted_state}} (\%) = (1 - \text{failTrust}/\text{numTrust}) * 100$ and unsealing success rate for untrusted status is: $R_{\text{unsealing_untrusted_state}} (\%) = (1 - \text{succUntrust}/\text{numUntrust}) * 100$ numTrust = Number of tests with trusted system failTrust = Number of failures in tests with trusted system numUntrust = Number of tests with untrusted system succUntrust = Number of successes in tests with untrusted system If both $R_{\text{unsealing_trusted_state}}$ and $R_{\text{unsealing_untrusted_state}}$ are \geq than the KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 80: KPI_P7 Load boot time.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime
Description	This KPI evaluates the boot time with and without the Software Integrity Architecture (SIA).
Context / Use Case	Platform, in UCs where software integrity is implemented.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In OBUs and RSUs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This KPI is measured by taking the boot time of an OBU and a RSU during all steps of the Bootstrap. The start time is defined by the act of power on and the end time by the OS login screen.
How to Evaluate	Evaluation is performed by comparing the boot time with and without SIA and then calculating the difference in percentage. Target value: Boot time increase < 30%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime
Test purpose	Measurements taken to evaluate the additional bootstrap time due to the SIA.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done starting with the platform switched off.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The boot time of the platform.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Starting with the platform switched off. The timer is started at the same time as the platform is switched on (e.g. by pressing the power button) and is stopped when the OS login screen is reached. The test is performed with and without SIA.
Verification criteria	<p>The result percentage is:</p> $R (\%) = ((\text{bootTime_with_SIA} - \text{bootTime_without_SIA}) / \text{bootTime_without_SIA}) * 100$ <p>bootTime_with_SIA = Bootstrap time of the platform with the SIA bootTime_without_SIA = Bootstrap time of the platform the without the SIA</p> <p>If R is ≤ than the KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 81: KPI_P_8 Load run time.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime
Description	This KPI evaluates the additional CPU utilization and memory consumption due to the Software Integrity Architecture (SIA).
Context / Use Case	Platform, in UCs where software integrity is implemented.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In OBUs and RSUs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	This KPI is measured by running OBU and RSU common applications/services and recording the CPU load and memory consumption in the two configurations.
How to Evaluate	<p>Comparing CPU load and memory consumption with and without the SIA.</p> <p>CPU load in percentage and memory consumption in percentage and in bytes or multiples.</p> <p>Target values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difference in CPU load < 10%. • Difference in memory consumption < 20%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime
Test purpose	Measurements taken to evaluate the additional CPU utilization and memory consumption due to the SIA.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during normal operation of the device.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Logs of the CPU load in percentage and memory consumption in bytes or multiples
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The platform runs its common applications/services while logging the CPU load in percentage and memory consumption in bytes or multiples. • The test is performed with and without the SIA.
Verification criteria	<p>The result percentage for the CPU load is R_CPU and the memory consumption percentage is:</p> $R_mem = ((mem_with_SIA - mem_without_SIA) / mem_without_SIA) * 100$ <p>mem_with_SIA = Memory consumption of the platform with the SIA mem_without_SIA = Memory consumption of the platform without the SIA</p> <p>If both R_CPU and R_mem are ≤ than their KPI target values the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 82: KPI_P_9 Remote attestation.

KPI Identifier	KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation
Description	The Performance of the Remote Attestation protocol.
Context / Use Case	Platform, in UCs where software attestation is implemented.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In RSUs and MEC.
How to observe/measure/monitor	This KPI evaluates the performance of the Remote Attestation protocol as the latency between the start of communication between two nodes and the end of the protocol by calculating the time in seconds.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Protocol latency < 3s.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation
Test purpose	Measurements taken to calculate the performance of the Remote Attestation protocol.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during normal operation of the device.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Log entries with the duration of the Remote Attestation measured on the Verifier side.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The attestation software measures the duration in seconds from the beginning of the Remote Attestation protocol to its end. The test is repeated several times to reach statistical relevance.
Verification criteria	If the mean duration R is \leq than the KPI target value the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 83: KPI_UC1_1 CAV cooperative manoeuvre.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV
Description	The CAV on the blocked lane is able to pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre.
Context / Use Case	UC1.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At the German living lab.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Qualitative evaluation of the traffic flow of the use case. An expert marks one pass through the UC as successful or not.
How to Evaluate	Calculate the percentage of passes considered successful over the total. Target value: Successful passes percentage > 75%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV
Test purpose	Test if the CAV is able to successfully pass a blockage while another CAV approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of autonomous driving trials. The traffic is flowing normally on both lanes. All PoDIUM functions run normally. Then, a lane blockage is detected and a CAV needs to pass this blockage while another CAV approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The CAVs have successfully passed the blockage. An expert or a group of experts mark the test run as either successful or not.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that all pre-test conditions are fulfilled. The two CAVs approach the blockage in such a way that the cooperative planner initiates a cooperative manoeuvre. The two CAVs pass the blockage according to the received manoeuvre. The expert or a group of experts compare the test run against the expected result. Repeat the test at least five times. Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).
Verification criteria	Divide the number of successful test runs by the number of total test runs. If the result is > than 75% the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL..

Table 84: KPI_UC1_2 VRU cooperative manoeuvre.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU
Description	The VRU on the free lane is able to pass the obstacle in a complex traffic situation without getting into a dangerous situation. Additionally, the CAV on the blocked lane is able to pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre.
Context / Use Case	UC1.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At the German living lab.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Qualitative evaluation of the traffic flow of the use case. An Expert marks one pass through the UC as successful or not.
How to Evaluate	Calculate the percentage of passes considered successful over the total. Target value: Successful passes percentage > 75%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU
Test purpose	Test if the CAV is able to successfully pass a blockage while a connected VRU approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of autonomous driving trials. • The traffic is flowing normally on both lanes. • All PoDIUM functions run normally. • Then, a lane blockage is detected and a CAV needs to pass this blockage while a connected VRU approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The VRU on the free lane has passed the obstacle without getting into a dangerous situation. Additionally, the CAV on the blocked lane has passed the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre. An expert or a group of experts mark the test run as either successful or not.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that all pre-test conditions are fulfilled. 2. The CAV and VRU approach the blockage in such a way that the cooperative planner initiates a cooperative manoeuvre. 3. The two CAV pass the blockage according to the received manoeuvre. 4. The expert or a group of experts compare the test run against the expected result. <p>Repeat the test at least five times. Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>Divide the number of successful test runs by the number of total test runs.</p> <p>If the result is > than 75% the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 85: KPI_UC1_3 Cooperative manoeuvre MultiConnectivity.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-MultiC
Description	A scheduler can successfully make use of all currently available communication technologies to ensure communication between the Server and a CAV by redundancy.
Context / Use Case	UC1.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At the German living lab.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Quantitative evaluation of the impact of redundancy on the reliability of packet transmission.
How to Evaluate	Calculate the percentage of packets given as input to the Multi-Connectivity scheduler and hence transmitted through duplication over all heterogeneous communication technologies that are not successfully received at the MEC.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Manoeuvre-MultiC
Test purpose	Test if the Multi Connectivity scheduler can make use of all available communication technologies through duplicating packets for transmission at the sender and deduplication at the receiver.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of autonomous driving trials. • The traffic is flowing normally on both lanes. • All PoDIUM functions run normally. • Then, a lane blockage is detected and a CAV needs to pass this blockage while another CAV approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>The Multi-Connectivity Scheduler receives the packets to be transmitted, duplicates these and transmits a copy on every available communication technology. The scheduler on the receiver side matches arriving packets for deduplication and transmits only the first copy of every packet further to the receiver.</p> <p>An expert or a group of experts mark the test run as either successful or not if duplication and deduplication was successful with a success threshold of 95% of the sent packets.</p>
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that all pre-test conditions are fulfilled. 2. The two CAVs approach the blockage in such a way that the cooperative planner initiates a cooperative manoeuvre. 3. The two CAVs pass the blockage according to the received manoeuvre. 4. The expert or a group of experts compare the test run against the expected result. <p>Repeat the test (here 62 times).</p>
Verification criteria	Divide the number of successful test runs by the number of total test runs. If the result is > than 95% the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 86: KPI_UC2_1 Traffic light flow improvement.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement
Description	Percentage of times that Emergency Vehicles (EVs) find green light when they arrive at a controlled intersection.
Context / Use Case	UC2. Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	EV. TMS or DT.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the logs of the EVs tracking functionality made by EV with the data for the status of traffic lights at each instant provided by TMS.
How to Evaluate	<p>Calculation of the percentage of times that the traffic light is green when EVs reach a junction with and without the connected EV tracking functionality.</p> <p>Calculate the improvement of the percentage when using the new functionality with respect of when not using it.</p> <p>Target value: Improvement with regards to tests without implementing the new functionality > 25%.</p>
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement
Test purpose	Measure the improvement in the percentage of times that EVs find green light when they arrive at a controlled intersection caused by the improvement of EV priority management applied within UC2.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. • EV with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed. • PoDIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation). • Data model of the emergency corridor provided.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The EV finds green at its arrival to intersections and crossed them without stopping nor significantly reduce its speed.
Test procedure sequence	<p>With the PoDIUM service enabled:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The EV initiates a trip along the corridor and notifies the PoDIUM enhanced priority management service. 2. The EV sends CAM messages to the PoDIUM platform informing about its position and speed. 3. The EV priority management service estimates the arrival time at each intersection, using the position received from the EV to improve the estimation. 4. The EV priority management activates priority for the EV at the traffic controllers with a reasonable anticipation to the estimated arrival of the EV to the intersection. 5. The EV arrives at and crosses each intersection. 6. Logs are collected to check the time and speed of the EV when arriving to the intersection. If available, the state of traffic lights at each time obtained from the local controller will be also collected.

	<p>7. The percentage of trips in which the EV crossed the intersection without stopping or reducing speed significantly and (if available) with green light is calculated.</p> <p>Baseline:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The EV initiates a trip along the corridor and notifies the legacy priority management service. 2. The EV sends CAM messages to the PoDIUM platform informing about its position and speed. 3. Several beacons installed along the corridor are activated while the vehicle passes besides them. 4. The EV priority management system estimates arrival time at intersections using only the beacon activation and a pre-configured speed profile. CAM messages are ignored. 5. The EV priority management activates priority for the EV at the traffic controllers. 6. The EV arrives at and crosses each intersection. 7. Logs are collected to check the time and speed of the EV when arriving to the intersection. If available, the state of traffic lights at each time obtained from the local controller will be also collected. 8. The percentage of trips in which the EV crossed the intersection without stopping or reducing speed significantly and/or (if available) with green light is calculated. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>The increase of the percentage of trips in which the EV finds green (and/or crosses without stopping nor reducing speed) with regards to the percentage measured for baseline tests:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very good: Increase between [100%, 10%). Good: Increase between [10%, 5%): Good. Fair: Increase between [5%, 2%). Bad: Increase between [2%, 0%).

Table 87: KPI_UC2_2 Trips between Origin and Destination computation.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD
Description	Percentage of trips for which the Origin and Destination (O-D) is correctly processed by TMS.
Context / Use Case	UC2. Calculation of O-D matrices.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	CVs (or CAVs). TMS O-D calculation module.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the timestamps of the beginnings and ends of trips at CVs with the logs of the TMS. Calculate the percentage of trips correctly processed.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Percentage of trips correctly processed > 95%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD
Test purpose	Calculate the percentage of trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS when generating O-D matrix data.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have the necessary permits for execution of trials. • O-D zones modelled. • CVs with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed. • PoDIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation).
Expected result (conformance requirements)	O-D matrix data are generated per time period, consistent with the trips made by connected vehicles.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connected vehicles conduct as many trips as possible, during the test period and across the pilot demonstration area, from different origins and destinations. 2. CVs send CAM messages to the PoDIUM platform informing about their position and speed. 3. The PoDIUM service for traffic metrics generation receives the information, detects the beginning and end of each trip, stores the anonymises the data, aggregates them per time period and generates an O-D matrix per period. 4. Logs are collected to check the time and location of the beginning and end of each trip. They are processed and compared with the generated O-D to check consistency. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	If the percentage of trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS is > 95% then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 88: KPI_UC2_3 Trip's delay computation.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay
Description	Percentage of travel times across road links correctly processed.
Context / Use Case	UC2. Calculation of average delays and travel times across road links and/or crossing intersections.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	CVs (or CAVs). TMS O-D calculation module.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the timestamps of the passing of through reference CVs with the logs of the TMS. Calculate the percentage of trip's delays correctly processed.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Percentage of trip's delays correctly processed > 95%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay
Test purpose	Calculate the percentage of travel times across road links correctly processed.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • City data model available. • CVs with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed. • PoDIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation).
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Average travel time and delay per road junction data are generated per time period, consistent with the trips made by connected vehicles.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connected vehicles conduct as many trips as possible, during the test period and across the pilot demonstration area, from different origins and destinations. 2. CVs send CAM messages to the PoDIUM platform informing about their position and speed. 3. The PoDIUM service for traffic metrics generation receives the information, tracks their movement along road segments, calculates the travel time and delay, stores them, anonymises the data, aggregates it per time period and generates metrics per time period (average travel time, average speed, average and accumulated delay). 4. Logs are collected to check the time and location of the beginning and end of each trip. They are processed and compared with the generated travel time to check consistency. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	If the percentage of trips along road segments for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS is > 95% the test then is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 89: KPI_UC2_4 EV priority impact on traffic reduction.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction
Description	Reduction of the extra red traffic light times for movements transversal to the EV corridor caused by guard times.
Context / Use Case	UC2. Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	EV. TMS or DT.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the logs of the EVs tracking functionality made by EV with the data for the status of traffic lights at each instant provided by TMS, particularising on guard times at intersections.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Reduction of the extra red traffic light times $\geq 25\%$.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction
Test purpose	Measure the reduction of the extra red traffic light times for movements transversal to the EV corridor caused by guard times of the management of priority for EV.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least fair results of KPI_UC2_1 should have been previously obtained with long guard times. Guard times configuration reduced.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	By improving the accuracy of the estimation of the arrival time of EV at intersections, it is expected that less guard time will be required and crossing vehicles and pedestrians will have to stop less time at read lights.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repetition of the same tests described for TC_KPI_UC2_1, but with configuring progressively reduced guard times, until the KP_UC2_1 becomes affected. This iteration process should be done for both the baseline and with the PoDIUM service enabled. For each repetition, it is necessary to calculate the duration of the priority for EV activation interval at each intersection, subtract the standard travel time for the EV at the entering road segment (length / standard speed), multiplied by the proportion of green time per cycle for transversal roads in a reference traffic plan. Calculate the average of this value for, on one side, the baseline tests, and for the tests with the PoDIUM service enabled.
Verification criteria	If the percentage of reduction is $\geq 25\%$ the test then is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 90: KPI_UC2_5 EV successful cooperative manoeuvres.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_5-EV_successful_coop_manoeuvre_percentage
Description	Percentage of coincidences for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV.
Context / Use Case	UC2. Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Traffic Management System/MEC logs and vehicle On-Board Unit logs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Collecting logs from the PoDIUM service (MEC/Gateway) to confirm the DENM warning message was sent, and CAV/CV logs (HMI/OBU) to confirm the message was correctly displayed or the manoeuvre was executed by the CAV.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Percentage of coincidences $\geq 95\%$.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_5-EV_successful_coop_manoeuvre_percentage
Test purpose	Calculation of the percentage of coincidences for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • City data model available. • CAVs/CVs with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed. • PoDIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation). • Data model of the emergency corridor provided. • EV with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed. • The planned routes of CAVs/CVs for the demo should include some common road segments with pre-defined EV corridors, and be timed to facilitate the coincidence of EVs and CAVs/CVs in some of the road segments.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Each time an EV moves has to overtake a CAV or CV at a road segment, the PoDIUM service sends a DENM warning message, that is correctly displayed to the driver (for CVs) or causes the CAV to execute a manoeuvre to facilitate the EV passing.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CV/CVs start their trips across the demo area. 2. EV starts its trip along one emergency corridor. 3. Coincidence of EV and some CAVs/CVs in the same road segment at the same time occurs during the trip, having the EV to overtake the CAV /CV. 4. Before such coincidence happens the PoDIUM should have sent a DENM message to the CAVs/CVs of interest. 5. CAV should execute a cooperative manoeuvre autonomously. 6. A warning should be displayed in HMI of CV, requesting the driver to execute a cooperative manoeuvre. 7. Analysis of logs from the EV, the CAV/CVs and the service. Detection of the events of coincidence of an EV and a CAV or CV at the same road segment. 8. Observation of the HMI of CV or CAV (check when warnings is displayed). 9. Observation of the response by CAV to the reception of the warning.

	Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).
Verification criteria	If the percentage of coincidences for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV is $\geq 95\%$ then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 91: KPI_UC2_6 VRU collision risk reaction time reduction.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_6-VRU_collision_risk_reaction_time_reduction
Description	Reduction of the response time by CV/CAVs when there is high risk of collision with a VRU.
Context / Use Case	UC2. VRU protection.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Collision Risk Estimator logs (MEC/edge local video processor). CAV/CV On-Board Unit (OBU) logs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Collecting logs from the CRE to identify the high risk of collision events and the time of alert transmission. Collecting speeds, positions, and acceleration logs from CAVs/CVs to measure the time/distance remaining when the driver/automation reacted.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Reduction of the response time > 20%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_6-VRU_collision_risk_reaction_time_reduction
Test purpose	Calculate the average reduction of the response time by CV/CAVs when there is high risk of collision with a VRU.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UC partners have the necessary permits for execution of trials. CAVs/CVs with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed (OBU). PoDIUM equipment installed in the intersection, including a RSU and an Edge computer with PoDIUM software installed (including the Collision Risk estimation functionality). Cameras with AI functionality for VRU detection installed at the intersection pointing to the potential collision risk areas between vehicles and VRUs.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Each time an event of high risk of collision between a CAV or CV and a VRU is predicted, a DENM messages is received by the vehicle, and the vehicle reduces its speed a significant time interval before the arrival to the potential collision location.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> CAV/CVs moves towards the intersection at a speed near the maximum permitted. The CAV/CV sends CAM messages periodically, informing about its position and speed. A VRU approaches the intersection in a potentially dangerous situation (lack of visibility, red light). The AI cameras detect the VRU and the CRE detects a situation of high risk of collision. The CRE sends a DENM message to the vehicles approaching he intersection. The CAV reduces speed automatically when receiving the message. A warning is displayed in the HMI of the CV and the driver reduces the speed. Calculate the time from the detection to the reaction, by comparing the timestamps in the logs of the CRE and the logs in the CV and CAVs (or observing the HMI display). Repeat the test multiple times and calculate the average. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	If the reduction with regards to an estimated reaction time for the baseline case is > 20% then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 92: KPI_UC2_7 Softer deceleration reaction in collision risk situations with VRUs.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC2_7-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration
Description	Reduction of the proportion of events of high risk of collision with a VRU for which the CV/CAVs has to make a hard braking.
Context / Use Case	UC2. VRU protection.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Collision Risk Estimator logs (MEC/edge local video processor). CAV/CV On-Board Unit (OBU) logs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Collecting logs from the CRE (to identify the high-risk event) and CAVs/CVs (looking for speeds and acceleration). Calculating the proportion of cases where a hard braking (high deceleration) is registered in the vehicle logs.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Reduction of risk of collision detections for which the reaction of the CV/CAV to avoid the collision implied a hard braking > 20%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_7- Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration
Test purpose	Calculate the reduction of the proportion of events of high risk of collision with a VRU for which the CV/CAVs has to make a hard braking.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • CAVs/CVs with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed (OBU). • PoDIUM equipment installed in the intersection, including an RSU and an Edge computer with PoDIUM software installed (including the Collision Risk estimation functionality). • Cameras with AI functionality for VRU detection installed at the intersection pointing to the potential collision risk areas between vehicles and VRUs.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Each time an event of high risk of collision between a CAV or CV and a VRU is predicted, a DENM messages is received by the vehicle, and the vehicle reduces its speed a significant time interval before the arrival to the potential collision location.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CAV/CVs moves towards the intersection at a speed near the maximum permitted. 2. The CAV/CV sends CAM messages periodically, informing about its position and speed. 3. A VRU approaches the intersection in a potentially dangerous situation (lack of visibility, red light). 4. The AI cameras detect the VRU and the CRE detects a situation of high risk of collision. 5. The CRE sends a DENM message to the vehicles approaching he intersection. 6. The CAV reduces speed automatically when receiving the message. A warning is displayed in the HMI of the CV and the driver reduces the speed. 7. Collect the logs from CRE and the logs from the CV (to identify the high risk of collision events) and the logs from CAVs/CVs (looking for speeds and acceleration).

	<p>8. Repeat the test multiple times and calculate proportion of cases in which a hard braking (high deceleration) is registered in the logs of the vehicle (directly or by dividing speed reduction by time). Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>Calculate the percentage of risk of collision detections for which the reaction of the CV or CAV to avoid the collision implied a hard braking. Compare with the estimated proportion for the baseline case. If the reduction between both cases is > 20% then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 93: KPI_UC3_1 Service Time.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime
Description	<p>Service delivery time (i.e. the reaction time at service layer) from time of incident detection or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, until incident notification of CVs and updated traffic instructions (“manoeuvres”) received by CVs. This KPI refers sets the “pace” of operation within the context of UC3.</p> <p>This time includes communication time, but also internal processing times, according to the following (successive) steps / milestones:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Traffic state perception update time: Period between successive updates of the traffic states generated from the Local TMC, using as input the fusion of data from different sources (traffic cameras, vehicle locations, obstacle/incident data). 2. Incident notification relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives an incident notification. 3. Traffic strategy decision time: Period to calculate and update the global traffic strategy within the Global TMC. 4. Strategy relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection (or other strategy update trigger) until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives the updated TMC traffic strategy (manoeuvre instruction). This is the longest step.
Context / Use Case	UC3.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Local TMC (Edge), Global TMC (cloud), OBUs of the CAV/CVs.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<p>From the time of incident detection (as measured by the event timestamp within the MEC), or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, we will measure the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Traffic state perception update time: Measured via timestamps for each updated “traffic state” within the TMC. 2. Incident notification: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs). 3. Traffic strategy decision time: Measured via timestamps of the Traffic Strategies calculated, stored and emitted by the TMC. 4. Strategy relay: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs).
How to Evaluate	<p>Target values for end-to-end Service delivery / reaction times:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local traffic state perception updated within < 1s. 2. Incident notification received by CAV/CVs in < 2s. 3. Traffic strategy generation updated within < 5s. 4. TMC strategy (manoeuvre instructions) received by CAV/CVs < 6s. <p>Multiple measurements (> 10) will take place in virtual simulation (false triggers in pre-demonstration technical trials), where max values must be achieved every time.</p>
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime
Test purpose	Measure the Service delivery time (i.e. the reaction time at service layer) from time of incident detection or other “trigger” for updating

	<p>the traffic strategy, until incident notification of CVs and updated traffic instructions (“manoeuvres”) received by CVs.</p>
<p>Pre-test conditions</p>	<p>A. Virtual simulation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MEC deployed, operational and connected to internet (incl. TMC, GW, LDM modules). • OBU-stack deployed in lab settings and connected to MEC. <p>B. Validation of the KPI in real conditions on the highway (additional to the above):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OBU hardware and OBU-stack set up in vehicles (e.g. IDIADA). • The CVs are moving along the highway. • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
<p>Expected result (conformance requirements)</p>	<p>The Platform must be able to detect incidents, or other changes in traffic, and generate and dispatch the respective CCAM messages (alerts, traffic strategies) which must be received by the CVs via 5G and/or C-V2X within a targeted timeframe.</p> <p>This KPI detects the “pace” of operation within the context of UC3. This time includes communication time, but also internal processing times:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incident alert relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives an incident notification. Target value: < 2s 2. Strategy relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection (or other strategy update trigger) until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives the updated TMC traffic strategy (maneuver instruction). Target value: < 6s
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<p>Measurement of durations will be calculated, by taking as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting time: the time of incident detection (as measured by the event timestamp within the MEC), or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy. • End times or milestone times: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incident alert: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs). 2. Strategy relay: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs). <p>Multiple measurements (> 10) will take place in virtual simulation (false triggers in pre-demonstration technical trials), where max target values must be achieved every time. Some measurements in real road will take place both through 5G and C-V2X communication channels, to account for latency.</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>If #2 time is <2s and #4 time is < 6s after incident detection by the MEC in at least 80% of the measurements in virtual simulation and in real road, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 94: KPI_UC3_2 Cross-border interruption time.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime
Description	Cross-border interruption time (i.e. avoid interruption of service while switching from one country 5G network to the other). While crossing the France-Spain border, ensure that if connectivity via 5G is interrupted (due to roaming from one country 5G network to the other), then this will be minimal, and be complemented via C-V2X coverage and will not cause any service interruption.
Context / Use Case	UC3.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	France-Spain cross-border segment of the LL highway.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measured through a tool that monitors and logs the connection state of the 5G modem.
How to Evaluate	Multiple measurements to take place during several cross-border crossings (at least 5) with same or different CV/ CAVs via connection monitor log software installed on the OBUs/PCs. Target values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G interruption from one country network to the other is < 1s. • Parallelization of C-V2X connection will allow to have continuous (seamless) connectivity with service interruption time < 500ms.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime
Test purpose	Measure the cross-border interruption time (i.e. avoid interruption of service while switching from one country 5G network to the other). While crossing the France-Spain border, ensure that the 5G connection interruption is minimal, and be complemented via C-V2X coverage and will not cause any significant service interruption.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The platform is operational. • CV/CAV are equipped with OBUs and able to connect to 5G/C-V2X. • RSUs are installed on the highway, operational and connected to the MEC. • Two 5G networks are available, one for each side of the border. • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Seamless connectivity via C-V2X when 5G network service is interrupted on the border section of the highway.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CV/CAV initiates its journey from one side of the border. • The CV/CAV crosses over the border and continues its journey. 5G service is briefly interrupted due to change of network operator. Meanwhile, the CV connects via C-V2X to the platform. • The interruption and reconnection times are logged (based on the messages received in the Gateway from a certain vehicle, as well in the vehicles' OBUs).
Verification criteria	If the connection of the CV/CAV to the MEC is interrupted for < 500ms, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL. Multiple measurements (at least 5) will take place. The result must be PASS in at least 3/5.

Table 95: KPI_UC3_3 Shuttle speed.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed
Description	MILLA's CAV shuttle needs to be capable to achieve 80 km/h in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions.
Context / Use Case	UC3.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	MILLA Shuttle CAV, in a closed circuit and in the selected highway section.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measured via the Shuttle's speed log. First, validated in closed circuit trials. Then this shall be demonstrated on a large stretch of the highway (traffic and safety permitting).
How to Evaluate	Target value: 80 km/h automated driving
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed
Test purpose	Measure MILLA's CAV Shuttle speed and achieve 80 km/h in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This will be validated in a closed circuit in France. Demonstrated on the LL highway in Spain. • For the highway demo: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CAV is fully operational in SAE4 (pre-approved). ○ Highway permits for CAV circulation obtained. ○ The MILLA shuttle is at the origin point of the route, ready to go. ○ Safety driver is in the Shuttle. Safety car(s) is below the shuttle, following along the way. • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	MILLA Shuttle successfully and safely navigating at 80 km/h in SAE4 on the highway.
Test procedure sequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The MILLA shuttle initiates at the origin point of the route, working in AD mode. • When allowed by legal speed limits, it accelerates to 80 km/h automatically. • It arrives to the point of destination. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	If the shuttle reaches 80 km/h in SAE 4, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 96: KPI_UC3_4 Traffic Strategies Implementation.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation
Description	<p>Evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies by the CAV (autonomously) and the CV drivers (manually). The referred traffic strategies that are transmitted to the vehicles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy 1: Reduce max speed (thus avoiding a harder braking later on, increased safety). • Strategy 2: Increase distance from car in front (thus avoiding harder braking, more time for reaction, increased safety). • Strategy 3: Change lane i.e. the car should avoid or prefer such lane.
Context / Use Case	UC3.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Within the vehicles (CV & CAV), and/or in the TMC/LDM.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<p>Once the message is received by the vehicle (via OBU and displayed in the HMI), the CV drivers react based on the indicated strategy (manoeuvre) and the CAVs autonomously implement the indicated strategy.</p> <p>How to monitor:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capturing the timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and displayed in the HMI. • Capturing by the logged speeds of the connected vehicles (CV/CAV), as stored in the TMC/LDM (for strategy 1 only).
How to Evaluate	<p>Target value:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delay of CAVs applying indicated strategy < 5s. • Delay of CV drivers applying indicated strategy < 10s. <p>Note: For lane change, this timing may be longer due to surrounding traffic – the manoeuvre will only take place once it is safe to do so.</p> <p>For each strategy we will sample at least 3 times the manoeuvre with all 4 vehicles (CV and CAV) and calculate the time of reaction of the vehicles. In total 36 samples of all 3 strategy implementation manoeuvres.</p>
Test Case ID	KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation
Test purpose	<p>Evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies by the CAV (autonomously) and the CV drivers (manually). For practical reasons we will only focus on the following traffic strategy that is transmitted to the vehicles, but this has to be repeated for the three strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce max speed to X km/h (speed limit to be defined depending on traffic conditions, below 120 km/h).
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • There are in total 4 vehicle available, with their respective drivers. • Drivers have been briefed about the experiment.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CVs and CAV fully equipped with OBUs and HMIs (tablets/laptops), and connected to internet and C-V2X. • Platform fully operational and connected (MEC), capable of emitting traffic strategies to the vehicles.
<p>Expected result (conformance requirements)</p>	<p>Traffic strategies are successfully implemented by the automated vehicles (CAV) and the connected vehicle drivers (CV), within a reasonable time frame of reaction.</p> <p>Target value, from the moment of reception of the strategy by the vehicles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delay of CAVs applying indicated strategy < 5s. • Delay of CV drivers applying indicated strategy < 10s.
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CVs and CAV circulating on the highway with the respective drivers. • The vehicles receive CCAM messages to reduce their speed, as prescribed by the new speed limit announced by the Platform. • The vehicles react to the new traffic strategy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The CAV reduces speed automatically, without driver intervention. ○ The CV drivers read the message on their in-vehicle HMI screens and slow down their vehicles accordingly. • Data loggers capture the “start and end of manoeuvre”. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Start of manoeuvre: Timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and displayed in the HMI. ○ End of manoeuvre: Timestamp of the Logged speeds of the vehicles (CVs/CAV) as stored in the MEC, when vehicle speed is first-time equal to the new speed limit. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>For each strategy we will trial at least 3 times the manoeuvre with all 4 vehicles (3 CVs and 1 CAV) and calculate the time of reaction of the vehicles. In total 12 samples per strategy implementation manoeuvre.</p> <p>If the strategies are implemented and the manoeuvre (speed reduction) is completed within the targeted reaction times, in at least 2/3 of the trial cases (to account for human error), while the other cases not having a very significant deviation or grave issue of implementation (e.g. messages not received, delays in transmission), then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 97: KPI_UC4_1 VIMA detection performance.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance
Description	<p>Performance of VRU Intersection Movement Assist (VIMA) application against false positive/negative.</p> <p>The VIMA application provides the connected and automated vehicle/driver with a warning and a time window to wait, based on VRU detection. Reliability of this service will be assessed.</p>
Context / Use Case	UC4.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In the CAV.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<p>Perform use case in different scenarios/trials with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected positive = Scenarios in which the system is expected to give a warning and a time to wait indication because the VRU is about to cross and conflicting with vehicle trajectory. • Expected negative = Scenarios in which the system should NOT give any warning or indication because VRU is not about to cross or not conflicting with vehicle trajectory (tested to check for any false warning). <p>Collect data and check true positive/negative, false positive/negative.</p>
How to Evaluate	<p>Compute the following performance indicators (PI) and compare them with target values.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PI1: True positive rate (probability of detection): true positives over total expected positives. • PI2: True negative rate (1 - false positive rate) is the number of true negative over total expected negatives. <p>Target value: For the current prototype implementation, the target is to have at least 90% of each PI, which in practice means a tolerance of 10% error.</p>
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance
Test purpose	Measure the performance of VRU detection by the Podium system, in terms of true positives/negatives.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAV, PoDIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational. • Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads. • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>CAV performs the following scenarios, with expected results:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. Straight pass – expected negative (no warning: VRU is still). 1.2. Straight warn – expected positive (warning: VRU violates red). 2.1. Right Turn with precedence management – expected positive (information: VRU is going to cross first). 2.2. Right Turn with sudden crossing – expected positive (warning: imminent VRU crossing). 3.1. Left turn - expected positive (information: VRU and other cars' are going to cross first). <p>Trials are repeated for each scenario with:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CPM only (infrastructure detections then processed by CAV to give indications). • DENM/IVIM only (infrastructure-based warnings/indications). • CPM+DENM/IVIM (combination of the former strategies). <p>The expectation is that the three methods give slightly different results and that the last one (combination) sums the benefits of the former ones.</p>
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run scenario in a controlled way for CAV and VRU (but in open traffic) according to the step-by-step description, with Podium system activated. 2. Check and annotate the HMI warnings on CAV. In parallel collect data logs. 3. Classify the true/false positive/negatives from annotation - note: this step helps spotting and isolating the most evident faults. 4. Verify the true/false positive/negatives from data logs - note: this step thoroughly checks and helps spotting any other faults, maybe not evident by HMI (e.g. stray warnings, or inaccurate warnings not noticed live during the trials). 5. Calculate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PI1: True positive rate (probability of detection): true positives over total expected positives. • PI2: True negative rate (1 - false positive rate) is the number of true negative over total expected negatives. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>If the applicable PI (depending on the expected positive/negative) in each scenario are > 90%, then the test is a PASS for this prototype verification stage, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>Note: product validation requires higher percentages.</p>

Table 98: KPI_UC4_2 Vehicle position accuracy in urban scenario.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban
Description	<p>CAV positioning accuracy at the intersection.</p> <p>Advisory depends on lane-level position and direction, thus matching of vehicle position and trajectory to the local topology is crucial. Lane level accuracy (1.5 m) is at least needed to interpret the advisory information, but sub-meter accuracy (0.1 m, 0.2 m tolerated) is recommended for collective perception applied to highly automated driving.</p>
Context / Use Case	UC4. Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In the CAV.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle (both receiving and transmitting) within 2 sigma (95%) in open sky, with at least 7 satellites in view, and elevation mask set to 5°.
How to Evaluate	Target values: Accuracy with RTK correction < 0.2 m. Accuracy without RTK correction < 1.5 m.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban
Test purpose	Measure the positioning accuracy of the CAV throughout the scenarios.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • CAV operational in UC4 scenarios. • PoDIUM platform service and infrast. equipped and operational. • Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>CAV is capable of self-localizing in-lane and lane-level accuracy is expected in most of the tests.</p> <p>The addition of RTK is expected to yield sub-meter accuracy. Outliers should be mainly due to poor GNSS signals. The latter cases may degrade or even compromise scenario functionality.</p>
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every time scenarios are run, record positioning data (including confidence ellipse and number of satellites in view), along with the Use Case functionality data (e.g. manoeuvre, HMI, etc.). 2. Compute average positioning accuracy during scenario trials, measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle over the entire duration of each trial. 3. In post-processing, compare positioning accuracy results with use case functionality and performance. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>If during the 95% of the time, the accuracy with RTK correction is < 0.2 m, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>If during the 95% of the time, the accuracy without RTK correction < 1.5 m, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>The percentage is calculated over the sampled position data in time span of each trial.</p> <p>Outlier cases (not passed) should be analysed against use case functionality and performance in those specific conditions (along with context information, such as number of satellites, etc.).</p>

Table 99: KPI_UC4_3 VIMA crossing manoeuvre optimization.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_optimization
Description	<p>VIMA suggestions should lead to optimal manoeuvres to cross the intersection. VIMA application provides warning and a time window to wait based on VRU detection. The hypotheses are that, with Podium system active (with respect to inactive) the vehicle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should react in advance (start deceleration manoeuvre). • Should wait a similar time slot. • Should have a smoother speed profile. <p>In the Living Lab, manoeuvres will be addressed with manual driving and HMI recommendations.</p>
Context / Use Case	UC4. Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In the CAV.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baseline: VRU crossing trial with system on, no HMI. Podium system runs in background in order to record the scene (vehicle and VRU crossing). • Treatment: VRU crossing trial with Podium system on and HMI with driving recommendation (which would mean CAV actuation). <p>This is applicable to all scenarios involving VIMA IVIM (which include the information that a VRU is crossing). Measure and compare baseline/treatment.</p>
How to Evaluate	<p>Evaluation based on baseline vs treatment comparison. In particular, Podium system should yield < +/-20% deviation in total time to cross.</p> <p>Target values: Reaction time advance (treatment/baseline) > 10%. Reduction in maximum acceleration/deceleration values > 10% .</p>
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_optimization
Test purpose	Evaluate Podium VIMA application (managing precedence at crossroads) in terms of impact on crossing manoeuvres.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • CAV operational in UC4 scenarios. • PoDIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational. • Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>With respect to a non-assisted crossing, the expectation is that the VIMA-assisted crossing yields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar waiting times for CAV to cross: not much higher, not much lower. • Anticipated reactions, in terms of time/space when vehicle starts braking/accelerating.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smoother speed profile during the whole crossing.
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<p>The KPI is applicable to the following test scenarios: 2.1. Right Turn with precedence management. 3.1. Left turn.</p> <p>Trials here are divided in baseline and treatment [8]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baseline: VRU crossing trial with system on, and no HMI. • Treatment: VRU crossing trial with Podium system active and HMI with driving recommendation (as CAV automated control is not foreseen in UC4). <p>Since Podium system records a lot of data during the use case, it is advised, even in the baseline, to run Podium system “as is” in background, in order to record the scene. This is useful for checking vehicle and VRU crossing, as well as context information (e.g. traffic) and for making sure that the treatment recordings were done in similar conditions as the baseline ones.</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the test and record manoeuvre data 2. Analyse data comparing treatment and baseline, addressing in particular: manoeuvre start time (vehicle starts decelerating), maximum acceleration/deceleration values, manoeuvre timing. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>Positive impact on manoeuvre is evaluated if results yield < +/-20% deviation in total time to cross.</p> <p>If reaction time advance (treatment/baseline) > 10%, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>If reduction in maximum acceleration/deceleration values > 10%, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p>

Table 100: KPI_UC4_4 VIMA timing.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing
Description	End-to-end reaction time from VRU collision risk detection at RSU until notification at CAV. VIMA, an edge-computing-based application informing of VRU presence at an intersection, should at least perform as good as an Intersection Collision Risk Warning (ICRW) application, as in [9].
Context / Use Case	UC4. Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At all the involved components.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Reaction time will be measured from timestamps. Since the tracking of each piece of information at each step may be difficult to achieve, the mean values of the five following steps will be measured and then summed up: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. At RSU, timing of VRU crossing detection application. 2. Latency of RSU-MEC communication. 3. At MEC, timing of digital twin and VIMA application. 4. Latency of MEC-CAV communication. 5. Timing of CAV application.
How to Evaluate	Target value: VIMA timing < 300 ms. The aforementioned ETSI document sets a requirement of 300 ms delay overall as maximum. Transposed to VIMA, for comparison, the sum of steps 1 to 5 above should not exceed 300 ms.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing
Test purpose	Test if the end-to-end reaction time from hazard detection at RSU until actuation/warning at CAV is enough.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials. • CAV operational in UC4 scenarios. • PoDIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational. • Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	It is expected that for safety scenarios (VRU collision risk warning) the CAV is timely warned, conforming to the ETSI standard requirement for Intersection Collision Risk Warning (ICRW) application [9].
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run scenarios based on DENM and CPM, which are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2. Straight warn (VRU violates red). 2.2. Right Turn with sudden crossing (VRU crosses). 2. Consider the mean values of the five following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. At RSU, timing of VRU crossing detection application. 2. Latency of RSU-MEC communication. 3. At MEC, timing of digital twin and VIMA application. 4. Latency of MEC-CAV communication. 5. Timing of CAV application. 3. Sum the mean values to obtain an estimate of the end-to-end latency.
Verification criteria	If the derived end-to-end latency is < 300 ms, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.

Table 101: KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle position accuracy in highway scenario.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway
Description	<p>CAV positioning accuracy on the highway. Warning and cooperative assistive/automated functions (e.g. C-ACC) can be defined up to the lane-level, along the highway (e.g. lane closure information). The CAV must be capable of understanding which lane it finds itself, meaning accuracy in positioning has to be < 1.5 m. Furthermore, outside the tunnel, the CAV can avail of sub-meter accuracy thanks to RTK corrections. Sub meter accuracy (0.1 m - 0.2 m tolerated) is one of the enabling factors of highly automated driving Operational Design Domain (ODD).</p>
Context / Use Case	UC5. Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In the CAV.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<p>Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle (both receiving and transmitting) within 2 sigma (95%):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In open sky, with at least 7 satellites in view, and elevation mask set to 5°. In tunnel with the two positioning solutions (trilateration and GPS signal creation).
How to Evaluate	<p>Target values:</p> <p>Outside the tunnel, accuracy with RTK correction < 0.2 m. Outside the tunnel, accuracy without RTK correction < 1.5 m. Inside the tunnel, accuracy < 1.5 m.</p>
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway
Test purpose	Measure the positioning accuracy of the CAV throughout the highway scenarios, inside the tunnel, compared to outside.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAV (and CV where applicable) operational in UC5 scenarios. A single technical solution for GNSS is operational in the tunnel: SDR or trilateration (they must NOT be available both at the same time). Infrastructure C-ITS warning messages available. Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	CAV is capable of self-localizing in-lane and the accuracy is sufficient for the use case purpose. A degradation performance is expected in the tunnel, sometimes yielding a positioning which is not at lane level. The latter situations are expected to impact considerably on C-ACC availability and on the ODD for AD L3 and L4 in presence of risk in the tunnel (DENM), less on the warning type scenario (scenarios 1.1, 2).
Test procedure sequence	<p>Positioning is the focus of UC5 at CAV. This KPI is applicable to all scenarios:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. RWW single vehicle 1.2. RWW and C-ACC follow 1.3. RWW and C-ACC cut-in 2. Traffic Jam Warning 3.1. AD keeps within ODD 3.2. AD exits the ODD <p>Furthermore, each should be repeated in 4 different conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outside tunnel.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inside tunnel with no positioning infrastructure (dead reckoning at CAV, only). • Inside tunnel with positioning infrastructure based on software defined radio (SDR). • Inside tunnel with positioning infrastructure based on V2X (trilateration-based positioning). <p>Note: the two positioning solutions must be tested separate (only SDR or only trilateration).</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every time scenarios are run, record positioning data along with the Use Case functionality data (e.g. manoeuvre, HMI, etc.). 2. Compute average positioning accuracy during scenario trials, Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle 3. Evaluate positioning accuracy results against use case functionality. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>If during the 95% of the time, the accuracy with RTK correction outside the tunnel is < 0.2 m, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>If during the 95% of the time, the accuracy without RTK correction outside the tunnel < 1.5 m, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>If during the 95% of the time, the accuracy inside the tunnel < 1.5 m, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>Percentage should be calculated over the samples in the test run, distinguishing inside from outside samples.</p> <p>Outlier cases (not passed) should be evaluated against use case functionality (along with context information, such as number of satellites, etc.) to check the causes, impact and whether some cases can be tolerated by the application.</p>

Table 102: KPI_UC5_2 Vehicle counting accuracy.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy
Description	<p>Accuracy percentage in the vehicles counting by entities that have this capability in Podium UC5.</p> <p>UC5 aims at improving the Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel. Among the monitoring sources, dedicated vehicle counters developed within the Project are installed in the tunnel and interfaced with the Digital twin system, to support the Risk Assessment module. Vehicles are counted and classified by its category (motorbike, car, bus or truck).</p> <p>Furthermore, vehicles are equipped with sensors detecting other road users. While the detection itself is not affected by the tunnel, when the vehicles' position comes into play, the lack of GNSS is expected to have an impact. For instance when matching objects of CPM received with the same objects detected by sensors (an object may be counted twice if not correctly matched).</p>
Context / Use Case	UC5. Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In MEC and back-end.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure vehicle counting per time period (e.g. in one hour) at the tunnel. • Compare it to the measurement of the system already in place on the A22. • Calculate the deviation target.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Deviation per each category < 10%.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy
Test purpose	Measure the accuracy percentage in the vehicles counting by roadside sensors.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAV, CV and vehicle counting roadside sensors operational in UC5 scenarios. • Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Vehicle counting is affected by the conditions but does not impact on risk management.
Test procedure sequence	<p>This KPI is applicable to all scenarios.</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every time scenarios are run, record infrastructure counting. 2. Compare measurements with the ground truth. 3. Evaluate deviation effects against use case functionality. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	If deviations are < 10%, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL. Higher deviations will be evaluated against use case functionality.

Table 103: KPI_UC5_3 Extended perception accuracy.

KPI Identifier	KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy
Description	Accuracy in perceiving vehicles in front. Vehicles are equipped with sensors detecting other road users. CAV and CV exchange detected vehicles in front through CPM. GNSS degradation as well as V2V communication latency is expected to have an impact, when matching/tracking objects of CPM received with the same objects detected by sensors.
Context / Use Case	UC5. Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In CAV/CV.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compare received CPM measurement with sensors object coordinates. Calculate the deviation against positioning accuracy degradation (confidence ellipse increasing) and communication lags (latency). Check the capability of object tracking by the data fusion module, depending on the deviation. Perform multiple tests over several traffic conditions, to obtain a significant and diversified number of cases.
How to Evaluate	Target value: Deviation tolerance (V2V with respect to sensors) < 10 %. The actual tolerance will be evaluated a posteriori, depending on the object tracking effectiveness which in turn depends on detected cases.
Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy
Test purpose	Measure the accuracy % in the vehicles counting by roadside sensors.
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAV and CV exchange detected vehicles in front through CPM. Use case partners have all necessary permits for execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Extended perception is degraded in GNSS denied environment, but the effect does not impact on cooperative and automated manoeuvres.
Test procedure sequence	<p>This KPI is applicable to the following scenarios:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> AD keeps within ODD. AD exits the ODD. <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Record CPM and detections by the on-board sensors. Analyse object matching in the vehicle's LDM, selecting those objects that were detected both by communication (CPM) and by on board sensors. Calculate the wrong/missed matches, against positioning accuracy degradation (confidence ellipse increasing) and communication lags (latency). <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>If deviation tolerance (V2V with respect to sensors) is < 10%, then the test is a PASS, otherwise is a FAIL.</p> <p>The actual tolerance will be evaluated a posteriori, depending on the object tracking effectiveness which in turn depends on the detected cases.</p>